

Title: The vertical Generation Theory of natural numbers

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【Abstract】: This paper constructs an iterative Diophantine equation $3x_{i+1} + 1 = x_i * 2^k$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}, x_i \in \text{odd}$). All odd numbers within i -th order pure odd number collate iterations can be found by these equations.

And also discovered the n -th-order tiling functions $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ for odd numbers, and construct

the continuous extended interval $I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}$). Using the 1-order tiling function $f^1(x) = 4x+1$,

all odd numbers within the parent extended interval I_k can be mapped one-to-one to the subextended interval I_{k+1} (a global-to-local bijection), while maintaining the invariance of their counts of pure odd iterations. Convergence by the reverse pure odd number collatz iterations process is rigorously proven, thereby proving that collatz's reverse iterations covers all odd numbers. An explicit upper bound function for the number of pure odd iterations of all odd numbers within the extended interval, with an estimation accuracy approaching 99.999% when the extended interval close to 10^{25} . A hailstone formula for odd numbers is given, with oscillation amplitudes accurately determined to zero error. And then establishes a theory for the vertical generation of natural numbers.

【keywords】 1. The pure odd number iterated Diophantine equation $3x_{i+1} + 1 = x_i * 2^k$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}, x_i \in \text{odd}$) and its positive integers; 2. The n -th-order tiling function: $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ and its inverse function:

$f^n(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$ (until $\frac{x-1}{4}$ is odd number); 3. The tiling odd numbers ($x_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$) and the seed odd

numbers ($x_i \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$); 4. The continuously extended interval: $I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$. 5. ($x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$) is the non-reproductive odd numbers; $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ is the expansive reproduction odd numbers; $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ is the contractive reproduction odd numbers; 6. The counts of hailstone amplitude formula for an odd number; 7. The convergence Theorem for Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations. 8. The upper bound function for estimation counts of pure odd number iterations on the extended interval I_k ; 9. For one time iteration there are three modes of reproductions:

$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1}$ does not exist ("non-reproduction", only tiling)

$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; ("expansion reproduction")

$$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}; (\text{"contraction reproduction"})$$

10. The Vertical Generation mode of Natural Numbers.

【 Introduction 】 1. The research direction of this paper: Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations. 2. The research contents:

Generation mode of Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations; The differences and relationships between the Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations and forward iterations; The Vertical Generation mode of Natural Numbers. 3. Limitations of the current research Collatz conjecture: Did not distinguish between even iterations from odd iterations; Did not distinguish between pure odd number reverse iterations and forward iterations; 4. The current gap in mathematical research on this topic is that while it has been discovered that many odd numbers share the same "collatz predecessors of odd numbers" no characteristics have yet been identified for these odd numbers with common "collatz predecessors of odd numbers". The characteristics of odd numbers within same "collatz predecessors of

odd numbers" could be obtained through The n-th-order tiling function: $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$, and the same "collatz predecessors of odd numbers" is seed number, these odd numbers are the tiling odd numbers. 5. In this paper the innovative aspects of this research are as follows: ① Constructs an iterative Diophantine equations $3x_{i+1} + 1 = x_i * 2^k$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}, x_i \in \text{odd}$), All of odd numbers within i-th order pure odd number collate iterations can be find by these equations. ② Discovered the n-th-order tiling functions $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ for odd numbers and its inverse function: $f^{-n}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$ (until $\frac{x-1}{4}$ is odd number);

③ Construct the continuous extended interval $I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}$). Using the 1-order tiling function $f^1(x) = 4x+1$, all odd numbers within the parent extended interval I_k can be mapped one-to-one to the subextended interval I_{k+1} (a global-to-local bijection), while maintain the invariance of their counts of pure odd iterations. ④ All odd numbers are classified by modulo 3 to three modes: "non-reproduction odd numbers and only tilinging"; "expansion reproduction odd numbers"; "contraction reproduction odd numbers". ⑤ All odd numbers are classified by modulo 8 to two modes: The tilinging odd numbers ($x_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$) and the seed odd numbers ($x_i \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$); ⑥ It is different between the reproduction and tilinging of wheat, It is also different between the reproduction and tilinging of odd numbers, on this point it similar to wheat. The research shows the difference between pure odd number reverse iterations and forward iterations is: It contain of type " $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ " odd numbers on the reverse iterations; but It do not contain of type " $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ " odd numbers on the forward iterations; since the type " $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ " odd numbers is "non-reproduction odd numbers and only tilinging", so it appear on the reverse iterations path but can not appear on the forward iterations path. ⑦ A three-step iterative method for constructing a purely odd reverse

generation system was developed: The first step tilinging \rightarrow By tilinging function: $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty$); The second step filtering \rightarrow Classify according to the remainder modulo 3 for filtering: $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$; Select the odd numbers that can continue iterating and reproducing: $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$; as well as the ultimate iterative odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. The third step reproduction \rightarrow For the odd numbers that can continue reproduced:

$$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}; \text{("expansion reproduction")}$$

$$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}; \text{("contraction reproduction")}$$

For the ultimate iterative odd numbers :By the leaf function: $L(x)=x*2^k(k \in \mathbb{N},k \rightarrow \infty)$,Generating the even numbers , $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_i * 2^k(k \in \mathbb{N},k \rightarrow \infty)$.Then repeat the three steps.③The convergence Theorem for Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations Proved⑨Present the count of hailstone amplitude formula for an odd number through every times iteration⑩Present An explicit upper bound function for the number of pure odd iterations of all odd numbers within the extended interval, with an estimation accuracy approaching 100%.⑪The key find: In the vertical generation of natural numbers, the generating functions:"contractive reproduction":

$$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3} \text{ (} x_i \text{ is the seed odd number, and: } x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \text{) ; expansion reproduction : } x_{i+1} =$$

$$\frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3} \text{ (} x_i \text{ is the seed odd number, and: } x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \text{) and: leaf function: } L(x)=x*2^k \text{ (where } x \text{ is an odd}$$

number, $k \in \mathbb{N},k \rightarrow \infty$) are precisely inverse functions to the two functions : $f(x)=3x+1$ (x is an odd number) and $L^{-1}(x)=\frac{x}{2^k}$ (x is an even number ,until $\frac{x}{2^k}$ is odd number) in Collatz's forward iteration.⑫collatz inverse Iteration seed odd numbers Closed Theorem 2): In the inverse iteration path of the seed odd number until it returns to "1", All the odd numbers generated by the inverse iteration form a closed set, and they all belong to the same algebraic topological space associated with that seed odd number. The algebraic topological spaces generated by different seed odd numbers are disjoint from each other, meaning their elements are pairwise distinct.Key proofs and Key discoveries:① 【The converse proposition of the range theorem of next reproductive iterations】.If tow odd numbers is the pair $(m,2m+1)$,Their counts of pure odd number iterations is equal.The probability that this converse proposition holds increases as the number of iterations increases. that the probability of the converse proposition holding increases as the data size grows, eventually approaching 100%.

②The theorem of Mersenne numbers's Iterative trend and Characteristics

③The theorem on the iterative pattern of Mersenne numbers with base 3

④If "k" consecutive odd numbers have the same count steps of pure odd Collatz iterations, then we call them "k consecutive odd numbers have the same count steps of pure odd Collatz iterations Synchronized collatz iteration Cluster", with the number of iterations being "i", abbreviated as "k-c". "56-c"=(24455665,24455775),its count of pure odd number iterations is 79.

⑤ 【Theorem】 : Any prime number is not the largest counts of pure odd number iterations in an algebraic topological space of a seed number .although prime numbers are special cases of odd numbers, they do not exhibit any special structures or characteristics in the iteration process involving purely odd numbers.the rules governing the Kolatz iteration of prime numbers are the same as those for ordinary odd numbers. ⑥The fastest pure iterations odd numbers within the extended interval

must be the seed odd numbers can not be the tillering odd numbers.

Chapter 1: Iterated Diophantine equations and its positive integer

【Definition】: We call an Iterated Diophantine equation: $3x+1=2^k(k \in \mathbb{N})$. We call an $(i+1)$ -th Iterated Diophantine equation: $3x_{i+1}+1=x_i \cdot 2^k(k \in \mathbb{N}, x_i \in \text{odd})$

Section 1: 1-th Iterated Diophantine equation: $3x_1+1=2^k(k \in \mathbb{N})$ And its positive integer solution

(1) **【Existence Theorem of Solutions for Iterative Diophantine Equation】**

$$\because 3x_1+1=2^k(k \in \mathbb{N}) \therefore x_1 = \frac{2^k-1}{3}$$

$$\because \forall k \in \mathbb{N}, 4^n \in \text{even},$$

$$\because 4 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore 4^n \equiv 1^n \pmod{3}, \therefore 1^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore 4^n - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$$

$$\text{Let: } k=2n, (n \in \mathbb{N}), \text{ Then: } x_1 = \frac{2^k-1}{3} = \frac{2^{2n}-1}{3} = \frac{4^n-1}{3}$$

$$\therefore x_1 = \frac{4^n-1}{3} \text{ is a positive integer.}$$

$$\therefore \text{When } k \text{ is an even integer, } \exists x_1 \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

$$\because \text{Odd} \times \text{Odd} = \text{Odd}, 3 \text{ is an odd}, (4^n-1) \text{ is an odd},$$

$$\therefore 3x_1 = (4^n-1), \therefore x_1 \text{ is an odd integer.}$$

$$\therefore \text{When } k \text{ is an even integer, } \exists x_1 = \frac{4^n-1}{3} (n \in \mathbb{N}) \text{ is an odd integer.}$$

(2) **【Infinity theorem on the number of solutions】**

$$\because n \in \mathbb{N}, \therefore n=0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,\dots \rightarrow \infty$$

\therefore There are countless positive integer solutions.

such as $x_1 = 1, 5, 21, 85, 341, 1365, 5461, 21845, 87381, 349525, 1398101, 5592405, 22369621, 89478485, 357913941, \dots$

We represent these infinite positive integer solutions with the symbol $x_{1,i}$, Here “1” denotes the first iteration, and “i” denotes the serial number of the solution to the equation.

Since there are countless iteration solutions, sometimes we use the symbol “ x_1 ” to represent any 1-th iterated solution in order to express it simply.

(3) **【A one-to-one correspondence theorem between the solution of the iterative Diophantine equation and the terms of the recurrence sequence : $a_n=4a_{n-1}+1$ 】**

$$\therefore 3x_1 = (4^n - 1),$$

$$\therefore x_{1, i} = \frac{4^m - 1}{3} = \frac{4 * 4^{m-1} - 1}{3} = 4 * \frac{4^{m-1} - 1}{3} + 1 = 4 * x_{1, i-1} + 1$$

$$\therefore x_{1, i} = 4 * x_{1, i-1} + 1$$

Because the general term formula of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ is $a_n = \frac{3 * 1 + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$, (where $n \in \mathbb{N}, a_0 = 1$ is the first term) by the generating function method. all 1-th iterated solutions x_1 are all terms of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ with $a_0 = 1$ as the first term. This general term formula is exactly the same as the general expression for solutions to the iterative Diophantine equation.

Reverse proof: Insert 1-th iterated solution into the recurrence formula: $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$

$$4x_{1, i+1} + 1 = 4 * \frac{4^m - 1}{3} + 1 = \frac{4^{m+1} - 1}{3} + 1 = 4x_{1, i+1}$$

$$\therefore 4x_{1, i+1} = 4x_{1, i+1}$$

(4) **【4x+1 Theorem:】** The solutions of the iterative Diophantine equation are all terms of the recurrence sequence; conversely, the terms of the recurrence sequence are all solutions of the iterative Diophantine equation.

(5) **【A Regularity Theorem with Residues Modulo 3 for Solutions of the 1-th iterated Diophantine Equations】**

Among the countless odd solutions to the Diophantine equation in the same iteration, they are all arranged in the order of $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ according to the magnitude of the exponent "n", without any omissions or duplication. The even numbers of the same iteration corresponding to them are all $1 * 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Proof:

$$\therefore O_1 = \{x_1 \mid x_1 = \frac{4^n - 1}{3}, n \in \mathbb{N}, n \text{ from } 0\}$$

$$\therefore \forall x \in O_1, \text{ Since } 4x+1 \text{ Theorem, Let: } x_1 = m \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

$$m = 3t + 1 \quad (t \in \mathbb{N}), \text{ Then: } 4m + 1 = 4(3t + 1) + 1 = 12t + 5,$$

$$\therefore (12t + 5) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \text{ Then: } 4(12t + 5) + 1 = 48t + 21$$

$$\therefore (48t + 21) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \text{ Then: } 4(48t + 21) + 1 = 192t + 64,$$

$\therefore (192t + 64) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \dots$ In this way, the rotation cycle follows the rule of $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

For $E_0 = \{e_0 \mid e_0 = 4^n, n \in \mathbb{N}, n \text{ from } 0\}$,

$\therefore \forall x \in O_1$ The elements in the set are distributed regularly according to $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, cycle according to the order from small to large exponent n .

$\forall x \in E_0, 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

【For example】 :

$\therefore x_0 = 1$,

\therefore Let: $3x_1 + 1 = x_0 * 2^m$

$\therefore x_1 = 1, m = 2$; (Here m takes the smallest exponent)

$X_1 = 1$	n	$x_{1,2+2n} = \frac{(3 * 1 + 1) * 4^{n - \frac{1}{3}}}{3}$	$a_{0,0} * 2^{m+2n}$ $(n \in \mathbb{N}), m = 2$ $a_{0,0} = 1$	different fall ($\div 2$) numbers
i=1		$(n \in \mathbb{N})$ Let: $a_{1,0} = 1$		
i-1=0	0	1	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=2$
i-1=0	1	5 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=4$
i-1=0	2	21 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=6$
i-1=0	3	85 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=8$
i-1=0	4	341 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=10$
i-1=0	5	1365 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=12$
i-1=0	6	5461 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=14$
i-1=0	7	21845 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=16$
i-1=0	8	87381 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=18$
i-1=0	9	349525 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=20$
i-1=0	10	1398101 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=22$
i-1=0	11	5592405 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=24$
i-1=0	12	22369621 $*3+1=$	$1 * 2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=26$

i-1=0	13	89478485	*3+1=	$1*2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=28$
i-1=0	14	357913941	*3+1=	$1*2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=30$
i-1=0	15	1431655765	*3+1=	$1*2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=32$
i-1=0	16	5726623061	*3+1=	$1*2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=34$
i-1=0	17	22906492245	*3+1=	$1*2^{2+2n}$	$2+2n=36$
i-1=0		$1*2^{2+2n}$
i-1=0	∞		$1*2^{2+2\infty}$	$2+2\times\infty$

Section 2: 2-th Iterated Diophantine equation: $3x_2+1=x_1*2^k(x_1 \in \text{odd}, k \in \mathbb{N})$ And its positive integer solution

(1) **【Existence Theorem of Solutions for 2-th iterated Diophantine Equation】**

$$\therefore 3x_2+1=x_1*2^k(x_1 \in \text{odd}, k \in \mathbb{N})$$

$$\therefore x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^k - 1}{3}$$

•When $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, k is an even integer,

Let: $x_1 = 3m+1, k=2n, m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N}$, Then:

$$x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^k - 1}{3} = \frac{(3m+1) * 2^{2n} - 1}{3} = \frac{(3m+1) * 4^n - 1}{3} = \frac{3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1}{3}$$

$$\therefore \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N},$$

$$\therefore 3m * 4^n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

$$\therefore (3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}.$$

$$\therefore x_2 = \frac{3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1}{3} \text{ is a positive integer}$$

$$\therefore \text{When } x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, k \text{ is an even integer, } \exists x_2 \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

$$\therefore \text{Odd} \times \text{Odd} = \text{Odd}, 3 \text{ is an odd integer, } (3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1) \text{ is an odd integer,}$$

$$\therefore 3x_2 = (3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1), \therefore x_2 \text{ is an odd integer.}$$

$$\therefore \text{When } x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, k \text{ is an even integer, } \exists x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^k - 1}{3} \text{ is an odd.}$$

••When $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, k is an odd integer,

Let: $x_1 = 3m+2$, $k=2n+1$, ($m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N}$), Then:

$$x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^{k-1}}{3} = \frac{(3m+2) * 2^{2n+1-1}}{3} = \frac{(3m+2) * 2 * 4^n - 1}{3} = \frac{3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^n - 1}{3}$$

∴ $\forall m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

∴ $3m * 2 * 4^n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $4 * 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

∴ $(3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^n - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

∴ $x_2 = \frac{3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^n - 1}{3}$ is a positive integer

∴ When $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, k is an odd integer, $\exists x_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$.

∴ Odd \times Odd = Odd, 3 is an odd integer, $(3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^n - 1)$ is an odd integer,

∴ $3x_2 = (3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^n - 1)$, ∴ x_2 is an odd integer.

∴ When $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, k is an odd, $\exists x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^{k-1}}{3}$ is an odd integer.

••When $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, k is any positive integer ,

Let: $x_1 = 3m$, k is any positive integer, ($m \in \mathbb{Z}, k \in \mathbb{N}$), Then:

$$x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^{k-1}}{3} = \frac{3m * 2^{k-1}}{3}$$

∴ $\forall m \in \mathbb{Z}, k$ is any positive integer,

∴ $(3m * 2^{k-1}) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$,

∴ $x_2 = \frac{3m * 2^{k-1}}{3}$ can not be a positive integer

∴ When $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, k is any positive integer,

$\nexists x_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$.

∴ Equation $3x_2+1 = x_1 * 2^k$ has no positive integer solution

The summary is as follows: For 2-th iterated Diophantine Equation $3x_2+1 = x_1 * 2^k$, when $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and “ k ” are all even numbers, there are positive integer solution; when $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and “ k ” are all odd numbers, there are positive integer solution; when $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and “ k ” are any positive integer, the equation has no positive integer solution.

(2) **【Infinity theorem on the number of 2-th Iterative solutions】**

∴ There are countless positive 1-th Iterative solutions

And $k \in \mathbb{N}$, ∴ $k=0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,\dots \rightarrow \infty$

∴ There are countless positive 2-th Iterative solutions

such as When: $x_1=5$,

$x_2=3,13,53,213,853,3413,13653,54613,218453,873813,\dots$

When: $x_1=85$,

$x_2=113,453,1813,7253,29013,116053,464213,1856853,\dots$

When: $x_1=341$,

$x_2=227,909,3637,14549,58197,232789,931157,3724629,\dots$

When: $x_1=21845$,

$x_2=14563,58253,233013,932053,3728213,14912853,\dots$

When: $x_1=3495253$,

$x_2=4660337,18641349,74565397,298261589,1193046357,\dots$

When: $x_1=57266230613$,

$x_2=38177487075,152709948301,610839793205,2443359172821,\dots$

When: $x_1=916259686981$,

$x_2=122167958641,488671834565,1954687338261,7818749353045,\dots$

When: $x_1=21,1365,87381,5592405,357913941,22906492245,\dots \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ There is no 2-th iteration solution x_2

(3) **【A one-to-one correspondence theorem between the solution of the iterative Diophantine equation and the terms of the recurrence sequence : $a_n=4a_{n-1}+1$ 】**

∴ $3x_2+1=x_1*2^k$ ($x_1 \in \text{odd}, k \in \mathbb{N}$)

$$\therefore x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2^k - 1}{3}$$

$$\therefore x_{2,i} = \frac{x_1 * 2^k - 1}{3} = \frac{4 * x_1 * 2^{k-2} - 1}{3} = 4 * \frac{x_1 * 2^{k-2} - 1}{3} + 1$$

$$\therefore x_{2,i} = 4x_{2,i-1} + 1$$

Because the general term formula of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ is $a_n = \frac{3x_{1,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$, (where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x_{2,0}$ is the first term) by the generating function method. all 2-th iterated solutions x_2 are all terms of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ with $x_{2,0}$ as the first term. This general term formula is exactly the same as the general expression for solutions to the iterative Diophantine equation.

Reverse proof: Insert 2-th iterated solution into the recurrence formula: $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$

$$\therefore x_{2,i} = \frac{x_1 * 2^{k-1}}{3}$$

$$\therefore 4x_{2,i} + 1 = 4 * \frac{x_1 * 2^{k-1}}{3} + 1 = \frac{x_1 * 2^{k+2-1}}{3} + 1 = x_{2,i+1}$$

$$\therefore 4x_{2,i} + 1 = x_{2,i+1}$$

(4) **【 $4x+1$ Theorem:】** The solutions of the 2-th iterated Diophantine Equation are all terms of the recurrence sequence; conversely, the terms of the recurrence sequence are all solutions of the 2-th the iterative Diophantine equation.

Because the general term formula of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ is $a_n = \frac{3x_{2,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$, (where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x_{2,0}$ is the first term) by the generating function method. all 2-th iterates solutions x_2 are all terms of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ with $x_{2,0}$ as the first term.

$$\therefore x_2 = \frac{3x_{1,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}, \text{ (where } n \in \mathbb{N}, x_{1,0} \text{ is the first term)}$$

(5) **【A Regularity Theorem with Residues Modulo 3 for Solutions of the 2-th iterated Diophantine Equations】**

Among the countless odd solutions to the Diophantine equation in the same iteration, they are all arranged in the order of $x_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_2 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ according to the magnitude of the exponent “n”, without any omissions or duplication.

Proof:

$$\therefore O_2 = \{x_2 \mid x_2 = \frac{3x_{1,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}, x_{1,0} \in \text{odd}, n \in \mathbb{N}, n \text{ from } 0\}$$

$$\therefore \forall x \in O_2, \text{ Since } 4x+1 \text{ Theorem, Let: } x_2 = m \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

$$m = 3t + 1 \text{ (} t \in \mathbb{N}\text{), Then: } 4m + 1 = 4(3t + 1) + 1 = 12t + 5,$$

$$\therefore (12t + 5) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \text{ Then: } 4(12t + 5) + 1 = 48t + 21$$

$\therefore (48t+21) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, Then: $4(48t+21)+1=192t+64$,

$\therefore (192t+64) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,.....In this way, the rotation cycle follows the rule of $x_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_2 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

$\therefore \forall x \in O_2$ The elements in the set are distributed regularly according to $x_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_2 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, cycle according to the order from small to large exponent n.

$\forall x \in E_1, 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Section 3: 3-th Iterated Diophantine equation: $3x_{i+1}+1=x_i*2^k$ ($x_i \in \text{odd}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$) And its positive integer solution

(1) **【Existence Theorem of Solutions for (i+1)-th iterated Diophantine Equation】**

$\therefore 3x_{i+1}+1=x_i*2^k$ ($x_i \in \text{odd integer}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$)

$$\therefore x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3}$$

•When $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, k is an even integer

Let: $x_i = 3m+1$, $k=2n$, ($m \in \mathbb{Z}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$), then:

$$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3} = \frac{(3m+1) * 2^{2n-1}}{3} = \frac{(3m+1) * 4^{n-1}}{3} = \frac{3m * 4^{n-1} + 4^{n-1}}{3}$$

$\therefore \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$\therefore 3m * 4^n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4^n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

$\therefore (3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

$\therefore x_{i+1} = \frac{3m * 4^{n-1} + 4^{n-1}}{3}$ is a positive integer

\therefore When $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, k is an even integer, $\exists x_{i+1} \in \mathbb{Z}$.

$\therefore \text{Odd} \times \text{Odd} = \text{Odd}$, 3 is an odd, $(3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1)$ is an odd integer ,

$\therefore 3x_{i+1} = (3m * 4^n + 1 * 4^n - 1)$, $\therefore x_{i+1}$ is an odd integer.

\therefore When $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, k is an even, $\exists x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3}$ is an odd .

••When $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, k is an odd integer,

Let: $x_i = 3m+2$, $k=2n+1$, ($m \in \mathbb{Z}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$), then:

$$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3} = \frac{(3m+2) * 2^{2n+1-1}}{3} = \frac{(3m+2) * 2 * 4^{n-1}}{3} = \frac{3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^{n-1}}{3}$$

∴ $\forall m \in \mathbb{Z}, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\therefore 3m * 2 * 4^n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, 4 * 4^{n-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

$$\therefore (3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^{n-1}) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}.$$

$$\therefore x_{i+1} = \frac{3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^{n-1}}{3} \text{ is a positive integer}$$

∴ When $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, k is an odd integer, $\exists x_{i+1} \in \mathbb{Z}$.

∴ Odd * Odd = Odd, 3 is an odd integer, $(3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^{n-1})$ is an odd integer,

∴ $3x_{i+1} = (3m * 2 * 4^n + 4 * 4^{n-1})$, ∴ x_{i+1} is an odd integer.

∴ When $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, k is an odd integer, $\exists x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3}$ is an odd integer.

•• When $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, k is any positive integer,

Let: $x_i = 3m$, k is any positive integer, ($m \in \mathbb{Z}, k \in \mathbb{N}$), then:

$$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3} = \frac{3m * 2^{k-1}}{3}$$

∴ $\forall m \in \mathbb{Z}, k$ is any positive integer,

$$\therefore (3m * 2^{k-1}) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3},$$

$$\therefore x_{i+1} = \frac{3m * 2^{k-1}}{3} \text{ can not be a positive integer}$$

∴ When $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, k is any positive integer,

$\nexists x_{i+1} \in \mathbb{Z}$.

∴ Equation $3x_{i+1} + 1 = x_i * 2^k$ has no positive integer solution

The summary is as follows: For $(i+1)$ -th iterated Diophantine Equation $3x_{i+1} + 1 = x_i * 2^k$, when $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and “ k ” are all even numbers, there are positive integer solution; when $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ and “ k ” are all odd numbers, there are positive integer solution; when $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and “ k ” are any positive integer, the equation has no positive integer solution.

(2) **【Infinitely many solutions theorem of $(i+1)$ -th iterated solutions】**

∴ $k \in \mathbb{N}$, ∴ $k=0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,\dots \rightarrow \infty$

∴ There are countless (i+1)-th Iterated solutions

such as When: $x_2=13$,

$x_3=17,69,277,1109,4437,17749,70997,283989,1135957,\dots$

When: $x_2=53$,

$x_3=35,141,565,2261,9045,36181,144725,578901,2315605,\dots$

When: $x_2=113$,

$x_3=75,301,1205,4821,19285,77141,308565,1234261,4937045,\dots$

When: $x_2=3637$,

$x_3=4849,19397,77589,310357,1241429,4965717,19862869,\dots$

When: $x_2=29125$,

$x_3=38833,155333,621333,2485333,9941333,39765333,\dots$

When: $x_2=116501$,

$x_3=77667,310669,1242677,4970709,19882837,1272501589,\dots$

.....

When: $x_3=17$,

$x_4=11, 45, 181, 725, 2901, 11605, 46421, 185685, 742741, \dots$

When: $x_3=277$,

$x_4=369, 1477, 5909, 23637, 94549, 378197, 1512789, 6051157, \dots$

When: $x_3=35$,

$x_4=23, 93, 373, 1493, 5973, 23893, 95573, 382293, 1529173, \dots$

When: $x_2=3, 213, 13653, 873813, \dots \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$; or $x_3=69,4437,283989,\dots \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$; or $x_4=45,2901,185685,369,23637,1512789,\dots \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$; 不存在比它多一次次迭代解 There exists no solution requiring one additional iterated beyond it.

(3) 【A one-to-one correspondence theorem between the solution of the (i+1)-th iterated Diophantine equation and the terms of the recurrence sequence : $a_n=4a_{n-1}+1$ 】

∴ $3x_{i+1}+1=x_i*2^k(x_i \in \text{odd}, k \in \mathbb{N})$

$$\therefore x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3}.$$

$$\therefore x_{i+1, j} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3} = \frac{4 * x_i * 2^{k-2-1}}{3} = 4 * \frac{x_i * 2^{k-2-1}}{3} + 1$$

$$\therefore x_{i+1, j} = 4 * x_{i+1, j-1} + 1$$

Because the general term formula of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ is $a_n = \frac{3 * x_{i,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$, (where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x_{i,0}$ is the first term) by the generating function method, all $(i+1)$ -th iterated solutions x_{i+1} are all terms of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ with $x_{i+1,0}$ as the first term. This general term formula is exactly the same as the general expression for solutions to the iterative Diophantine equation.

Reverse proof: Insert $(i+1)$ -th iterated solution into the recurrence formula: $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$

$$\therefore x_{i+1, j} = \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3}.$$

$$\therefore 4x_{i+1, j} + 1 = 4 * \frac{x_i * 2^{k-1}}{3} + 1 = \frac{x_i * 2^{k+2-1}}{3} + 1 = x_{i+1, j+1}$$

$$\therefore 4x_{i+1, j} + 1 = x_{i+1, j+1}$$

(4) **【4x+1 Theorem:】** The solutions of the $(i+1)$ -th iterated Diophantine Equation are all terms of the recurrence sequence; conversely, the terms of the recurrence sequence are all solutions of the $(i+1)$ -th the iterative Diophantine equation.

Because the general term formula of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ is $a_n = \frac{3x_{i,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$, (where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x_{i,0}$ is the first term) by the generating function method, all $(i+1)$ -th iterates solutions x_{i+1} are all terms of the recurrence sequence $a_n = 4a_{n-1} + 1$ with $x_{i,0}$ as the first term.

$$\therefore x_{i+1} = \frac{3x_{i,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}, \text{ (where } n \in \mathbb{N}, x_{i,0} \text{ is the first term)}$$

(5) **【A Regularity Theorem with Residues Modulo 3 for Solutions of the $(i+1)$ -th iterated Diophantine Equations】**

Among the countless odd solutions to the Diophantine equation in the same iteration, they are all arranged in the order of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ according to the magnitude of the exponent “n”, without any omissions or duplication.

Proof:

$$\therefore O_{i+1} = \{x_{i+1} \mid x_{i+1} = \frac{3x_{i,0} + 1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}, x_{i,0} \in \text{odd}, n \in \mathbb{N}, n \text{ from } 0\}$$

$\therefore \forall x \in O_{i+1} \in$, Since $4x+1$ Theorem, Let: $x_{i+1} = m \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

$m=3t+1$ ($t \in \mathbb{N}$), Then: $4m+1 = 4(3t+1)+1 = 12t+5$,

$\therefore (12t+5) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, Then: $4(12t+5)+1 = 48t+21$

$\therefore (48t+21) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, Then: $4(48t+21)+1 = 192t+64$,

$\therefore (192t+64) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \dots$

$\forall x \in O_{i+1} \in$, Since $4x+1$ Theorem, Let: $x_{i+1} = m \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

$m=3t+2$ ($t \in \mathbb{N}$), Then: $4m+1 = 4(3t+2)+1 = 12t+9$,

$\therefore 12t+9 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$,

$\therefore 4(12t+9)+1 = 48t+37 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

$\forall x \in O_{i+1} \in$, Since $4x+1$ Theorem, Let: $x_{i+1} = m \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$,

$m=3t$ ($t \in \mathbb{N}$), Then: $4m+1 = 12t+1$,

$\therefore 12t+1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

$\therefore 4(12t+1)+1 = 48t+5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

In this way, the rotation cycle follows the rule of $x_{i+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_{i+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_{i+1} \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$.

$\therefore \forall x \in O_{i+1}$ The elements in the set are distributed regularly according to $x_{i+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_{i+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_{i+1} \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, cycle according to the order from small to large exponent n.

(6) **【 The (i+1) -th ultimate iterated solution theorem and the (i+1)- th extended iterated solution theorem 】**

According to the rule theorem of modulo-3 remainder of the solution of iterative Diophantus, for an odd number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, there is no solution that iterates more than it, and for an even number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, there is no solution that iterates more than it does. Therefore, there is no solution that iterates more than it for a natural number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. We call the natural number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ the ultimate iterative solution. For an odd number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, there must be a solution that iterates more than it, and for an even number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, there must be a solution that iterates more than it, so a natural number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ must have a solution that iterates more than it, and we call the natural number that satisfies the condition $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ an extended iterative solution,

(7) **【Regression Theorem for Solutions of Iterative Diophantine Equation】**

For any solution to the (i+1)-th iterated Diophantine equation, if the condition $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ is satisfied, there must be a chain of regression: “ $x_{i+1} \rightarrow x_i \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow x_2 \rightarrow x_1 \rightarrow 1$ ”

(8) 【Extensibility Theorem for Solutions of Iterative Diophantine Equation】

For the solution of any the (i+1)-th iterated Diophantine equation, if the condition $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ is satisfied, there must be an extended chain: “ $1 \rightarrow x_1 \rightarrow x_2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow x_i \rightarrow x_{i+1}$ ”

(8) 【Existence theorem of natural numbers with iteration times tending to infinity】 According to the modular complementary property “they are all arranged in the order of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ according to the magnitude of the exponent “n” of the solution of the iterative Diophantine equation and the extension theorem of the solution of the iterative Diophantine equation, it can be strictly inferred that the iterative Diophantine equation can be iterated endlessly, which means that there are natural numbers with iteration times tending to infinity

Chapter 2: The Pure Odd-Number Iteration collatz Reverse Generation Method Arranged in Ascending Order of Iteration Count.

Section 1: Basic Concepts, Definitions, and Their Properties.

1. The modular arithmetic rule for odd numbers when the quotient of a division operation is an odd number and its representation method.

【Definition】 : When the quotient resulting from a division operation is an odd number, the modular arithmetic operations involving all odd numbers are referred to as the “odd quotient modulo rule,” denoted by the symbol “ $a \equiv r \pmod{m}$ (m odd q)” [a=p *q+r, p is an odd number].

For example:

$$(1) 7 \div 2 = 3 \dots 1 \rightarrow 7 \equiv 1 \pmod{2};$$

$$(2) 9 \div 2 = 4 \dots 1 \rightarrow 9 \equiv 1 \pmod{2};$$

The correspondence between the “odd quotient modulo rule” and the Chinese Remainder Theorem :

$$2(2n+1)+1=4n+3 \rightarrow x \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$$

$$4(2n+1)+1=8n+5 \rightarrow x \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$$

$$4(2n+1)+3=8n+7 \rightarrow x \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$$

$$8(2n+1)+1=16n+9 \rightarrow x \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 9 \pmod{16}$$

$$8(2n+1)+3=16n+11 \rightarrow x \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 11 \pmod{16}$$

$$8(2n+1)+5=16n+13 \rightarrow x \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 13 \pmod{16}$$

$$8(2n+1)+7=16n+15 \rightarrow x \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 15 \pmod{16}$$

2. For any odd number x , $f^1(x)=4x+1$ is called the 1st-order tillinging function, $f^2(x)=4[4x+1]+1=16x+5$ is called the 2nd-order tillinging function, and so on. $f^n(x)=\frac{3x+1}{3}*4^n-\frac{1}{3}$ is then referred to as the n -th-order tillinging function. The odd numbers obtained through these tillinging functions are termed $4x+1$ is 1st-order tillinging odd numbers, denoted by $T_1=4x+1$, $16x+5$ is 2nd-order tillinging odd numbers, denoted by $T_2=16x+5$, and so on, up to the n -th-order tillinging odd numbers $\frac{3x+1}{3}*4^n-\frac{1}{3}$, denoted by $T_n=\frac{3x+1}{3}*4^n-\frac{1}{3}$. The tillinging functions can continue indefinitely, and the resulting tillinging odd numbers can be arbitrarily large.

3. **【Definition】**: In the “odd quotient modulo rule”, the odd numbers represented by $x \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ are called initial seed odd numbers. In other words, all non-tillinging odd numbers are initial seed odd numbers.

$$\therefore x \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 5 \pmod{8};$$

$\therefore x \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ are tillinging odd numbers ; and $x \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$ are initial seed odd numbers ;

Note: The difference between “initially odd seeds” and “reproductive viable odd numbers”: “Initially odd seeds” are named based on the tillinging function, and they are classified according to their remainder when divided by 4. “reproductive viable odd numbers” are named based on two reproductive functions: $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$, $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$, and they are classified according to their remainder when divided by 3.

4. **【Definition】**: The inverse function of the tillinging function: For any tillinging odd number x , the function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$ is referred to as the reverse tracing function. This function can trace a tillinging odd number back to its corresponding seed odd number.

5. For any given seed odd number, the numerous tillinging odd numbers generated by the tillinging function form a phase space. Within this phase space, the initial seed odd number is known as an attractor. Every phase space contains an infinite number of tillinging odd numbers, but there is always only one unique attractor, which is the initial seed odd number. Together, they constitute a dynamic iterative system. In this system, all elements have the same times of pure odd Collatz iterations; thus, the phase space is isomorphic about pure odd Collatz iterations. The even-numbered iteration relationship between adjacent tillinging odd numbers is denoted by The difference of 2 times divided by 2. This relationship is represented using the symbol $T_{k+1} \stackrel{=}{=} 2^2 = T_k$. Where the symbol “ $\stackrel{=}{=} 2^2 =$ ” denotes “2 pure even Collatz iterations apart”. The isomorphic phase space generated by the odd-numbered x_0 seeds is denoted by the symbol $S(x_i) = \{x \mid x = \frac{(3 * x_i + 1)}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}\}$. There are an infinite number of elements in this isomorphic phase space $S(x_i)$, which form a particular subset of odd integers with the same pure odd iterations count.

6. **【 Definition 】** : $[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}$) is referred to as a continuously extended interval, denoted by the symbol $I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$. The following table outlines the properties of continuously extended intervals:

k	I_k	Count of integers in the interval	Count of odd numbers in the interval	Count of tillering odd numbers in the interval
1	[1,4]	4^1	$2*4^0$	1
2	[5,20]	4^2	$2*4^1$	$2*4^0$
3	[21,84]	4^3	$2*4^2$	$2*4^1$
4	[85,340]	4^4	$2*4^3$	$2*4^2$
5	[341,1364]	4^5	$2*4^4$	$2*4^3$
6	[1365,5460]	4^6	$2*4^5$	$2*4^4$
7	[5461,21844]	4^7	$2*4^6$	$2*4^5$
8	[21845,87380]	4^8	$2*4^7$	$2*4^6$
9	[87381,349524]	4^9	$2*4^8$	$2*4^7$
k	$[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$	4^k	$2*4^{k-1}$	$2*4^{k-2}$
$k \rightarrow \infty$				

$$\therefore \bigcup_1^{\infty} I_k = \mathbb{N}$$

The infinite union of continuously expanding intervals can cover the entire set of natural numbers.

Among them, all the odd numbers form a set that includes all odd numbers, and all the even numbers form a set that includes all even numbers. In this context, interval I_k is referred to as the parent interval of interval I_{k+1} , while interval I_{k+1} is called the child interval of interval I_k .

7. The odd number “1” is referred to as the primary seed number.

8. **【Definition】**: The infinite tiller nature of any odd number: Any odd number can be tiller a “regular seed.” Using a tillering function, a regular seed can tiller to be 1st-order tillering odd numbers, 2nd-order tillering odd numbers, and so on, up to the k -order tillering odd numbers. In fact, any regular seed can continue to tiller indefinitely. These form a special subset of odd numbers that exhibit this characteristic $S(x_0) = \{x_0, T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_k, \dots\} (k \rightarrow \infty)$.

9. **【Definition of parent odd numbers】**: The “tillering of odd numbers” refers to those odd numbers for which the number of pure odd Collatz iteration count remains unchanged. The “reproduction of odd numbers” means that the resulting odd offspring have one more pure odd Collatz iteration count than their parent odd numbers. Thus, parent odd numbers are those capable of reproducing offspring, and there are two types of such numbers: $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. They are odd numbers that can continue to undergo reverse iteration. There is also a type of odd number $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ that cannot reproduce offspring; these are known as “terminating iteration odd numbers.” They are odd numbers that can not continue to undergo reverse iteration.

10. According to the content of Chapter 1, the odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ are referred to as “non-reproductive odd numbers.” These can only be generated through the tillering function, and their pure odd Collatz iteration count is equal. The reproduction pattern of $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ odd numbers is as follows: $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$, since the value of the offspring odd number is greater than that of the parent odd number, it is considered an “expansion reproduction” pattern; The reproduction pattern of $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ odd numbers is as follows: $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$, whereas since the value of the offspring odd number is smaller than that of the parent odd number, it is called a “contraction reproduction” pattern. Thus one-third of the odd numbers belong to the expansive reproduction category, one-third to the contractive reproduction category, and the remaining one-third constitute non-reproductive odd numbers.

11. **【Definition】**: If an odd or even number x can return to 1 after k times pure odd forward iteration count, then we denote this using the function symbol $C_{\text{odd}}(x) = k$. This function is referred to as the “counting function for the number of pure odd-number forward iterations of natural numbers”.

For example: $C_{\text{odd}}(5) = 1; C_{\text{odd}}(3) = 2; C_{\text{odd}}(17) = 3; \dots$

$C_{\text{odd}}(2^n) = 0;$

$C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = i$ (x_i is the Solution of the i -th iterated Diophantine Equations);

$C_{\text{odd}}(4x_i + 1) = i$ (x_i is the Solution of the i -th iterated Diophantine Equations);

$C_{\text{odd}}(2^n * x_i) = i$ (x_i is the Solution of the i -th iterated Diophantine Equations);

From the definition of function $C_{\text{odd}}(x)=k$, the formula can be derived as follows:

\forall odd number x (Let: $C_{\text{odd}}(x)=k$)

$$C_{\text{odd}}(3x+1)=C_{\text{odd}}(x)-1=k-1;$$

$$C_{\text{odd}}(x)=C_{\text{odd}}(3x+1)+1$$

12. **【Definition】**: The function $L(x)=x*2^1$ is called a 1-th leaf function. The function $L(x)=x*2^2$ is also referred to as 2-th leaf function, and so on. In general, the function $L(x)=x*2^k$ is termed k -th leaf function (where x is any odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$).

$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(x)=C_{\text{odd}}(x*2^k)$ (where x is any odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$).

13. **【Definition:】** For the odd numbers “ x_i ” within the extended interval, we refer to them as stem numbers. Each stem number within this interval, when subjected to the 1-th leaf function $L(x)=x*2^1$, produces an even number known as the 1-th leaf number x_i*2^1 . When subjected to the 2-th leaf function $L(x)=x*2^2$, it produces another even number, which is called the 2-th leaf number x_i*2^2 and so on. An even number obtained by applying the k -th leaf function $L(x)=x*2^k$ is referred to as the k -th leaf number x_i*2^k ($k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$).

According to the unique factorization theorem of natural numbers, all even numbers can be expressed in the form of leaf numbers. Therefore, the set of all leaf numbers is equivalent to the set of all even numbers. For each leaf number, its corresponding extended interval can be determined based on its associated stem number. In this way, the consecutive extended intervals cover all even numbers.

14. **【Definition】**: The inverse function of a leaf function is as follows: the inverse function of 1-th leaf function is $L^{-1}(x)=\frac{x}{2^1}$; the inverse function of 2-th leaf function is $L^{-1}(x)=\frac{x}{2^2}$; and so on. The inverse function of an k -th leaf function is $L^{-1}(x)=\frac{x}{2^k}$. Through the inverse functions of leaf functions, any leaf number can be uniquely mapped to its corresponding stem number($k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$).

15. **【Definition】** Trajectory Suffixes(abbreviation as:“TS”). Two Natural numbers that have identical trajectory suffixes in a forward Collatz iteration. If a natural number x_{i+j} and another natural number x_i , meeting condition:($C_{\text{odd}}(x_{i+j})>C_{\text{odd}}(x_i)$), and both start from x_i and converge to “1”. Then we called their have identical trajectory suffixes starting from x_i . This is denoted by the symbol “ $x_{i+j}=TS=x_i$ (from x_i)”. Read as "Natural numbers x_{i+j} and x_i have identical trajectory suffixes starting from x_i "

For example:

$$\textcircled{1}9 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1;$$

$$19 \rightarrow 29 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1;$$

$$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(9)=6; C_{\text{odd}}(11)=4; \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(9)>C_{\text{odd}}(11), \text{ trajectory suffixes is: } 11 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1;$$

$$\therefore 9=TS=11 \text{ (from } 11) ; 19=TS=11 \text{ (from } 11) ;$$

② **【Inference 1】** : Any tilling odd number and its corresponding seed odd number has the same Trajectory Suffixes , denoted as: $T_k=TS=x_0$ (from x_0) .

③ **【Inference 2】** : Any leaf numbers and its corresponding stem number has the same Trajectory Suffixes , denoted as: $x_i*2^k=TS=x_i$ (from x_i) .($x_i \in \text{odd}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$)

Section 2: Lemma on the Reverse Generation of pure odd number collatz iteration

【Lemma 1】 In the isomorphic phase space $S(x_i)=\{x \mid x = \frac{(3^* x_i+1)*4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}}{3}\}$, The pure odd iteration count of the tilling odd numbers is equal the pure odd iteration count of the seed odd number . For adjacent tilling odd numbers,their pure even numbers is difference in the number of iterations is “ $\div 2$ ”2 times.

Proof: $\forall T_k \in S(x_i)$, Let: $T_k = \frac{(3^* x_i+1)*4^{k-\frac{1}{3}}}{3}$,

Then: $3T_{k+1} = 3[\frac{(3^* x_i+1)*4^{k-\frac{1}{3}}}{3}] + 1 = (3x_i+1)*4^k$

$\rightarrow (3x_i+1)*4^k \div 2^{2k} = (3x_i+1)$.

$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(3T_{k+1}) = C_{\text{odd}}((3x_i+1)*4^k) = C_{\text{odd}}(3x_i+1) = C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) - 1 = i - 1$

$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(T_k) = C_{\text{odd}}(3T_{k+1}) + 1 = (i-1) + 1 = i$

\therefore When $n=0$, the seed odd number $= T_0 = \frac{(3^* x_i+1)*4^{1-\frac{1}{3}}}{3} = x_i$

$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(T_k) = C_{\text{odd}}(T_0) = C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = i$

$\therefore \forall T_k \in S(x_i), C_{\text{odd}}(T_k) = i (n \in \mathbb{N}, n=0, 1, 2, 3, \dots)$;

Let: $\forall T_k \in S(x_i), T_{k+1} \in S(x_i)$, Then: $T_{k+1} = 4T_k + 1$,

$\rightarrow (3T_{k+1}+1) = 3(4T_k+1)+1 = 12T_k+4 = 4(3T_k+1)$

$\rightarrow 4(3T_k+1) \div 2 \div 2 = (3T_k+1)$

$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(T_{k+1}) = C_{\text{odd}}(T_k) = i$, And: $T_{k+1} = \div 2^2 = T_k$

【Lemma 2】

【The Inheritance Theorem for tilling Function】 : tilling function has inheritance; they can inherit the number of iterations in a pure odd Collatz iteration. For all tilling odd numbers, the pure odd Collatz iteration count is determined by the seed odd number in their corresponding phase space. A 1st-order tilling odd number has a number of pure even iterations that is 2 more than its seed value; a 2nd-order tilling odd number has 4 more even iterations than its seed value, and so on. For an

n-th-order tiling odd number, the number of pure even iterations is 2n more than its seed value.

Proof: $\forall T_k \in S(x_i), C_{\text{odd}}(T_k)=i, T_0=x_i$

$$\because C_{\text{odd}}(T_{k+1})=C_{\text{odd}}(T_k)=C_{\text{odd}}(x_i)=i$$

$$\therefore T_{k+1}=\div 2^2=T_k \rightarrow T_1=\div 2^2=x_i, T_2=\div 2^4=x_i, T_3=\div 2^6=x_i, \dots, T_n=\div 2^{2n}=x_i,$$

【 Lemma 3 】 The Theorem of Reversible Tracing for tiling Odd Numbers: If an odd number is a tiling odd number, then in phase space $S(x_i)$, using the reversible tracing function $f^1(x)=\frac{x-1}{4}$, it is always possible to find a tiling odd number or seed odd number that is at least 4 times smaller than it. These numbers will have the same number of pure odd-numbered Collatz iterations.

Proof: $\forall T_k \in S(x_i), \exists T_{k-1} \in S(x_i), (T_{k-1} \text{ is a tiling odd number or seed odd number })$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(T_{k-1})=C_{\text{odd}}(T_k)=i, T_k=\div 2^2=T_{k-1}$

【 Lemma 4 】 The Theorem of Full Coverage Inheritance for the Number of Iterations in the Pure Odd Collatz iteration count, from the Parent Expansion Interval to the Child Expansion Interval: All odd numbers within the parent extension interval I_k can be isomorphously mapped to the sub-extension interval I_{k+1} using the 1-order tiling function $f^1(x)=4x+1$. This mapping preserves the property of having Pure Odd Collatz iteration count inheritance. These proliferated odd numbers constitute one-fourth of the sub-extension interval and are all odd numbers with a remainder of 1 when divided by 4, $x \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$

Proof:

$$\because \forall \text{ odd number } x \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right], \quad \frac{4^k-1}{3} \leq x < \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3},$$

$$\therefore 4 * \frac{4^k-1}{3} + 1 \leq 4x+1 < 4 * \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} + 1,$$

$$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} + 1 \leq 4x+1 < \frac{4^{k+2}-16}{3} + 1,$$

$$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} \leq 4x+1 < \frac{4^{k+2}-13}{3},$$

$$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} \leq 4x+1 < \frac{4^{k+2}-4}{3},$$

$$\therefore (4x+1) \in I_{k+1}$$

$$\therefore \forall \text{ odd number } x \in I_k \rightarrow f^1(x)=4x+1 \rightarrow \exists \text{ odd number } (4x+1) \in I_{k+1}$$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(4x+1)=C_{\text{odd}}(x)$,

These proliferated odd numbers such as $x \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ constitute one-fourth of the sub-extension interval, Their all are tillering odd numbers.

【 Lemma 5 】 The local isomorphism bijection theorem for sub-extension intervals I_{k+1} and parent extension intervals I_k : The odd numbers such as $x \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ in the sub-extension interval I_{k+1} can be mapped to all the odd numbers within the parent extension interval I_k using the inverse tracing function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$. This mapping is a bijection that preserves the invariant property of the pure odd number Collatz iteration counts for each number.

Proof:

$$\therefore \forall \text{ odd number } x \in I_{k+1} = \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2}-1}{3} \right], \quad \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} \leq x < \frac{4^{k+2}-1}{3},$$

$$\therefore \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} - 1 \right] \div 4 \leq \frac{x-1}{4} < \left[\frac{4^{k+2}-1}{3} - 1 \right] \div 4,$$

$$\therefore \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right] \div 4 \leq \frac{x-1}{4} < \left[\frac{4^{k+2}-7}{3} \right] \div 4,$$

$$\therefore \left[\frac{4^k-1}{3} \right] \leq \frac{x-1}{4} < \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-7}{3} \right],$$

$$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} \text{ is an odd bigger than } \frac{4^{k+1}-7}{3}$$

$$\therefore \frac{x-1}{4} \text{ is an odd number, } \therefore x-1 \text{ must be } (x-1) \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$$

$$\therefore \exists \text{ odd number } \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow \frac{x-1}{4} \leq \frac{4^{k+1}-9}{3}$$

$$\therefore \frac{4^k-1}{3} \leq \frac{x-1}{4} < \frac{4^{k+1}-9}{3},$$

$$\therefore \left[\frac{4^k-1}{3} \right] \leq \frac{x-1}{4} < \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right],$$

$$\therefore \frac{x-1}{4} \in I_k$$

$$\therefore \exists \text{ odd number } x \in I_{k+1} \rightarrow f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow \text{odd number } \frac{x-1}{4} \in I_k$$

And: since $x \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \Leftrightarrow x \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$

\therefore odd number $x \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ is tillering odd number

$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(\frac{x-1}{4})=C_{\text{odd}}(x)$, since Lemma 4, All odd numbers $\frac{x-1}{4}$ cover the all odd numbers of parent extension intervals I_k .

【 Lemma 6 】 For any odd number, The deterministic theorem regarding the pure odd Collatz iteration count: The pure odd Collatz iteration count of any odd number is fixed. After its corresponding extended interval, a subinterval can be found where a “1-order tiling odd number” can be identified. After the next subinterval, a “2-order tiling odd number” can be found, and so on. After every next extended interval, a number at the corresponding “k-order tiling odd number” can be obtained, as k approaches infinity. Thus, an infinite-level tiling odd number is generated. These odd numbers form an isomorphic phase space, wherein all odd numbers have the same pure odd Collatz iteration count. Moreover, no two different phase spaces intersect; in other words, the any two elements in different phase spaces are not equal to each other. And the any two elements in same phase spaces are not equal to each other too.

Proof:

$\therefore I_k$ is a continuously extended interval, and: $\bigcup_1^\infty I_k = \mathbb{N}$,

$\therefore \forall$ odd number $x \in I_k$

$\therefore \forall$ odd number $x \rightarrow \exists i \in \mathbb{N}$, let: $C_{\text{odd}}(T_k) = i$,

\therefore For any odd number, The pure odd Collatz iteration count of any odd number is fixed.

$\therefore \forall$ odd number $x \in I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}]$, $\frac{4^k-1}{3} \leq x < \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}$,

$\therefore 4 * \frac{4^k-1}{3} + 1 \leq 4x + 1 < 4 * \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} + 1$,

$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} + 1 \leq 4x + 1 < \frac{4^{k+2}-16}{3} + 1$,

$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} \leq 4x + 1 < \frac{4^{k+2}-13}{3}$,

$\therefore \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} \leq 4x + 1 < \frac{4^{k+2}-4}{3}$,

$\therefore (4x+1) \in I_{k+1}$

$\therefore \text{For } \forall \text{ odd number } x \in I_k, \rightarrow \exists T_1 \in I_{k+1}; \rightarrow \exists T_2 \in I_{k+2}; \dots \rightarrow \exists T_m \in I_{k+m};$

When $m \rightarrow \infty$, $\exists T_\infty \in I_{k+\infty}$;

And then : $\exists S(x) = \{x, T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m, \dots\} (m \rightarrow \infty)$;

$$\therefore x < T_1 < T_2 < \dots < T_m < \dots < T_\infty$$

$$\therefore \forall i \in \mathbb{N}, j \in \mathbb{N}, i \neq j, T_i \neq T_j$$

$$\text{If: } S(x) = \{x, T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m, \dots\} (m \rightarrow \infty);$$

$$S(y) = \{x, T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m, \dots\} (m \rightarrow \infty);$$

$$x \neq y;$$

$$\forall T_i \in S(x), T_j \in S(y), \text{ then } : T_i \neq T_j$$

Prove by contradiction:

Assume that equation $T_i = T_j$ holds true. then :

$$T_i \rightarrow f^1(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow \text{odd number } T_{i-1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow f^1(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow x;$$

$$T_j \rightarrow f^1(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow \text{odd number } T_{j-1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow f^1(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow y;$$

\therefore Because each phase space has a unique odd-numbered seed.

$$\therefore T_i = T_j \rightarrow x = y;$$

\therefore This contradicts $x \neq y$;

\therefore All original assumptions are invalid.

$$\therefore x \neq y;$$

$$\forall T_i \in S(x), T_j \in S(y), \text{ then } : T_i \neq T_j$$

【Lemma 7】 Uniformity Theorem for Probability Distributions of Three Types in pure odd collatz reverse iteration .

From the existence theorem of solutions to the reverse iterative Diophantine equations in Chapter 1, it can be concluded that: The odd number of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ is a terminating reverse iteration ;The odd number of $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ is a continue reverse iteration, and enters an expanded mode; The odd number of $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ is continue reverse iteration, and enters a compressed mode. The probability distribution for each of these three reverse iteration modes is one-third.

Proof:

\forall odd number $x \in I_k$, Based on the distribution pattern of odd numbers modulo 3, it can be concluded that

$$P(x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}, P(x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}, P(x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3},$$

\forall odd number $x \in S(x) = \{x, T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m, \dots\} (m \rightarrow \infty)$;

Based on the properties of the tilling function, it can be concluded that:

Let: $T_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, Then: $T_{i+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, T_{i+2} \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$;

Let: $T_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, Then: $T_{i+1} \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, T_{i+2} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$;

Let: $T_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, Then: $T_{i+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, T_{i+2} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$;

$$\therefore P(x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}, P(x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}, P(x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3},$$

The distribution pattern of natural numbers generated by the Peano axioms, as well as the distribution of odd numbers derived from the properties of the tilling function, have been proven in two different ways. It was shown that for the three types of pure-odd number Collatz iterations, the probability distribution is uniform, amounting to one-third in each case.

【Lemma 8】 The Transfer Theorem of the Reproductive fertility of the tilling Function. The tilling function can transform any odd number without reproductive capability into countless odd numbers with reproductive capability, accounting for two-thirds of the total. It can also convert a single odd number with reproductive capability into numerous odd numbers without reproductive capability, which make up one-third of the total. $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ Although it cannot continue iterating directly, it can still do so indirectly through its k -th tilling odd numbers. This is because its 1-th tilling odd number and 2-th tilling odd number necessarily be $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. This is the principle of migration for the tilling function.

Proof:

$$\therefore \forall \text{ odd number } x \in S(x) = \{x, T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m, \dots\} (m \rightarrow \infty);$$

And the odd number of $T_m \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$ are “reproductive odd numbers.” the odd number of $T_m \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ are “non-reproductive odd numbers.” The seed odd numbers

\therefore The seed odd numbers are countless and $m \rightarrow \infty$,

\therefore the odd number of $T_m \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$ are countless;

the odd number of $T_m \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ are countless too;

Since Lemma 7

$T_m \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$ accounting for two-thirds of the total.

$T_m \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ accounting for one-thirds of the total.

∴“reproductive odd numbers”accounting for two-thirds of the total.and “non-reproductive odd numbers”accounting for one-thirds of the total.

$$T_m \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow T_{m+1} \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow T_{m+2} \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$$

So $T_m \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ can be continue iterating indirectly by its k-th tillering odd numbers forever and endlessly.

【 Inference 】 : The theorem regarding the indirect continuity of the Collatz pure odd number reverse iteration and the direct continuity of the forward iteration

According to Lemma 8, during the reverse iteration of Collatz's pure odd numbers, when an odd number encounters meet the conditions $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, it must transition to an odd number meet the conditional $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$,in order to continue the iteration. This method is known as indirect continuous iteration. In Collatz's forward iteration, two consecutive odd numbers are always between meet the conditions $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$. Behind each tillering odd number be generated from a seed odd number, which may not be fertile, as meet the conditions $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Therefore, Collatz's forward iteration does not terminate ,and cannot encounters odd number as meet conditions $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. This phenomenon is referred to as direct continuous iteration. This represents the fundamental difference between Collatz's reverse iteration and forward iteration.

【 Definition 】 : During the process of tillering, the tillering by the odd numbers with the characteristic of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ is carried out for the purpose of continued reproduction. This type of tillering is called passive tillering. The tillering by the odd numbers with the characteristic of $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, It is part of the infinite tillering process in the generation of odd numbers, and is referred to as active tillering.

Let's take the odd number 27 as an example to analyze the difference between its forward iteration path and reverse iteration path:

The forward iteration path : 27 → 41 → 31 → 47 → 71 → 107 → 161 → 121 → 91 → 137 → 103 → 155 → 233 → 175 → 263 → 395 → 593 → 445 → 167 → 251 → 377 → 283 → 425 → 319 → 479 → 719 → 1079 → 1619 → 2429 → 911 → 1367 → 2051 → 3077 → 577 → 433 → 325 → 61 → 23 → 35 → 53 → 5 → 1

reverse iteration path: $27 \leftarrow x_{41} = \frac{41 * 2 - 1}{3} = 27 \leftarrow 41 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{40} = \frac{31 * 4 - 1}{3} = 41 \leftarrow 31 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{39} = \frac{47 * 2 - 1}{3} = 31 \leftarrow 47 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{38} = \frac{71 * 2 - 1}{3} = 47 \leftarrow 71 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{37} = \frac{107 * 2 - 1}{3} = 71 \leftarrow 107 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{36} = \frac{161 * 2 - 1}{3} = 107 \leftarrow 161 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{35} = \frac{121 * 4 - 1}{3} = 161 \leftarrow 121 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{34} = \frac{91 * 4 - 1}{3} = 121 \leftarrow 91 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{33} = \frac{137 * 2 - 1}{3} = 91 \leftarrow 137 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{32} = \frac{103 * 4 - 1}{3} = 137 \leftarrow 103 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{31} = \frac{155 * 2 - 1}{3} = 103 \leftarrow 155 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{30} = \frac{233 * 2 - 1}{3} = 155 \leftarrow 233 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{29} = \frac{175 * 4 - 1}{3} = 233 \leftarrow 175 \equiv 1$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\text{mod } 3) \leftarrow x_{28} = \frac{263 * 2-1}{3} = 175 \leftarrow 263 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{27} = \frac{395 * 2-1}{3} = 263 \leftarrow 395 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{26} = \\
& \frac{593 * 2-1}{3} = 395 \leftarrow 593 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{25} = \frac{445 * 4-1}{3} = 593 \leftarrow 445 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\
& \leftarrow x_{24} = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 111 + 1 = 445 \leftarrow 111 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{24} = \frac{167 * 2-1}{3} = 111 \leftarrow 167 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{23} = \\
& \frac{251 * 2-1}{3} = 167 \leftarrow 251 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{22} = \frac{377 * 2-1}{3} = 251 \leftarrow 377 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{21} = \frac{283 * 4-1}{3} = 377 \leftarrow 283 \equiv 1 \\
& (\text{mod } 3) \leftarrow x_{20} = \frac{425 * 2-1}{3} = 283 \leftarrow 425 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{19} = \frac{319 * 4-1}{3} = 425 \leftarrow 319 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{18} = \\
& \frac{479 * 2-1}{3} = 319 \leftarrow 479 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{17} = \frac{719 * 2-1}{3} = 479 \leftarrow 719 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{16} = \frac{1079 * 2-1}{3} = 719 \leftarrow 1079 \equiv 2 \\
& (\text{mod } 3) \leftarrow x_{15} = \frac{1619 * 2-1}{3} = 1079 \leftarrow 1619 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{14} = \frac{2429 * 2-1}{3} = 1619 \leftarrow 2429 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \\
& \leftarrow x_{13} = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 607 + 1 = 2429 \leftarrow 607 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{13} = \frac{911 * 2-1}{3} = 607 \leftarrow 911 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{12} = \\
& \frac{1367 * 2-1}{3} = 911 \leftarrow 1367 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{11} = \frac{2051 * 2-1}{3} = 1367 \leftarrow 2051 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{10} = \\
& \frac{3077 * 2-1}{3} = 2051 \leftarrow 3077 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_9 = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 769 + 1 = 3077 \leftarrow x_9 = \frac{577 * 4-1}{3} = 769 \leftarrow 577 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\
& 3) \leftarrow x_8 = \frac{433 * 4-1}{3} = 577 \leftarrow 433 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_7 = \frac{325 * 4-1}{3} = 433 \leftarrow 325 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\
& \leftarrow x_6 = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 81 + 1 = 325 \leftarrow 81 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_6 = \frac{61 * 4-1}{3} = 81 \leftarrow 61 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\
& \leftarrow x_5 = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 15 + 1 = 61 \leftarrow 15 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_5 = \frac{23 * 2-1}{3} = 15 \leftarrow 23 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_4 = \\
& \frac{35 * 2-1}{3} = 23 \leftarrow 35 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_3 = \frac{53 * 2-1}{3} = 35 \leftarrow 53 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_2 = f^2(x) = 16x+5 = 16 \times 3 + 5 = 53 \leftarrow 3 \equiv 0 \\
& (\text{mod } 3) \leftarrow x_2 = \frac{5 * 2-1}{3} = 3 \leftarrow 5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_1 = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 1 + 1 = 5 \leftarrow x_1 = 1
\end{aligned}$$

During the reverse iteration of 27, such as $445 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_{24} = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 111 + 1 = 445 \leftarrow 111 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $325 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_6 = f^l(x) = 4x+1 = 4 \times 81 + 1 = 325 \leftarrow 81 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ all represents passive tilling. Another represents active tilling.

Collatz reverse iteration clearly reflects the iteration path of odd number starting from "1". However, in the path of forward Collatz iteration sequence, since the ultimate iteration odd number cannot continue iterating on its own, characterized by $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, it transitions to its tilling odd numbers, which then continue the iteration process. Therefore, in the forward iteration, the ultimate iteration odd numbers is invisible. According to Collatz reverse iteration algorithm, if an odd number iterates to the next odd number, When the expansion greater than $\frac{4}{3}$ threshold, or compression smaller $\frac{2}{3}$ threshold, it indicates that the ultimate odd number has been replaced by its tilling odd number. This is how to identify tilling odd numbers, and it's the best way to do so without using an inverse tracing function for the tilling function.

The concept of an integer with high stopping time is an illusion that arises in the study of odd numbers in the Collatz iteration. This illusion can be eliminated immediately by using tillering function, transforming the integer with high stopping time into an integer with low stopping time .

For example:① $T_{30}=167557925336195093845 \leftarrow x_{42}=145 \leftarrow x_{42}=\frac{109*4-1}{3}=145 \leftarrow x_{41}=109 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$
 $\leftarrow T_1=109 \leftarrow x_{41}=27$

$$\therefore 3 \times 167557925336195093845 + 1 = 502673776008585281536 \div 2^{62} = 109;$$

$\therefore x_{42}=167557925336195093845$ is an integer with low stopping time, the total steps of iterations is $42+62=104$, counts of pure odd number Iterations is 42. It contains invisible odd numbers 27 in the path of forward Collatz iteration sequence.

The concept of an integer with high stopping time is an illusion that arises in the study of odd numbers in the Collatz iteration. This illusion can be eliminated immediately by using tillering function, transforming the integer with high stopping time into an integer with low stopping time .

For example:② $x_{194}=837799$ is an integer with high stopping time , the total steps of iterations is 524, counts of pure odd number

Iterations is 194, but by tillering function:

$$\therefore x_{195} = \frac{3*1117065+1}{3} * 4^{10000-\frac{1}{3}} \leftarrow T_{10000} = x_{195} = \frac{837799*4-1}{3} = 1117065 \leftarrow x_{194} = 837799 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$$

$\therefore 3 \times 1117065 + 1 = 837799 \times 2^2$

$$[3(\frac{3*1117065+1}{3} * 4^{10000-\frac{1}{3}} + 1)] = (3*1117065+1) * 4^{10000} = 837799 \times 2^{20002}$$

$\therefore x_{195} = \frac{3*1117065+1}{3} * 4^{10000-\frac{1}{3}}$ the total steps of iterations is $525+20002=20527$, counts of pure odd number Iterations is 195.

$$\therefore x_{195} = \frac{3*1117065+1}{3} * 4^{10000-\frac{1}{3}} \text{ become an integer with low stopping time.}$$

The explanation of "4-2-1" trivial cycle in the Collatz conjecture:

$$\therefore x_1=5 \leftarrow x_1=f^1(x)=4x+1=4 \times 1+1=5 \leftarrow x_1=1$$

$$\therefore \text{And: } x_\infty=1 \leftarrow x_n=1 \dots \dots \leftarrow x_3=\frac{1*4-1}{3}=1 \leftarrow x_2=1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \leftarrow x_2=\frac{1*4-1}{3}=1 \leftarrow x_1=1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$$

In 1937, since the German mathematician Mr Lothar Collatz did not clarify when proposing Collatz conjecture whether iterations should continue once an odd number returns to "1", if we proceed with the iteration according to the approach and algorithm described in this article, an infinite loop of "4-2-1" trivial cycle will occur.

【Lemma 9】The convergence Theorem for Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations. In the process of odd numbers generating by reverse Collatz pure odd number Iterations, For the same odd number, if the iterated continuously ($x_i \rightarrow x_{i+1}$), whether in the expansion mode or compression mode, it will eventually converge. The Collatz pure odd-number iteration can extend to infinite odd numbers, and the crucial factor is the mechanism by the tiling function generates “reproductive viable odd numbers” such as: $T_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $T_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, these odd number all are “reproductive viable odd numbers”.

Proof:

∴ “reproductive viable odd numbers” x_i by Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations and non-tiling, This approach is unrelated to the tiling function. so:

$$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 4 - 1}{3}; \text{ (“expansion reproduction”)}$$

$$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 2 - 1}{3}; \text{ (“contraction reproduction”)}$$

And $P(x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}, P(x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}, P(x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{3}$ are terminating reverse iteration ;

∴ At the continuable Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations, We can also explain it this way:

$$P(x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}) = P(x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}) = \frac{1}{2},$$

∴ $\forall x_i$ is the odd number of the continuable Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations .

$$x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 4 - 1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}; \text{ (“expansive reproduction”)}$$

$$x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 2 - 1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}; \text{ (“contractive reproduction”)}$$

∴ $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 4 - 1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“expansive reproduction”) and $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 2 - 1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“contractive reproduction”) occurring is random, yet the probabilities are equal. It’s just like flipping a coin. Thus

We can Let: $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 4 - 1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“expansive reproduction”) and $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} =$

$\frac{x_i^* 2 - 1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“contractive reproduction”) appear alternately in sequence:

$$x_i \rightarrow \frac{x_i^* 4 - 1}{3} \rightarrow \frac{(\frac{x_i^* 4 - 1}{3})^* 2 - 1}{3} \leq (\frac{8}{9} x_i);$$

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{8}{9}^k x_i = 0$$

∴ it converges.

If $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 4-1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“expansive reproduction”) and $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 2-1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“contractive reproduction”) do not appear in an alternating sequence but have equal probabilities of occurring, then the equation must be satisfied:

$$\left(\frac{4}{3}\right)^{100m} * \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{71m} x_i \leq 1 * x_i$$

That is, when the ratio of the number of occurrences of $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 4-1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“expansive reproduction”) to that of $x_i \rightarrow P(x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* 2-1}{3}) = \frac{1}{2}$; (“contractive reproduction”) is 100:71. the result of reverse pure odd number iteration for any odd number is less than its self.

So $\frac{8}{9}$ can be used as a reliable indicator for the decay index during reverse iteration of pure odd numbers.

∴ For the any one odd number, if the iterated continuously ($x_i \rightarrow x_{i+1}$), it will eventually converge.

【 A Direct Corollary of Lemma 9: 】 According to Lemma 9, any odd number that can undergo continuous reverse pure odd number collatz iteration will eventually converge. This has nothing to do with the convergence of the collatz forward iteration. Because the convergence of the collatz forward iteration is proved by the count of pure odd iteration. It can be explained or guaranteed as follows :from another reproduction odd number within the parent extension interval I_k , that all seed odd numbers (Although we don’t know the number of iterations it undergoes) within the parent extension interval I_k will after a finite number of reverse pure odd number collatz iterations, become the tillering odd numbers within the sub-extension interval I_{k+1} .

【 Lemma 10 】 The theorem of Classification of Odd Numbers in Phase Space and Their mathematical Properties.

In a certain phase space of the i-th pure odd number iterated solution, the seed odd number x_i is referred to as a lower-order pure even-number iteration odd number. The 1th-order tillering odd numbers T_1 is called intermediate-order pure even-number iteration odd numbers, while the m-th order tillering odd number $T_m (m \geq 2)$ is termed a higher-order pure even-number iteration odd number. Since the collatz forward iteration of the seed odd number x_i can occur in either an expansion or compression mode, the hierarchical properties of the odd numbers in the phase space are detailed in the following table:

∴ $x \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$ are initial seed odd numbers ;

$$\text{∴ } \textcircled{1} x \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \rightarrow x_i = 8n+1 \rightarrow [3(8n+1)+1] = (24n+4) \div 2^2 \rightarrow x_{i-1} = 6n+1$$

$$\textcircled{2} x \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \rightarrow x_i = 8n+3 \rightarrow [3(8n+3)+1] = (24n+10) \div 2 \rightarrow x_{i-1} = 12n+5$$

$$\textcircled{3} x \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \rightarrow x_i = 8n+7 \rightarrow [3(8n+7)+1] = (24n+22) \div 2 \rightarrow x_{i-1} = 12n+11$$

$\therefore x_{i-1} = 6n+1 < x_i = 8n+1 \therefore$ the seed odd number $x \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ compressed

$\therefore x_{i-1} = 12n+5 > x_i = 8n+3 \therefore$ the seed odd number $x \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ expanded

$\therefore x_{i-1} = 12n+11 > x_i = 8n+7 \therefore$ the seed odd number $x \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ expanded

Explanation: Since the odd numbers that satisfy condition $x \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \rightarrow x_i = 8n+5 \rightarrow [3(8n+5)+1] = (24n+16) \div 2^3 \rightarrow x_{i-1} = 3n+2$ are the seed odd numbers, they do not need to be discussed again.

$\textcircled{1} x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ compression mode

Odd umbers	Classification of Odd Numbers	count of pure even-number iteration back to x_{i-1}
the seed odd number x_i	2-order pure even-number iteration odd number	2
T_1	4-order pure even-number iteration odd numbers	$2+2=4$
$T_m (m \geq 2)$	$2+2m$ -order pure even-number iteration odd number	$2+2m$

$\textcircled{2} x_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ expansion mode

Odd umbers	Classification of Odd Numbers	count of pure even-number iteration back to x_{i-1}
the seed odd number x_i	1-order pure even-number iteration odd number	1

T_1	3-order pure even-number iteration odd numbers	$1+2=3$
$T_m (m \geq 2)$	$1+2m$ -order pure even-number iteration odd number	$1+2m$

③ $x_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ expansion mode

Odd umbers	Classification of Odd Numbers	count of pure even-number iteration back to x_{i-1}
the seed odd number x_i	1-order pure even-number iteration odd number	1
T_1	3-order pure even-number iteration odd numbers	$1+2=3$
$T_m (m \geq 2)$	$1+2m$ -order pure even-number iteration odd number	$1+2m$

【Lemma 11】 The count of hailstone amplitude formula for an odd number: According to Lemma 10, we can determine that for an odd number, after undergoing the operation $(3x+1)$, it requires a certain counts of “ $\div 2$ ”operations to iteratively reach the next odd number. This represents the hailstone amplitude of that odd number. The specific method is as follows:

- (1) First, determine whether the odd number is a “tillering odd number” or a “seed odd number”.
- (2) If it is a tillering odd number, use the inverse tracing function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$ of the tillering function to determine its level as a tillering odd number and identify the corresponding seed odd number.
- (3) If it is a seed odd number, classify it based on its remainder when divided by 8. Then, refer to the table in Lemma 10 to calculate the counts of “ $\div 2$ ”operations required to iteratively reach the next odd number after the $(3x+1)$ operation. For tillering odd numbers, use the same method and refer to the table in Lemma 10 for calculations.

In total, this method involves four types of modulo classifications, allowing for an accurate calculation of the counts of hailstone amplitude of an odd number. This approach differs from the conventional forward iteration division method.

For example①:When the odd number is a “seed odd number”

classify it based on its remainder when divided by 8.	The seed odd number $x_i \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$	$3x+1$	counts of “÷2”	Pure odd number Iteratively reach the next odd number
$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$	97	292	$2^2=4$	73
	1881	5644		1411
	41057	123172		30793
	987345	2962036		740509
	4321905	12965716		3241429
$x_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$	99	298	$2^1=2$	149
	2883	8650		4325
	52059	156178		78089
	389447	1168342		584171
	5432707	16298122		8149061
$x_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$	103	310	$2^1=2$	155
	3987	11962		5981
	63063	189190		94595

	98551	295654		147827
	1234511	3703534		1851767
.....

For example②: When the odd number is a “tillering odd number”

tillering odd number T_m	the corresponding seed odd number. x_i	classify it based on its remainder when divided by 8.	$3x+1$	counts of “÷2”	Pure odd number Iteratively reach the next odd number
$T_1=133$	33	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$	400	$2+2m=4$	25
$T_2=501$	31	$x_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$	1504	$1+2m=5$	47
$T_3=1749$	27	$x_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$	5248	$1+2m=7$	41
$T_4=6458$	25	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$	19456	$2+2m=10$	19
$T_5=23893$	23	$x_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$	71680	$1+2m=11$	35
$T_6=79189$	19	$x_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$	237568	$1+2m=13$	29
$T_7=283989$	17	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$	851968	$2+2m=16$	13
$T_8=1004885$	15	$x_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$	3014656	$1+2m=17$	23
$T_9=2970965$	11	$x_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$	8912896	$1+2m=19$	17

$T_{10}=9786709$	9	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$	29360128	$2+2m=22$	7
.....

【 Collatz Path Length Determination Theorem 】 : The iterations of an odd number always occur between set{seed odd numbers+tillering odd numbers }and {seed odd numbers+tillering odd numbers }. Therefore, the length of an odd-numbered iteration path, whether it's forward or backward, depends on the number of seed odd numbers and the number of tillering odd numbers during the iteration process. If there are more seed odd numbers, then there will be more counts of pure odd-numbered iterations, causing the iteration path to descent slowly. Conversely, if there are more tillering odd numbers, the iteration path will descent quickly. The proportional relationship between the number of pure odd-numbered iterations and the number of pure even-numbered iterations is determined by the ratio between the number of tillering odd numbers and the number of odd seed numbers, Not only that, but it also has a close relationship with how much levels of each tillering odd number. For example:

① ∴ $1 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 21 \rightarrow 85$

↓

$113 \rightarrow 453 \rightarrow 1813 \rightarrow 7253$

↓

$4853 \rightarrow 19341 \rightarrow 77365 \rightarrow 309461$

↓

206307

Analysis: The path of odd number 206307 contains 4 seed odd numbers and 9 tillering odd numbers.

∴ $C_{\text{odd}}(206307)=4; C_{\text{even}}(206307)=26;$

∴ The iteration path of odd number 206307 will descent quickly.

② ∴ $1 \rightarrow 5$

↓

$3 \rightarrow 13$

↓

17

Analysis: The path of odd number 305 contains 11 seed odd numbers and 4 tillering odd numbers.

$$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(305)=11; C_{\text{even}}(305)=26;$$

\therefore The iteration path of odd number 305 will descent slowly.

③ In the iteration path of the famous stubborn odd number 63728127 using the Collatz iteration, a statistical analysis of the seed odd numbers and the tillering odd numbers is as follows:

Analysis: The path of odd number 63728127 contains 310 seed odd numbers and 46 tillering odd numbers.

Among them: In consecutive segments, extreme values with an odd number of seeds occurred 26 times, 16 times, 14 times, and so on.

$$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(63728127)=357; C_{\text{even}}(63728127)=592;$$

$$\therefore 357:592=1:1.6582633$$

311 seed odd numbers Analysis (“1”excluding) :

the counts of seed odd number.	classify it based on its remainder when divided by 8.	Percentage Occupied
127	$x_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$	35.5%
81	$x_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$	22.6%
102	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$	28.57%

47 tillering odd numbers Analysis:

the counts of tillering odd numbers	classify it based on its remainder when divided by 8.	Percentage Occupied
47	$x_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$	13.1.5%

47 tillering odd numbers Analysis:

Ordinal number Counts of iterations Oddnumbr

- 1 第 23 次 178,801,076,213 Large-numberregime
- 2 第 37 次 203,895,569,981 Large-numberregime
- 3 第 40 次 172,036,887,173 Large-numberregime
- 4 第 56 次 110,352,395,245 Large-numberregime
- 5 第 65 次 66,286,199,821 intermediate phase
- 6 第 66 次 24,857,324,933 intermediate phase
- 7 第 89 次 68,107,258,637 intermediate phase
- 8 第 90 次 25,540,221,989 intermediate phase

- 9 第 100 次 46,024,309,349 intermediate phase
- 10 第 102 次 12,944,337,005 intermediate phase
- 11 第 108 次 18,430,511,093 intermediate phase
- 12 第 146 次 172,756,861,573 intermediate phase
- 13 第 157 次 58,371,276,397 intermediate phase
- 14 第 162 次 55,407,110,021 intermediate phase
- 15 第 167 次 26,296,733,861 intermediate phase
- 16 第 173 次 18,721,014,637 intermediate phase
- 17 第 177 次 11,846,892,077 intermediate phase
- 18 第 179 次 3,331,938,397 intermediate phase
- 19 第 181 次 1,874,215,349 intermediate phase
- 20 第 199 次 676,242,109 small-number regime
- 21 第 203 次 427,934,461 small-number regime
- 22 第 209 次 609,305,125 small-number regime
- 23 第 220 次 823,490,725 small-number regime
- 24 第 230 次 1,483,957,037 small-number regime
- 25 第 232 次 417,362,917 small-number regime
- 26 第 236 次 132,056,237 small-number regime
- 27 第 239 次 27,855,613 small-number regime
- 28 第 261 次 814,105,181 small-number regime
- 29 第 263 次 457,934,165 small-number regime
- 30 第 278 次 6,119,621 minimal phase
- 31 第 279 次 1,147,429 minimal phase
- 32 第 290 次 1,550,789 minimal phase
- 33 第 291 次 290,773 minimal phase

- 34 第 299 次 58,229 minimal phase
- 35 第 301 次 8,189 minimal phase
- 36 第 312 次 88,573 minimal phase
- 37 第 321 次 425,645 minimal phase
- 38 第 327 次 75,757 minimal phase
- 39 第 332 次 35,957 minimal phase
- 40 第 336 次 2,845 minimal phase
- 41 第 340 次 901 minimal phase
- 42 第 349 次 1,093 minimal phase
- 43 第 350 次 205 minimal phase
- 44 第 351 次 77 minimal phase
- 45 第 352 次 29 minimal phase
- 46 第 355 次 13 minimal phase
- 47 第 356 次 5 last step

Among them:

T₁-type structures:26

T₂-type structures:13

T₃-type structures:6

T₄-type structures:1

T₅-type structures:3

Section 3: An algorithm for generating odd numbers through reverse pure odd numbers collatz iteration .

This Mode of generating odd numbers Similar to the reproduction methods of wheat, involving both vegetative(tiller) and sexual propagation.

Algorithm Step 1:Starting from the most fundamental odd number “1”,By the tillering function : $f^n(x)=\frac{3x+1}{3}*4^{n-1}$, all the odd numbers become tillering odd numbers. In the forward Collatz iteration, Every

odd number will eventually return to “1” only through once operation $(3x+1)$.

$$1 \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}} \rightarrow 5, \rightarrow 21, \rightarrow 85, \rightarrow 341, \rightarrow 1365, \rightarrow 5461, 21845, \rightarrow 87381, \rightarrow 349525, \\ \rightarrow 1398101 \rightarrow \quad , \quad 5592405 \rightarrow \quad , \quad 22369621 \quad , \\ \rightarrow 89478485 \rightarrow 357913941, \rightarrow 1431655765, \rightarrow 5726623061, \rightarrow 22906492245, \rightarrow 91625968981, \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \\ \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty)$$

There are an infinite number of such odd numbers, all of which are denoted by x_1 ($C_{\text{odd}}(x_1)=1$) .

Algorithm Step 2: Classify the solutions of pure odd-number iteration based on their remainder modulo 3: $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ represents the ultimate iteration solution; $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ denotes the expanded iteration solution; $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ indicates the compressed iteration solution.

$$\{x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}\} = \{21, 1365, 87381, 5592405, 357913941, \dots\}$$

$$\{x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}\} = \{1, 85, 5461, 349525, 22369621, 1431655765, \dots\}$$

$$\{x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}\} = \{5, 341, 21845, 1398101, 89478485, \dots\}$$

Algorithm Step 3: The iteration of odd $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ values cannot continue iteration directly. However, it can continue iteration indirectly through its 1-order tillering odd number, or 2-order tillering odd number, or 3-order tillering odd number, and so on, even up to k-order tillering odd number continue iteration indirectly ($k \rightarrow \infty$). This process can continue infinitely through indirect iteration.

The iteration algorithm values for odd $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ is: $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$, The iteration algorithm

values for odd $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ is $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$.

Algorithm Step 4: For those that result in x_{i+1} upon further iteration (seed odd numbers, here is x_2),

repeat the steps of Algorithm 1. For each seed odd number, By the tillering function : $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}$,

all the seed odd numbers become tillering odd numbers. tillering function to generate an infinite number of tillering odd numbers .

Repeat the steps of algorithms 1, 2, and 3 in sequence to obtain x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots , and so on, until the counts of the pure number iteration is obtained infinite .

For odd $x_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ algorithms is: $x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 4 - 1}{3}$, such as:

$$x_2 = \frac{1 * 4 - 1}{3} = 1,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{85 * 4 - 1}{3} = 113,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{5461 * 4 - 1}{3} = 7281,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{349525 * 4 - 1}{3} = 466033,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{22369621 * 4 - 1}{3} = 29826161,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{1431655765 * 4 - 1}{3} = 1908874353,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{91625968981 * 4 - 1}{3} = 122167958641,$$

.....

For odd $x_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ algorithms is: $x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2 - 1}{3}$, such as:

$$x_2 = \frac{5 * 2 - 1}{3} = 3,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{341 * 2 - 1}{3} = 227,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{21845 * 2 - 1}{3} = 14563,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{1398101 * 2 - 1}{3} = 932067,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{89478485 * 2 - 1}{3} = 59652323,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{5726623061 * 2 - 1}{3} = 3817748707,$$

$$x_2 = \frac{366503875925 * 2 - 1}{3} = 244335917283,$$

.....

then: by the tiling function algorithms is : $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}$,

$$x_2 = 113, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=7281, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=466033, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=29826161, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=1908874353, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=122167958641, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

.....

$$x_2=3, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=227, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=14563, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=932067, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=59652323, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=3817748707, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

$$x_2=244335917283, \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

seed odd integer	T1	T2	T3	T4	Tk
3		13	53	213	853
227		909	3637	14549	58197
14563		58253	233013	932053	3728213
932067		3728269	14913077	59652309	238609237
59652323		238609293	954437173	3817748693	15270994773
3817748707		15270994829	61083979317	2.44336E+11	9.77344E+11
.....

113	453	1813	7253	29013
7281	29125	116501	466005	1864021
466033	1864133	7456533	29826133	119304533
29826161	119304645	477218581	1908874325	7635497301
1908874353	7635497413	30541989653	1.22168E+11	4.88672E+11
.....

The above table presents an infinite list of tilling odd numbers tillered from the seed odd numbers x_2 through tilling function : $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$

Explanation1: “ $x_2 = \frac{1 * 4 - 1}{3} = 1$ ” is both a solution resulting from 1-th pure odd number iteration count and a solution resulting from 2-th pure odd number iteration count. If the iteration continues, “ $x_i = \frac{1 * 4 - 1}{3} = 1$ ” can be a solution after any number of i-th pure odd number iteration count. This is the essence of the “4-2-1” loop. Therefore, in the 2-th pure odd number iteration count iteration, we excluded “1”. This was clearly explained in Chapter 1.

Explanation 2: Odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ represent ultimate iteration odd numbers. This does not mean they cannot tilling . Iteration refers to performing the $(3x+1)$ operation one more time, It maintains the constancy of the counts of $(3x+1)$ operations. All odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ cannot to pure odd number iterations , but they can continue tilling infinitely.

Section 4: From the parent extension interval $I_k = [\frac{4^k - 1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1} - 4}{3}]$ to the sub-extension interval $I_k = [\frac{4^{k+1} - 1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2} - 4}{3}]$, this transformation is demonstrated through an isomorphic mapping using the the 1st-order tilling function: $f^1(x) = 4x + 1$. This isomorphic mapping provides full coverage of the parent extension interval: every odd number within the parent interval can be corresponded one-to-one to a tilling odd number in the sub-extension interval via the 1st-order tilling function .

① Example 1: $I_1 = [1, 3] \rightarrow I_2 = [5, 13]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(1) = C_{\text{odd}}(5) = 1, C_{\text{odd}}(3) = C_{\text{odd}}(13) = 2$

② Example 2: $I_2 = [5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19] \rightarrow I_3 = [21, 23, 25, 29, \dots, 83]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(5) = C_{\text{odd}}(21) = 1; C_{\text{odd}}(7) = C_{\text{odd}}(29) = 5; \dots C_{\text{odd}}(19) = C_{\text{odd}}(77) = 6;$

③ Example 3: $I_3 = [21, 23, 25, \dots, 83] \rightarrow I_4 = [85, 87, 89, \dots, 339]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(21) = C_{\text{odd}}(85) = 1; C_{\text{odd}}(23) = C_{\text{odd}}(93) = 4; \dots C_{\text{odd}}(83) = C_{\text{odd}}(333) = 40;$

④ Example 4: $I_4 = [85, 87, 89, \dots, 339] \rightarrow I_5 = [341, 343, 345, \dots, 1363]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(85) = C_{\text{odd}}(341) = 1; C_{\text{odd}}(87) = C_{\text{odd}}(349) = 9; C_{\text{odd}}(89) = C_{\text{odd}}(357) = 9;$

..... $C_{\text{odd}}(339)=C_{\text{odd}}(1357)=16$;

⑤ Example 5: $I_5=[341,343,345,\dots,1363] \rightarrow I_6=[1365,1367,1369,\dots,5459]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(341)=C_{\text{odd}}(1365)=1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(343)=C_{\text{odd}}(1373)=45$; $C_{\text{odd}}(345)=C_{\text{odd}}(1381)=45$; $C_{\text{odd}}(1363)=C_{\text{odd}}(5453)=21$;

⑥ Example 6:

$I_6=[5461,5463,5465,\dots,21843] \rightarrow I_7=[21845,21847,21849,\dots,87379]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(5461)=C_{\text{odd}}(21845)=1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(5463)=C_{\text{odd}}(21853)=40$; $C_{\text{odd}}(5465)=C_{\text{odd}}(21861)=57$; $C_{\text{odd}}(21843)=C_{\text{odd}}(87373)=47$;

⑦ Example 7:

$I_7=[21845,21847,21849,\dots,87379] \rightarrow I_8=[87381,87383,87385,\dots,349523]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(21845)=C_{\text{odd}}(87381)=1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(21847)=C_{\text{odd}}(87389)=15$; $C_{\text{odd}}(21849)=C_{\text{odd}}(87397)=15$; $C_{\text{odd}}(87379)=C_{\text{odd}}(349517)=66$;

⑧ Example 8:

$I_8=[87381,87383,87385,\dots,349523] \rightarrow I_9=[349525,349527,349529,\dots,1398099]$;

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(87381)=C_{\text{odd}}(349525)=1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(87383)=C_{\text{odd}}(349533)=33$; $C_{\text{odd}}(87385)=C_{\text{odd}}(349541)=32$; $C_{\text{odd}}(349523)=C_{\text{odd}}(1398093)=134$;

⑨ Example 8:

$I_9=[349525,349527,349529,\dots,1398099] \rightarrow I_{10}=[1398101,1398103, 1398105, \dots, 5592403]$;

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(349525)=C_{\text{odd}}(1398101)=1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(349527)=C_{\text{odd}}(1398109)=38$;

$C_{\text{odd}}(349529)=C_{\text{odd}}(1398117)=33$; $C_{\text{odd}}(1398099)=C_{\text{odd}}(5592397)=75$;

⑩ Example 10:

$I_{10}=[1398101,1398103,1398105,\dots,5592403] \rightarrow I_{11}=[5592405, 5592407, 5592409, \dots, 22369619]$

And: $C_{\text{odd}}(1398101)=C_{\text{odd}}(5592405)=1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(1398103)=C_{\text{odd}}(5592413)=21$;

$C_{\text{odd}}(1398105)=C_{\text{odd}}(5592421)=81$;; $C_{\text{odd}}(5592403)=C_{\text{odd}}(22369613)=61$;

【 The local isomorphic bijection theorem of the tiling function between the parent expansion interval and the child expansion interval 】 : The odd numbers $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ [equals $x_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$] within the child expansion interval form an isomorphic bijection with all the odd numbers in the parent expansion interval. This isomorphic bijection establishes a one-to-one correspondence between one-quarter of the odd numbers in the child expansion interval and all the odd numbers in the parent

expansion interval.

【Inference】 : Any extended interval must contain two odd numbers that $C_{\text{odd}}(x_1)=1$ or $C_{\text{odd}}(x_2)=2$. Any sub-expanded interval must contain all the odd numbers equal the counts of pure odd iteration from the parent expanded interval. Any extended interval must contain at least one odd number with a purely odd iteration count that exceeds the maximum iteration count in the parent expanded interval.

Proof:

$$1 \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}, \text{ then: } \left[\frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}} \right] \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right], C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4^k-1}{3}\right) = 1;$$

$$3 \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}, \text{ then: } \left[\frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}} \right] \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right],$$

$$C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{3 * 3+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}\right) = 2;$$

$$\forall x \in I_k \rightarrow f^l(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}} = (4x+1) \in I_k, \rightarrow C_{\text{odd}}(4x+1) = C_{\text{odd}}(x)$$

$\forall I_k; \exists x_i \in I_k; \text{ Let: } C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = \max, \text{ And } x_i \text{ can be continue iteration to } x_{i+1}; \text{ and } x_{i+1} \in I_{k+1};$

Section 5: Classification of Odd Last Digits in the Convergence of Collatz Forward Iteration for Natural Numbers

【Definition】 : We refer to the odd number that converges to “1” before the natural number reaches during its forward iteration process as the “tail odd number”. Different natural numbers can converge to 1 through their respective tail odd numbers. For example, there’s the 5-tail type, 21-tail type, 85-tail type, 341-tail type, 1365-tail type, 5461-tail type, 21845-tail type, $\frac{4^k-1}{3}$ -tail type ($k \in \mathbb{N}$), and so on. The tail numbers is the 1-th iterated solution of collatz pure odd number reverse iteration $x_1 = \frac{4^k-1}{3}$.

【Definition】 : Which with the pure odd number reverse iteration continuing infinitely, The set composed of all these odd numbers generated by “tail number ” $x_1 = \frac{4^k-1}{3}$, It is called the algebraic topological space . It is denoted by the symbol $T\left(\frac{4^k-1}{3}\right)$. For example: $T(5); T(21); T(85); T(341); T(1365); T(5461); T(21845); T(87381); T(349525); T(1398101); \dots$

【Theorem】 : Different algebraic topological spaces generated by different “tail number ” are pairwise disjoint. In other words, the elements in different algebraic topological spaces generated by different “tail number ” are distinct from one another.

Proof by contradiction:

Let: $\forall x_i \in T(a); \forall x_j \in T(b); a = \frac{4^k-1}{3}, b = \frac{4^j-1}{3}, k \neq j, a \neq b;$

If: $\exists x_i = x_j;$

According to the bijectivity of the pure odd number reverse iteration algorithm and the inverse function

of the algorithm function: ① $f^1(x) = 4x+1 \iff f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$, ② $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* - 4}{3} \iff x_i = \frac{3x_{i+1}+1}{4}$,

③ $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* - 2}{3} \iff x_i = \frac{3x_{i+1}+1}{2}$.

(1) If: x_i is the tilling number, then: by the inverse function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$: $x_i \rightarrow$ seed number x_0 ; then: by the

② $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* - 4}{3} \iff x_i = \frac{3x_{i+1}+1}{4}$, or: ③ $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* - 2}{3} \iff x_i =$

$\frac{3x_{i+1}+1}{2}$, $x_0 \rightarrow$ seed number: $x_{-1,0} \dots \rightarrow$ "tail number": a ;

If: x_i is the seed number then: by the ② $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* - 4}{3} \iff x_i = \frac{3x_{i+1}+1}{4}$, or: ③ $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

$\rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i^* - 2}{3} \iff x_i = \frac{3x_{i+1}+1}{2} \dots \rightarrow$ "tail number": a ;

(2) If: x_j is the tilling number, then: by the inverse function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$: $x_j \rightarrow$ seed number x_0 ; then: by the

② $x_j \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{j+1} = \frac{x_j^* - 4}{3} \iff x_j = \frac{3x_{j+1}+1}{4}$, or: ③ $x_j \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{j+1} = \frac{x_j^* - 2}{3} \iff x_j =$

$\frac{3x_{j+1}+1}{2}$, $x_0 \rightarrow$ seed number: $x_{-1,0} \dots \rightarrow$ "tail number": b ;

If: x_j is the seed number then: by the ② $x_j \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{j+1} = \frac{x_j^* - 4}{3} \iff x_j = \frac{3x_{j+1}+1}{4}$, or: ③ $x_j \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

$\rightarrow x_{j+1} = \frac{x_j^* - 2}{3} \iff x_j = \frac{3x_{j+1}+1}{2}$, $x_0 \rightarrow$ seed number: $x_{-1,0} \dots \rightarrow$ "tail number": b ;

∴ If: $\exists x_i = x_j; \rightarrow a = b$, This contradiction with $a \neq b$;

∴ $\forall x_i \in T(a); \forall x_j \in T(b); a = \frac{4^k-1}{3}, b = \frac{4^j-1}{3}, k \neq j, a \neq b; \Rightarrow x_i \neq x_j$

∴ $T(a) \cap T(b) = \emptyset, (a \neq b)$.

Such as: $T(5) \cap T(85) = \emptyset; T(5) \cap T(341) = \emptyset; T(5) \cap T(5461) = \emptyset; T(5) \cap T(21845) = \emptyset; \dots$

$T(85) \cap T(341) = \emptyset; T(85) \cap T(5461) = \emptyset; T(85) \cap T(21845) = \emptyset; \dots$

$T(341) \cap T(5461) = \emptyset; T(341) \cap T(21845) = \emptyset; T(341) \cap T(349525) = \emptyset; \dots$

$$T(5461) \cap T(21845) = \emptyset ; T(5461) \cap T(349525) = \emptyset ; T(5461) \cap T(1398101) = \emptyset ; \dots$$

$$T\left(\frac{4^k-1}{3}\right) \cap T\left(\frac{4^j-1}{3}\right) = \emptyset \quad (k \neq j);$$

Explanation: Since the odd number of $\frac{4^k-1}{3} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ is the ultimate iteration, they appear not generate directly algebraic topological spaces composed of odd numbers. Instead, they can only be used as the stem number to produce corresponding leaf numbers, there by forming an infinite-level leaf number phase space. However, they can still generate indirectly algebraic topological spaces, through the tillering function, thereby producing 1-th order tillering odd number $x_i = \frac{4^k-1}{3} \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow (4x_i + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or 2-th order tillering odd number: $x_i = \frac{4^k-1}{3} \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow (16x_i + 5) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. Indirectly, this leads to the creation of algebraic topological spaces, So $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ that cannot be observed in forward iteration.

$$\text{denoted by: } L\left(x_i = \frac{4^k-1}{3} \equiv 0\right) = x_i * 2^k \quad (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

such as:

$$\frac{4^k-1}{3} = 21 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow \text{the leaf number phase space: } L(21) = 21 * 2^k, (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

$$\frac{4^k-1}{3} = 1365 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow \text{the leaf number phase space: } L(1365) = 1365 * 2^k, (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

$$\frac{4^k-1}{3} = 87381 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow \text{the leaf number phase space: } L(87381) = 87381 * 2^k, (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

.....

$$\frac{4^k-1}{3} \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow \text{the leaf number phase space: } L\left(\frac{4^k-1}{3}\right) = \frac{4^k-1}{3} * 2^k, (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

$$\therefore \# T(21); \# T(1365); \# T(87381); \dots \# T\left(\frac{4^k-1}{3} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}\right);$$

$$\text{Only } \exists L\left(\frac{4^k-1}{3}\right) = \frac{4^k-1}{3} * 2^k, (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

But for i-th iteration odd number ($i \geq 2$), $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow$ by the tillering function $x_i \rightarrow (4x_i + 1) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$; or $x_i \rightarrow (16x_i + 5) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$; $\exists T\left(\frac{3x_i-1}{3} * 4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}\right)$

such as:

$$x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow (4x_2+1)=13; \rightarrow x_2=13\equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow T(13);$$

$$x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow (16x_2+5)=53; \rightarrow x_2=53\equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow T(53);$$

$$x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-1} - \frac{1}{3}, T_3=213; \rightarrow x_2=213\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow L(213);$$

$$x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-1} - \frac{1}{3}, T_4=853; \rightarrow x_2=853\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$$

$$\rightarrow T(853);$$

$$x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-1} - \frac{1}{3}, T_5=3413; \rightarrow x_2=3413\equiv 2 \pmod{3}$$

$$\rightarrow T(3413);$$

$$x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^{n-1} - \frac{1}{3}, T_6=13653; \rightarrow x_2=13653\equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow L(13653);$$

.....

So $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ that cannot be observed in forward iteration.

such as: $x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3}; x_2=213\equiv 0 \pmod{3}; x_2=13653\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

For example:

the ultimate iteration: $x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, in backward iteration : $x_2=3 \rightarrow T_1=13$; or $T_2=53$; and so on, generate indirectly algebraic topological spaces $T(13)$ or $T(53)$, and so on;

But in forward iteration : $13 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1$, There is no $x_2=3$, only indirectly by $T_1=13$; in fact $C_{\text{odd}}(3)=C_{\text{odd}}(13)=2$;

$53 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1$, There is no $x_2=3$, only indirectly by $T_2=53$; in fact $C_{\text{odd}}(3)=C_{\text{odd}}(53)=2$;

So $x_2=3\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ that cannot be observed in forward iteration.

【Inference 1(collatz forward Iteration odd numbers Closed Theorem1)】 : In the forward collatz pure odd number iteration path ,The odd sequence of generated from the same odd number, until it return to “1” . They can only belong to the same algebraic topological space with the same “tail number” .

For example:

$$\textcircled{1} 5\text{-tail: } 57 \rightarrow 43 \rightarrow 65 \rightarrow 49 \rightarrow 37 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 13 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 1$$

$$\textcircled{2} 85\text{-tail: } 144163 \rightarrow 216245 \rightarrow 20273 \rightarrow 15205 \rightarrow 2851 \rightarrow 4277 \rightarrow 401 \rightarrow 301 \rightarrow 113 \rightarrow 85 \rightarrow 1$$

$$\textcircled{3} 341\text{-tail: } 2263 \rightarrow 3395 \rightarrow 5093 \rightarrow 955 \rightarrow 1433 \rightarrow 1075 \rightarrow 1613 \rightarrow 605 \rightarrow 227 \rightarrow 341 \rightarrow 1$$

④5461-tail:2327347→3491021→1309133→490925→184097→138073→103555→155333→29125
→5461→1

⑤21845-tail:581837→218189→81821→30683→46025→34519→51779→77669→14563→21845→
1

⑥349525-tail:74481113→55860835→83791253→3927715→5891573→552335→828503→1242755
→1864133→349525→1

⑦1398101-tail:148962563→2234433845→41895721→3142791→47132687→70699031→10604854
7→159072821→14913077→1398101→1

⑧22369621-tail:595850387→893775581→335165843→502748765→188530787→282796181→132
56071→19884107→29826161→22369621→1

⑨89478485-tail:2383401671→3575102507→5362653761→4021990321→3016492741→565592389
→106048573→39768215→59625323→89478485→1

⑩1431655765-tail:38134427553→28600820665→21450615499→32175923249→24131942437→45
24739207→6787108811→10180663217→7635497413→1431655765→1

⑪5726623061-tail:156198615314987→234297922972481→175723442229361→131792581672021
→1544444316469→144791654669→54296870501→10180663219→13270994829→5726623061→1

【Inference 2】:(collatz inverse Iteration seed odd numbers Closed Theorem 2): In the inverse iteration path of the seed odd number until it returns to “1”, All the odd numbers generated by the inverse iteration form a closed set, and they all belong to the same algebraic topological space associated with that seed odd number. The algebraic topological spaces generated by different seed odd numbers are disjoint from each other, meaning their elements are pairwise distinct.

$$T(x_i) \cap T(x_j) = \emptyset \quad (x_i, x_j \text{ both are seed odd numbers, and } x_i \neq x_j)$$

$$L(x_i) \cap L(x_j) = \emptyset \quad (x_i, x_j \text{ both are the ultimate iteration odd numbers, and } x_i \neq x_j)$$

$$T(x_i) \cap L(x_j) = \emptyset \quad (x_i \text{ is seed odd number, } x_j \text{ is the ultimate iteration odd number, since } T(x_i) \text{ is the set of odd numbers, } L(x_j) \text{ is the set of even numbers})$$

【Definition】 :The fast iterations odd number within the continuously extended interval, and the fastest iterations odd number within the continuously extended interval.

Definition: $x_i \in I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}] (k \in \mathbb{N})$, If $C_{\text{odd}}(x_i)$ is relatively large within the continuously extended interval, then x_i is called The fast iterations odd number. If $C_{\text{odd}}(x_i)$ is the largest within the continuously extended interval, then x_i is called the fastest iterations odd number.

Analysis of generation principle about the The fast iterations odd number and the fastest iterations odd number :

During the generation of principle analysis, The tilling odd number is abbreviated as “T”, and The seed odd number is abbreviated as “S”. The ultimate iteration odd number is abbreviated as “U”.

① $I_1=[1,4]$, The fastest iterations odd number is “3”: $1 \rightarrow 5(T) \rightarrow 3(U)$,

$\therefore (T):(U):(S)=1:1:0 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(3)=2$; The total number of iterations from 3 to 1 is 5.

② $I_2=[5,20]$, The fastest iterations odd number is “9” or “19” :
 $1 \rightarrow 5(T) \rightarrow 3(U) \rightarrow 13(T) \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 9(U)$.

$\therefore (T):(U):(S)=2:2:3 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(9)=6$; The total number of iterations from 9 to 1 is 19.

$1 \rightarrow 5(T) \rightarrow 13(T) \rightarrow 17 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 29(T) \rightarrow 19$.

$\therefore (T):(U):(S)=3:0:3 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(19)=6$; The total number of iterations from 19 to 1 is 19.

③ $I_3=[21,84]$, The fastest iterations odd number is “73”; The fast iterations odd number is “55” or “27”;

$1 \rightarrow 5(T) \rightarrow 53(T) \rightarrow 35 \rightarrow 23 \rightarrow 61(T) \rightarrow 325(T) \rightarrow 433 \rightarrow 577 \rightarrow 3077(T) \rightarrow 2051 \rightarrow 1367 \rightarrow 911 \rightarrow 2429(T) \rightarrow 1619 \rightarrow 1079 \rightarrow 719 \rightarrow 479 \rightarrow 319 \rightarrow 425 \rightarrow 283 \rightarrow 377 \rightarrow 251 \rightarrow 167 \rightarrow 445(T) \rightarrow 593 \rightarrow 395 \rightarrow 263 \rightarrow 175 \rightarrow 233 \rightarrow 155 \rightarrow 103 \rightarrow 137 \rightarrow 91 \rightarrow 121 \rightarrow 161 \rightarrow 107 \rightarrow 71 \rightarrow 47 \rightarrow 125(T) \rightarrow 83 \rightarrow 55 \rightarrow 73$;

$\therefore (T):(S)=8:34 \approx 0.2353 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(73)=42; C_{\text{even}}(73)=73$; The total number of iterations from 73 to 1 is 115.

For The fast iterations odd number is “55”

$\therefore (T):(S)=8:33 \approx 0.2424 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(55)=41; C_{\text{even}}(55)=71$; The total number of iterations from 55 to 1 is 112.

For The fast iterations odd number is “27”

$1 \rightarrow 5(T) \rightarrow 53(T) \rightarrow 35 \rightarrow 23 \rightarrow 61(T) \rightarrow 325(T) \rightarrow 433 \rightarrow 577 \rightarrow 3077(T) \rightarrow 2051 \rightarrow 1367 \rightarrow 911 \rightarrow 2429(T) \rightarrow 1619 \rightarrow 1079 \rightarrow 719 \rightarrow 479 \rightarrow 319 \rightarrow 425 \rightarrow 283 \rightarrow 377 \rightarrow 251 \rightarrow 167 \rightarrow 445(T) \rightarrow 593 \rightarrow 395 \rightarrow 263 \rightarrow 175 \rightarrow 233 \rightarrow 155 \rightarrow 103 \rightarrow 137 \rightarrow 91 \rightarrow 121 \rightarrow 161 \rightarrow 107 \rightarrow 71 \rightarrow 47 \rightarrow 31 \rightarrow 41 \rightarrow 27$

$\therefore (T):(S)=7:34 \approx 0.2058 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(27)=41; C_{\text{even}}(27)=70$; The total number of iterations from 27 to 1 is 111.

④ $I_4=[85,340]$, The fastest iterations odd number is “327”; The fast iterations odd number is “313” or “231”;

$1 \rightarrow 5(T) \rightarrow 53(T) \rightarrow 35 \rightarrow 23 \rightarrow 61(T) \rightarrow 325(T) \rightarrow 433 \rightarrow 577 \rightarrow 3077(T) \rightarrow 2051 \rightarrow 1367 \rightarrow 911 \rightarrow 2429(T) \rightarrow 1619 \rightarrow 1079 \rightarrow 719 \rightarrow 479 \rightarrow 319 \rightarrow 425 \rightarrow 283 \rightarrow 377 \rightarrow 251 \rightarrow 167 \rightarrow 445(T) \rightarrow 593 \rightarrow 395 \rightarrow 263 \rightarrow 175 \rightarrow 233 \rightarrow 155 \rightarrow 103 \rightarrow 137 \rightarrow 91 \rightarrow 121 \rightarrow 161 \rightarrow 107 \rightarrow 71 \rightarrow 47 \rightarrow 125(T) \rightarrow 1333(T) \rightarrow 1777 \rightarrow 2369 \rightarrow 1579 \rightarrow 2105 \rightarrow 1404 \rightarrow 935 \rightarrow 623 \rightarrow 415 \rightarrow 553 \rightarrow 737 \rightarrow 491 \rightarrow 327$

$\therefore (T):(S)=9:43 \approx 0.2093 \therefore C_{\text{odd}}(327)=52; C_{\text{even}}(327)=91$; The total number of iterations from 327 to 1 is 143.

For The fast iterations odd number is “313”

1→5(T)→53(T)→35→23→61(T)→325(T)→433→577→3077(T)→2051→1367→911→2429(T)→1619→1079→719→479→319→425→283→377→251→167→445(T)→593→395→263→175→233→155→103→137→91→485(T)→323→215→143→95→253→337→449→299→199→265→353→235→313

∴(T):(S)=8:39≈0.2051 ∴C_{odd}(313)=47;C_{even}(313)=93;The total number of iterations from 313 to 1 is 130.

For The fast iterations odd number is“231”

1→5(T)→53(T)→35→23→61(T)→325(T)→433→577→3077(T)→2051→1367→911→2429(T)→1619→1079→719→479→319→425→283→377→251→167→445(T)→593→395→263→175→233→155→103→137→91→121→161→107→71→47→31→661(T)→881→587→391→521→347→231

∴(T):(S)=8:38≈0.2105 ∴C_{odd}(231)=46;C_{even}(231)=81;The total number of iterations from 231 to 1 is 127.

⑤I₅=[341,1364],The fastest iterations odd number is“1161”;The fast iterations odd number is“871”or“1249”;

1→5(T)→53(T)→35→23→61(T)→325(T)→433→577→3077(T)→2051→1367→911→2429(T)→1619→1079→719→479→319→425→283→377→251→167→445(T)→593→395→263→175→233→155→103→137→91→485(T)→323→215→143→95→253(T)→337→449→299→797(T)→2125(T)→11333(T)→7555→10073→6715→8953→47749(T)→63665→42443→28295→18863→12575→8383→11171→7451→4967→3311→2207→1471→1961→1307→871→1161

∴(T):(S)=13:53≈0.2453 ∴C_{odd}(1161)=66;C_{even}(1161)=125;The total number of iterations from 1161to 1 is 181

For The fast iterations odd number is“871”

∴(T):(S)=13:52≈0.25 ∴C_{odd}(871)=65;C_{even}(871)=113;The total number of iterations from 871to 1 is 178.

1→5(T)→13(T)→17→11→29(T)→19→101(T)→67→89→59→157(T)→3349→4465→23813(T)→15875→10583→7055→4703→50165(T)→33443→22295→14863→19817→13211→8807→23485(T)→31313→83501(T)→55667→37111→49481→32987→21991→29321→19547→13031→8687→5791→7721→5147→3431→2287→12197(T)→32525(T)→21683→14455→19273→25697→17131→22841→15227→10151→6767→4511→3007→4009→5345→3563→2375→1583→1055→703→937→1249.

∴(T):(S)=11:53≈0.2075 ∴C_{odd}(1249)=64;C_{even}(1249)=112;The total number of iterations from 1249to 1 is 176.

⑥I₆=[1365,5460],The fastest iterations odd number is“3711”;The fast iterations odd number is“2919”or“4319”;

1→5(T)→53(T)→35→23→61(T)→325(T)→433→577→3077(T)→2051→1367→911→2429(T)→1619→1079→719→479→319→425→283→377→251→167→445(T)→593→395→263→175→233→155→103→137→91→121→161→107→71→47→125(T)→83→55→73→97→517(T)→689→1837(T)→2449→13061→8707→11609→7739→5159→3439→4585→6439→8585→5723→3815→2543→27125(T)→18083→48221(T)→32147→21431→14287→19049→50797→67729→90305→60203→160541→107027→71351→47567→31711→42281→28187→18791→12527→8351→5567→3711;

∴(T):(S)=12:75≈0.16 ∴C_{odd}(3711)=87;C_{even}(3711)=150;The total number of iterations from 3711 to 1 is 237.

For The fast iterations odd number is“2919”

1→5(T)→13(T)→17→11→29(T)→19→101(T)→67→89→59→157(T)→3349→4465→23813(T)→15875→10583→7055→4703→50165(T)→33443→22295→14863→19817→13211→8807→23485(T)→31313→83501(T)→55667→37111→49481→32987→21991→29321→19547→13031→8687→5791→7721→5147→3431→2287→12197(T)→32525(T)→21683→14455→19273→25697→17131→22841→15227→10151→6767→4511→3007→4009→5345→3563→2375→1583→1055→703→937→4997(T)→3331→4441→5921→3947→10525(T)→14033→37421(T)→24947→16631→11087→7391→4927→6569→4379→2919

∴(T):(S)=14:65≈0.2153 ∴C_{odd}(2919)=79;C_{even}(2919)=65;The total number of iterations from 2919 to 1 is 216.

For The fast iterations odd number is“4379”

∴(T):(S)=14:64≈0.2187 ∴C_{odd}(4379)=78;C_{even}(4379)=64;The total number of iterations from 4379 to 1 is 214.

Summary: (1) Each tillering odd number corresponds to an odd seed number. This seed number can be $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ or $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. The classification of active tillering and passive tillering. For example, $61=4 \times 15+1$ ($15 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$); $325=4 \times 81+1$ ($81 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$); $445=4 \times 111+1$ ($111 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$); $1837=4 \times 459+1$ ($459 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$) are active tillering, while $125=4 \times 31+1$ ($31 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$); $3077=4 \times 769+1$ ($769 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$); $2429=4 \times 607+1$ ($607 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$) are passive tillering. These numbers are hidden during the iteration process and are used to distinguish between direct and indirect consecutive iterations. (2) In the paths of fast iteration odd numbers and fastest iteration odd numbers, the ratio of the number of tillering odd numbers to the number of seed odd numbers is very small, fluctuating around 0.21. There was even an extremely low value of 0.16. This phenomenon indicates that the classification based on modulo-3 remainders and modulo-2 remainders cannot be reconciled during the iteration process. It does not represent so-called chaos.

We continue to count the fastest iteration odd numbers and rapid iteration odd numbers within the continuous expansion interval as follows:

$I_1=[1,4]$	The fastest or fast iterations odd number	The counts of the pure odd number iterations	The total number of iterations from "n" to 1	$R=\frac{C_t}{C_s}$	$R=\frac{C_{odd(n)}}{C_{total}}$
	3	2	5	2:0	40.00%
$I_2=[5,20]$	9	6	19	4:2	31.58%
	19	6	19	3:3	31.58%
$I_3=[21,84]$	73	42	115	8:34	36.52%
	55	41	112	8:33	36.61%
	27	41	111	7:34	36.94%
$I_4=[85,340]$	327	52	143	9:43	36.36%
	313	47	130	8:39	36.15%
	231	46	127	8:38	36.22%
$I_4=[341,1364]$	1161	66	181	13:53	36.46%
	871	65	178	13:52	36.52%
	1249	64	176	11:53	36.36%
$I_6=[1365,5460]$	3711	87	237	12:75	36.71%
	2919	79	216	14:65	36.57%
	4379	78	214	14:64	36.49%
$I_7=[5461,21844]$	17647	102	280		36.43%
	17673	102	280		36.43%
	13255	101	275		36.73%
	19593	100	273		36.63%
	19883	100	273		36.63%

I ₈ =[21845,87381]	77031	129	350		36.86%
	52527	125	339		36.87%
	87087	122	332		36.75%
	35655	119	323		36.84%
I ₉ =[87381,349525]	230631	164	442		37.10%
	345947	163	440		37.04%
	263103	150	406		36.95%
	270271	150	406		36.95%
	288489	143	388		36.86%
	288615	143	388		36.86%
I ₁₀ =[349525,1398100]	1117065	196	527		37.19%
	1126015	196	527		37.19%
	837799	195	524		37.21%
	1256699	194	522		37.16%
	1252663	189	509		37.13%
	1345383	187	504		37.10%
	1302127	182	491		37.07%
	1365161	175	473		36.99%
	1390505	175	473		36.99%
	1194143	172	465		36.99%
	1151855	172	465		36.99%
	1394431	170	460		36.99%
	1250857	165	447		36.91%
	1384329	163	442		36.88%

Section 1: Methods of Generating Odd Numbers

① $1 \rightarrow$ By tilling function: $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} (n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty)$

$1 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 21 \rightarrow 85 \rightarrow 341 \rightarrow 1365 \rightarrow 5461 \rightarrow 21845 \rightarrow 87381 \rightarrow 349525 \rightarrow 1398101 \rightarrow 5592405 \rightarrow 22369621 \rightarrow 89478485 \rightarrow 357913941 \rightarrow 1431655765 \rightarrow 5726623061 \rightarrow 22906492245 \rightarrow 91625968981 \rightarrow 366503875925 \rightarrow 1466015503701 \rightarrow 5864062014805 \rightarrow 23456248059221 \rightarrow 93824992236885 \rightarrow 375299968947541 \rightarrow \dots$

$\rightarrow \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} (n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty)$

② Classify according to the remainder modulo 3 for filtering: $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$;

Select the odd numbers that can continue iterating and reproducing: $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$; as well as the ultimate iterative odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

③ For the odd numbers that can continue iterating and reproducing:

$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; (“expansion reproduction”)

$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$; (“contraction reproduction”)

For the ultimate iterative odd numbers :By the leaf function: $L(x) = x * 2^k (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty)$, Generating the leaf numbers

$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_i * 2^k (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty)$

④ For the all new Generating Odd Numbers: x_{i+1}

Repeat the ①, ②, ③ steps to obtain the odd numbers of $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots \rightarrow x_i \rightarrow x_{i+1} \rightarrow (i \rightarrow \infty)$

(Explanation: The odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, Although it is the ultimate iterative odd numbers, but it can be tilling)

The reverse generation of odd numbers can be summarized in three steps: tilling, filtering, and iteration. Iteration itself is further divided into two methods: “expansion reproduction” and “contraction reproduction”.

The overall process is as follows:

$1 \rightarrow$ By tilling function $\rightarrow \{x_i = \frac{4^n - 1}{3} \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty)\}$,

From $\{x_i = \frac{4^n - 1}{3} \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty)\}$ filter $\rightarrow \{x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}\}$

$$X_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 4 - 1}{3}; (\text{“expansion reproduction”})$$

$$X_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2 - 1}{3}; (\text{“contraction reproduction”})$$

$$\begin{cases} x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 4 - 1}{3} \\ x_2 = \frac{x_1 * 2 - 1}{3} \end{cases} \rightarrow \{x_2\} \rightarrow \text{By tillering function} \rightarrow \{x_2\} \rightarrow \text{filter}$$

$$\rightarrow \{x_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, x_2 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}\} \rightarrow \dots$$

Section 2: Methods of Generating even Numbers

For any stem number x_i , By the leaf function: $L(x_i) = x_i * 2^k (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty)$, Generating the leaf numbers.

Section 3: The Relationship Between the Number of Iterations and the Range of Odd Numbers Generated.

(1) For any leaf number, corresponds to a phase space belonging to a certain stem number. This stem number is the unique attractor of that phase space. Therefore, for any leaf number, its corresponding stem number can be uniquely determined through the inverse function of the leaf function. The inverse function of an k -th leaf function is $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k}$. Through the inverse functions of leaf functions, any leaf number can be uniquely mapped to its corresponding stem number ($k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$).

$$\forall \text{ leaf number } x_i * 2^k \in L(x_i) = x_i * 2^k (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty)$$

$$\therefore x_i * 2^k \rightarrow L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k} \rightarrow x_i$$

(2) From the complete coverage of all odd numbers by the continuously expanding intervals, it can be concluded that:

$$\forall \text{ odd number } x_i \in \bigcup_1^\infty I_k = \mathbb{N} \rightarrow x_i \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^k - 1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1} - 4}{3} \right] (k \in \mathbb{N})$$

If x_i is the tillering odd number, since **【Lemma 5】** By the inverse tracing function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$.

$$x_i \rightarrow \exists \frac{x_i - 1}{4} \in I_{k-1}; \text{ and: } C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{x_i - 1}{4}\right) = i.$$

$\therefore \forall$ odd number “ x ”, $\exists I_k$ or I_{k-1} , let “ x ” Complete iterations within this extended range.

(3) Since the tillering function and its inverse function form a bijection between the parent extended interval and the child extended interval, each odd number, may be a tillering odd number, or may be a seed odd number, but it remains the only one that exists. The counts of iterations is the only certain.

a tiling number $\xrightarrow{\text{bijection}}$ a seed number

① \forall "x" is leaf number \rightarrow By The inverse function of an k-th leaf function is $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k} : \text{"x"} \rightarrow x_i$

Since the "k" is only one, \forall "x" is leaf number is the only one that exists.

$$\therefore x_i \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^{k-1}}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right] (k \in \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{and: } C_{\text{odd}}(x) = C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = i.$$

$\therefore \forall$ leaf number "x", $\exists I_k$ or I_{k-1} , let "x" Complete iterations within this extended range.

Since stem number is the unique attractor of that phase space.

\forall "x" is leaf number, $C_{\text{odd}}(x) = i$, The counts of iterations is the only certain.

② Since (2) and (4), \forall Nature number "x", $\exists I_k$ or I_{k-1} , let "x" Complete iterations within this extended range and the counts of iterations is the only certain.

(6) All the stem number within the parent expansion interval I_k , whether through the 1-th leaf function $L(x) = x * 2^1$ or the 2-th leaf function $L(x) = x * 2^2$, will be mapped to either the parent expansion interval I_k or the sub-expansion interval I_{k+1} , thereby becoming the leaf number within these two consecutive expansion intervals $I_k - I_{k+1}$. Conversely, the 1-th leaf number and the 2-th leaf number within any two consecutive expansion intervals can be mapped back to the parent expansion interval using either the inverse of the 1-th leaf function: $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^1}$ or the inverse of the 2-th leaf function: $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^2}$. These two mapping methods constitute a "global-local bijection" at the local level between the parent expansion interval and the sub-expansion intervals. $I_k \xrightarrow{\text{bijection}} I_k - I_{k+1}$

Proof:

$$\{I_k \cup I_{k+1}\} = \left[\frac{4^{k-1}}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2}-4}{3} \right]$$

$$\forall x_i \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^{k-1}}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right] (k \in \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \frac{4^{k-1}}{3} \leq x_i \leq \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \rightarrow L(x) = x * 2^1$$

$$\rightarrow 2 * \frac{4^{k-1}}{3} \leq 2x_i \leq 2 * \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \rightarrow \frac{2 * 4^{k-1}}{3} \leq 2x_i \leq \frac{2 * 4^{k+1}-8}{3} \rightarrow 2x_i \in \left[\frac{4^{k-1}}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2}-4}{3} \right]$$

$$\rightarrow 2x_i \in \{I_k \cup I_{k+1}\}$$

$$\forall x_i \in I_k = \left[\frac{4^{k-1}}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \right] (k \in \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \frac{4^{k-1}}{3} \leq x_i \leq \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \rightarrow L(x) = x * 2^2$$

$$\rightarrow 4 * \frac{4^{k-1}}{3} \leq 4x_i \leq 4 * \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3} \rightarrow \frac{4 * 4^{k-1}}{3} \leq 4x_i \leq \frac{4 * 4^{k+1}-16}{3} \rightarrow 4x_i \in \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-8}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2}-32}{3} \right]$$

$$\therefore \left[\frac{4^{k+1}-8}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2}-32}{3} \right] \subset \left[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+2}-4}{3} \right]$$

$$\rightarrow \therefore 4x_i \in \{I_k \cup I_{k+1}\}$$

Similarly, we can prove that: $8x_i \in \{I_k \cup I_{k+1} \cup I_{k+2}\}; \dots \dots x \cdot 2^p x_i \in \{I_k \cup I_{k+1} \cup I_{k+2} \dots \cup I_{k+p}\}$; So all of leaf numbers will be mapped to $\bigcup_1^p I_k$

$$\text{Conversely, } 2x_i \in \{I_k \cup I_{k+1}\} \rightarrow x_i \in I_k$$

$$4x_i \in \{I_k \cup I_{k+1}\} \rightarrow x_i \in I_k$$

$$\therefore \forall x_i \in I_k \xrightarrow[\cong]{\text{bijection}} \{2x_i, 4x_i\} \subset \{I_k \cup I_{k+1}\} \text{ (“global-local bijection”)}$$

This is a “global-local bijection” at the local level between the parent expansion interval and the sub-expansion intervals. $I_k \xrightarrow[\cong]{\text{bijection}} I_k - I_{k+1}$

$$(7) \quad \forall x_i \in I_k \rightarrow f(x) = 4x + 1 \rightarrow (4x_i + 1) \in I_{k+1}, \rightarrow \{T_1\} \subset I_{k+1};$$

$$\therefore \forall x_i \in I_k \xrightarrow[\cong]{\text{bijection}} \{T_1\} \subset I_{k+1} \text{ (“global-local bijection”)}$$

This is a “global-local bijection” by tiling function at the parent expansion interval and the sub-expansion intervals

Similarly, we can prove that:

$$\forall x_i \in I_k \rightarrow f^2(x) = 16x + 5 \rightarrow (16x_i + 5) \in I_{k+2}, \rightarrow \{T_2\} \subset I_{k+2};$$

.....

$$\forall x_i \in I_k \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3^{x+1} \cdot 4^n - 1}{3} \rightarrow T_n = \left(\frac{3^{x+1} \cdot 4^n - 1}{3} \right) \in I_{k+n}, \rightarrow \{T_n\} \subset I_{k+n};$$

$$\therefore \forall x_i \in I_k \xrightarrow[\cong]{\text{bijection}} \{T_n\} \subset I_{k+n} \text{ (“global-local bijection”)};$$

“global-local bijection” is the fundamental cause of the hailstone phenomenon in the Collatz conjecture.

(8) For any natural number, it will return to 1 within a finitely many pure odd iterations.

Proof:

If a natural number “x” is leaf number, “x” \rightarrow By the k-th leaf inverse function: $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k} \rightarrow x_i$ (become the stem number) $\rightarrow x_i \in I_k$; Then: If x_i is a tiling number $\rightarrow x_i = T_n$ By the 1-th tiling inverse function: $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$, $T_n \rightarrow T_{n-1}$. By the 1-th tiling inverse function: $f^{-1}(x) =$

$$\frac{x-1}{4}, T_{n-1} \rightarrow T_{n-2}, \dots, T_n \rightarrow T_0 = x_i (\text{become the seed number}) \rightarrow C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = i \rightarrow C_{\text{odd}}(x) = i$$

∴ “x” will return to 1 within “i” times pure odd iterations.

From (7)(8) it follows that, Starting from the second extended interval, the natural numbers within two consecutive extended intervals, at least 37.5% of the natural numbers, The pure odd number iteration count inherited from their parent extended interval. Any explicit upper bound function estimate for the pure odd number iteration count will contain at least 37.5% redundancy.

(9) The above reasoning process is a bijection from the local to global, therefore, there is no infinite cycle that does not return to 1, Otherwise, it would contradict all lemmas, and it would also contradict the unique factorization theorem for natural number, it would also contradict the completeness of the remainders in the modulo 3 classification of natural numbers, it would also contradict the 2-adic structure of the natural numbers.

(10) since **【Lemma 9】** The convergence Theorem for Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations. and since **【Theorem】** : Different algebraic topological spaces generated by different “tail number ” do not intersect with each other. and since **【Inference】**: Inference 2 (collatz inverse Iteration seed odd numbers Closed Theorem 2): In the inverse iteration path of the seed odd number until it returns to “1”, All the odd numbers generated by the inverse iteration form a closed set, and they all belong to the same algebraic topological space associated with that seed odd number. The algebraic topological spaces generated by different seed odd numbers are disjoint from each other, meaning their elements are pairwise distinct.

∴ All of the seed odd numbers within the extension intervals, it will be covered within a finite number of pure odd iterations.

$$\therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{9^k} x_{i+k} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{8}{9}\right)^k x_i = 0$$

∴ If these seed odd numbers are not covered within within a finite number of pure odd iterations, then they directly return to 1.

(11) An explicit upper bound function for the number of pure odd iterations of all odd numbers within the extended interval

∴ There two mode of “reproductive odd numbers” x_i by Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations (non-tillering mode), then: for one time iteration

$$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}; (\text{“expansion reproduction”})$$

$$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}; (\text{“contraction reproduction”})$$

∴ Since the probability of “expansion reproduction” is equal to the probability of “contraction

reproduction”, assuming that “expansion reproduction” and “contraction reproduction” appear alternately. Therefore, the decay index when pure odd-number iterations converge is: $\frac{4}{3} * \frac{2}{3} = \frac{8}{9}$ for one time iteration. This is the same as the probability of getting heads or tails when flipping a coin.

If it takes x pure odd-number iterations for the odd number $\frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3}$ to converge to $\frac{4^k-1}{3}$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3} * \left(\frac{8}{9}\right)^x \leq \frac{4^k-1}{3}$$

$$\therefore \left(\frac{8}{9}\right)^x \leq \frac{4^k-1}{4^{k+1}-1}$$

$$\therefore x \geq \frac{\ln\left(\frac{4^k-1}{4^{k+1}-1}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{8}{9}\right)} \quad (k \in \mathbb{N})$$

When: $k=1, x_1=13.664429$;

$k=2, x_2=13.664429$;

$k=3, x_3=12.184136$;

$k=4, x_4=11.870375$;

$k=5, x_5=11.794833$;

$k=6, x_6=11.776121$;

$k=7, x_7=11.771453$;

$k=8, x_8=11.770287$;

$k=9, x_9=11.769996$;

$k=10, x_{10}=11.769923$;

$k=11, x_{11}=11.769905$;

$k=12, x_{12}=11.769900$;

$k=13, x_{13}=11.769899$;

$k=14, x_{14}=11.769899$;

$k=15, x_{15}=11.769898$;

When: $k \rightarrow \infty$, $\lim_{k=1 \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(\frac{4^k-1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{8}{5})} = \frac{2\ln 2}{2\ln 3 - 3\ln 2} = 11.769898385$;

∴ Starting from the 15th extended interval I_{15} , The number of iterations in Collatz odd-only iteration increases strictly linearly, And its slope $k=11.769898385$;

∴ The upper bound function of the number of collatz odd-only iterations is $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_n$

∴ The slope tends to stabilize starting from the 15th extended interval, The “b” of upper bound function is $\sum_{n=1}^{15} x_n = 180.88 \approx 181$.

∴ Starting from the 16th extended interval I_{16} , For expansion interval I_k , The count pure odd iterations upper bound function is: $C_{\text{odd}}(I_k) = 11.769898385(k-15) + 181 (k \geq 16)$.

Or, a more precise upper bound function expression is: $C_{\text{odd}}(I_k) = \frac{2\ln 2}{2\ln 3 - 3\ln 2}(k-15) + 181 (k \geq 16)$

【A main theory about upper bound function of collatz pure odd numbers iterations】

Let $C_{\text{odd}}(n)$ is the counts of pure odd numbers iterations for odd number “n”. For the extended interval I_k , \exists explicit upper bound function: $C_{\text{odd}}(I_k)$, it can be hold:

1. Almost all odd numbers “n” within the extended interval I_k , $C_{\text{odd}}(n) \leq C_{\text{odd}}(I_k)$;
2. Let P_k is the percentage of odd numbers that meet condition upper bound function, then:

$P_k \nearrow 1 (k \rightarrow \infty)$;

3. But for any k , \exists a few escaping odd numbers can not meet condition upper bound function, and:

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (1 - P_k) = 0$$

The table below shows the statistics of the estimation of the extended interval by this upper bound function:

The continue extended interval $[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3})$	The count of seed odd number	The upper bound count of pure odd-number iterations	The count of Escaping odd numbers	The percentage of Escaping odd numbers
[1,5)	2	13.66	0	0

[5,21)	8	27.32	0	0
[21,85)	32	39.51	4	12.5%
[85,341)	128	51.38	1	0.78%
[341,1365)	512	63.17	5	0.9765%
[1365,5461)	2048	74.95	6	0.2929%
[5461,21845)	8192	86.72	58	0.708%
[21845,87381)	32768	98.49	152	0.4638%
[87381,349525)	131072	110.26	551	0.4204%
[349525,1398101)	524288	122.03	1769	0.3374%
[1398101,5592405)	2097152	133.80	6670	0.3181%
[5592405,22369621)	8388608	145.57	23061	0.2749%
[22369621,89478485)	33554432	157.34	75345	0.2245%
[89478485,357913941)	134217728	169.11	249236	0.1857%
[357913941,1431655765)	536870912	180.88		0.1616%
[1431655765,5726623061)	2147483648	192.35		0.1335%

[5726623061,22906492245)	8589934592	204.53		0.1066%
[22906492245,91625968981)	3435973836 8	216.30		0.08784%
[91625968981,366503875925)	2199023255 552	228.07		0.0710%
[366503875925,1466015503701)	8796093022 208	239.84		0.0608%
[1466015503701,5864062014805)	3518437208 8832	251.62		0.04997%
[5864062014805,2345624805922 1)	5629499534 21312	263.39		0.04062%
[23456248059221,938249922368 85)		275.17		0.03447%
[93824992236885,375299968947 541)		286.92		0.0264%
[375299968947541,15011998757 90165)		298.69		0.0223%
[1501199875790165,6004799503 160661)		310.46		0.01743%
[6004799503160661,2401919801 2642645)		322.23		0.01323%
[24019198012642645,960767920 50570581)		334.00		0.01152%
[96076792050570581,384307168 202282325)		345.77		0.00983%
[384307168202282325,15372286 72809129301)		357.54		0.00859%
[1537228672809129301,6148914 691236517205)		369.31		0.00555%

[6148914691236517205,2459565 8764946068821)		381.08		0.004900%
[24595658764946068821,983826 35059784275285)		392.85		0.00392%
[98382635059784275285,393530 540239137101141)		404.62		0.00338%
[393530540239137101141,15741 22160956548404565)		416.39		0.00267%
[1574122160956548404565,6296 488643826193618261)		428.16		0.00233%
[6296488643826193618261,2518 5954575304774473045)		439.93		0.00189%
[25185954575304774473045,100 743818301219097892181)		451.70		0.00143%
[100743818301219097892181,40 2975273204876391568725)		463.47		0.00100%
[402975273204876391568725,16 11901092819505566274901)		475.24		0.00085%
[1611901092819505566274901,6 447604371278022265099605)		487.01		0.00083%
[6447604371278022265099605,2 5790417485112089060398421)		498.78		0.00059%
[25790417485112089060398421, 103161669940448356241593685)		510.55		0.00052%
[,)		522.32		
[,)		534.09		
[,)		545.86		

[,)		557.63		
[,)		569.40		
[,)		581.17		
[,)		592.94		

①Explanation 1 about The upper bound function of the number of collatz odd-only iterations:

Here ,the extended intervals adopt the left-closed right-open representation,which differs from the previous notation,the purpose is to adapt to the design requirements of the upper bound function,and this change has no effect on the all nature numbers within the extended intervals

②Explanation 2 about The upper bound function of the number of collatz odd-only iterations:

∴ For every extended interval $I_k = [\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-4}{3}] (k \in \mathbb{N})$, When $k \rightarrow \infty, C_{\text{odd}}(I_k)_{\text{max}} \rightarrow \infty$, But $\exists x_1 = \frac{4^k-1}{3}, C_{\text{odd}}(x_1)=1$, So in each extended interval I_k , there exist odd number whose redundancy tends to infinity.

③Explanation 3 about The upper bound function of the number of collatz odd-only iterations:

By Any explicit upper bound function estimate for the pure odd number iteration count will contain at least 37.5% redundancy.the same hold for this upper bound function

④Explanation 4 about The upper bound function of the number of collatz odd-only iterations:

From extended interval I_1 to extended interval I_{11} , It shows that

The percentage of Escaping odd numbers tends to stabilize at approximately 0.3%.

⑤Explanation 5 about The upper bound function of the number of collatz odd-only iterations:

The fastest iterations odd number is far exceeding the upper bound, It is tiny minority ,for example:

$73 \in I_3$, upper bound $C_{\text{odd}}(I_3)=39.51$, but $C_{\text{odd}}(73)_{\text{max}}=42$;

$327 \in I_4$, upper bound $C_{\text{odd}}(I_4)=51.38$, but $C_{\text{odd}}(327)_{\text{max}}=52$;

$1161 \in I_5$, upper bound $C_{\text{odd}}(I_5)=63.17$, but $C_{\text{odd}}(1161)_{\text{max}}=66$;

3711€I₆,upper bound C_{odd}(I₆)=74.95,but C_{odd}(3711)_{max}=87;
 19883€I₇,upper bound C_{odd}(I₈)=86.72,but C_{odd}(19883)_{max}=100;
 87087€I₈,upper bound C_{odd}(I₈)=98.49,but C_{odd}(87087)_{max}=122;
 230631€I₉,upper bound C_{odd}(I₉)=110.26,but C_{odd}(230631)_{max}=164;
 1117065€I₁₀,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₀)=122.03,but C_{odd}(1117065)_{max}=194;
 3732423€I₁₁,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₁)=133.80,but C_{odd}(3732423)_{max}=221;
 20638335€I₁₂,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₂)=145.57, C_{odd}(20638335)_{max}=259;
 63728127€I₁₃,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₃)=157.34, C_{odd}(63728127)_{max}=356;
 268549803€I₁₄,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₄)=169.11, C_{odd}(268549803)_{max}=361;
 1412987847€I₁₅,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₅)=180.88, C_{odd}(1412987847)_{max}=375;
 4890328815€I₁₆,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₆)=192.35, C_{odd}(4890328815)_{max}=425;
 17828259369€I₁₇,upper bound C_{odd}(I₁₇)=204.53, C_{odd}(17828259369)_{max}=456;

In summary: The tillering function determines the large redundancy in estimates using upper bound functions. The inconsistency between the classification of modulo-3 remainders and modulo-2 remainders results The fastest iterations odd number is far exceeding the upper bound.However, the number of The fast iterations odd number is extremely rare. The iteration method with $\frac{8}{9}$ as the decay exponent,Between consecutive expansion intervals, an upper bound function is constructed using an accumulation method for the number of iterations, ensures the stability and reliability of the escape rate in the upper bound function estimates.And The percentage of Escaping odd numbers clearly decreases gradually as the extended interval range increases.

12.5%→0.78%→0.9765%→0.2929%→0.708%→0.4638%→0.4204%→0.3374%→0.3181%→0.2749%→0.2245%→0.1857%→0.1616%→0.1335%→0.1066%→0.08784%→0.0710%→0.0608%→0.0497%→0.04062%→0.03447%→0.0264%→0.0223%→0.01743%→0.01323%→0.01152%→0.00983%→0.00859%→0.00555%→0.004900%→0.003920%→0.00338%→0.00267%→0.00233%→0.00189%→0.00100%→0.00085%→0.00083%→0.00059%→0.00053%→.....

【 Table of Correspondences between Estimated Upper Bounds of Pure Odd number Iteration Counts and Continuous extended intervals 】

Through the upper bound function expression :C_{odd}(I_k)= $\frac{2ln2}{2ln3-3ln2}(k-15)+181(k \geq 16)$,It shows :its

C_{odd}(I₉₉)=1169.67;C_{odd}(I₁₀₀)=1181.44;

It means the odd number $x \in [\frac{4^{99}-1}{3}, \frac{4^{100}-4}{3}]$, its Estimated Upper Bounds of Pure Odd number Iteration

Counts is ≤ 1182 . In other words, the 99.9% of odd numbers within the interval $[\frac{4^{99}-1}{3}, \frac{4^{100}-4}{3}]$, its

Estimated Upper Bounds of Pure Odd number Iteration Counts is ≤ 1182 .

(12) Statistics Table of the pure odd Iteration Times to Coverage Degree of Continuous extended intervals: Data source explanation: I₁-I₆ Calculated manually by the author. I₇-I₁₂ Calculated using Python code by the author. All of the fastest-iterating odd numbers have been verified on the renowned website <https://www.dcode.fr/collatz-conjecture>, confirming the accuracy of the data. Note: Since the total numbers of iterations on this website includes the initial odd number up to last odd number "1", while the total number of iterations defined here refers to the actual number of operations performed, the actual number of iterations is one less than the total number of iterations on the website. The description in this article is correct.

The continue extended interval $[\frac{4^k-1}{3}, \frac{4^{k+1}-1}{3})$	The upper bound count of pure odd-number iterations	The percentage of Coverage Degree	The count of pure odd-number iterations of The fastest iterations odd number	The percentage of Coverage Degree
[1,5)	13.66	100%	$C_{\text{odd}(3)}_{\text{max}}=2$	100%
[5,21)★	27.32	100%	$C_{\text{odd}(9)}_{\text{max}}=6$	100%
[21,85)	39.51	87.5%	$C_{\text{odd}(73)}_{\text{max}}=4$ 2	100%
[85,341)	51.38	99.22%	$C_{\text{odd}(327)}_{\text{max}}=$ 52	100%
[341,1365)★	63.17	99.0235%	$C_{\text{odd}(1161)}_{\text{max}}=$ 66	100%
[1365,5461)	74.95	99.7071%	$C_{\text{odd}(3711)}_{\text{max}}=$ 87	100%
[5461,21845)	86.72	99.292%	$C_{\text{odd}(17647)}_{\text{ma}}$ $x=101$	100%

[21845,87381)★	98.49	99.6362%	$C_{\text{odd}}(77031)_{\text{max}}$ $x=129$	100%
[87381,349525)	110.26	99.5794%	$C_{\text{odd}}(230631)_{\text{m}}$ $\text{ax}=164$	100%
[349525,1398101)	122.03	99.6626%	$C_{\text{odd}}(1117065)$ $\text{max}=196$	100%
[1398101,5592405)★	133.80	99.6819	$C_{\text{odd}}(3732423)$ $\text{max}=221$	100%
[5592405,22369621)	145.57	99.7251%	$C_{\text{odd}}(1573319)$ $1)_{\text{max}}=262$	100%
[22369621,89478485)	157.34	99.7755%	$C_{\text{odd}}(6372812)$ $7)_{\text{max}}=356$	100%
[89478485,357913941)★	169.11	99.8143%	$C_{\text{odd}}(2685498)$ $03)_{\text{max}}=361$	100%
[357913941,1431655765)	180.88	99.8384%	$C_{\text{odd}}(1412987)$ $847)_{\text{max}}=375$	100%
[1431655765,5726623061)	192.35	99.8665%	$C_{\text{odd}}(4890328)$ $815)_{\text{max}}=425$	100%
[5726623061,22906492245)	204.53★	99.88934%	$C_{\text{odd}}(1782825)$ $9369)_{\text{max}}=456$	100%
[22906492245,91625968981)	216.30	99.91216%	$C_{\text{odd}}(7512813)$ $8247)_{\text{max}}=461$	100%
[91625968981,366503875925)	228.07	99.9290%	$C_{\text{odd}}(2024854)$ $02111)_{\text{max}}=49$ 1	100%
[366503875925,1466015503701)	239.84★	99.9392%		
[1466015503701,5864062014805)	251.62	99.95003%		
[5864062014805,23456248059221)	263.39	99.95938%		

[23456248059221,93824992 236885)	275.17★	99.6553%		
[93824992236885,37529996 8947541)	286.92	99.9736%		
[375299968947541,1501199 875790165)	298.69	99.9777%		
[1501199875790165,600479 9503160661)	310.46★	99.98257%		
[6004799503160661,240191 98012642645)	322.23	99.98677%		
[24019198012642645,96076 792050570581)	334.00	99.98848%		
[96076792050570581,38430 7168202282325)	345.77★	99.99017%		
[384307168202282325,1537 228672809129301)	357.54	99.99141%		
[1537228672809129301,614 8914691236517205)	369.31	99.99445%		
[6148914691236517205,245 95658764946068821)	381.08★	99.9951%		
[24595658764946068821,98 382635059784275285)	392.85	99.99608%		
[98382635059784275285,39 3530540239137101141)	404.62	99.99662%		
[393530540239137101141,1 574122160956548404565)	416.39★	99.99733%		
[1574122160956548404565, 6296488643826193618261)	428.16	99.99767%		
[6296488643826193618261, 25185954575304774473045)	439.93	99.99811%		

[25185954575304774473045,100743818301219097892181)	451.70★	99.99857%		
[100743818301219097892181,402975273204876391568725)	463.47	99.9990%		
[402975273204876391568725,1611901092819505566274901)	475.24	99.99915%		
[1611901092819505566274901,6447604371278022265099605)	487.01★	99.99917%		
[6447604371278022265099605,25790417485112089060398421)	498.78	99.99941%		
[25790417485112089060398421,103161669940448356241593685)	510.55	99.99948%		

Data source explanation: I_2 - I_{12} represents the results of global computation. I_{13} - I_{43} indicates that the range is divided evenly into 1 million sub-intervals, and one number is randomly selected from each of these 1 million sub-intervals. In total, 1 million odd numbers are obtained by once experiment, through multiple experiments.

The statistical data in the table above show that within The continue extended intervals, the number of iterations for the Collatz pure odd-number iteration can be accurately estimated by an upper bound

function. The existence of an escape rate does not negate the idea that “global-local bijection” $I_k \xleftrightarrow{\text{bijection}} I_{k+1}$

I_k - I_{k+1} covers set of all odd numbers cases. Instead, it provides a quantitative proof that “seeds that are odd numbers within the parent extended interval will inevitably become tillering odd numbers after a finite number of iterations.” The upper bound function serves as a quantitative estimate of collatz iterations for the total odd numbers within the extended interval. With over 99% accuracy, and trend towards 100%.coverage of the extended interval by count the fastest odd number of iterations ,Moreover, as the extended interval continues to increase, the coverage rate of this upper bound function keeps rising, approaching 100%. However, it will never reach 100%, as has been explained earlier.It shows this indicates the reliability and stability of the upper bound function, giving it theoretical value in the context of number theory.

【The characteristic theorem for odd maximum iteration counts】 : In any topological space of an odd seed odd number, the odd number within the maximum iteration count must be the remainder modulo 3 is 0.

Proof:

∴ for any odd number $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow$

$$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}; \text{("expansion reproduction")}$$

$$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}; \text{("contraction reproduction")}$$

Since **【Lemma 9】** The convergence Theorem for Collatz pure odd number reverse iterations. and since **【The algebraic topological spaces generated by different seed odd numbers are disjoint from each other, meaning their elements are pairwise distinct】**.

∴ Any odd number $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow$ After a finite number of iterations $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+k} \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

∴ The odd number within the maximum iteration count must be the remainder modulo 3 is 0.

For example:

extended interval	The odd number within the maximum iteration count	Total iteration count	The remainder modulo 3
I ₃	27	111	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₄	73	115	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$
I ₅	1161	181	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₆	3711	237	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₇	17647	278	$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$
I ₈	77031	350	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₉	230631	442	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

I ₁₀	1117065	527	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₁₁	840051	685	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₁₂	63728127	949	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₁₄	670617279	986	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₁₇	12235060455	1184	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
I ₂₁	1444338092271	1408	$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
.....

Among them: only $73 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, $17647 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Another all are $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. And :

$$x_{42} = 73 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{43} = \frac{73 * 4 - 1}{3} = 97 \rightarrow x_{43} = 97 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{44} = \frac{97 * 4 - 1}{3} = 129 \rightarrow x_{44} = 129 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} ;$$

$$x_{101} = 17647 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{102} = \frac{17647 * 4 - 1}{3} = 23529 \equiv 0 \pmod{3} .$$

As the same way ,The odd number within the more and more maximum iterations count can be find by the maximum iterations count odd numbers continue.

(13) A visualed structure of the Collatz odd-number iteration inverse tree, arranged in order of iteration count.

① Starting from the most primitive odd number “1”, the first iteration of odd numbers obtained through the tillering function consists of countless level-1 branches, known as “tail odd numbers”. These form pairwise disjoint algebraic topological spaces:

$$S_1(1), S_2(5), S_3(21), S_4(85), S_5(341), S_6(1365), S_7(5461), S_8(21845), S_9(87381), S_{10}(349525), S_{11}(1398101), S_{12}(5592405), S_{13}(22369621), S_{14}(89478485), S_{15}(357913941), S_{16}(1431655765), S_{17}(5726623061), S_{18}(22906492245), S_{19}(91625968981), S_{20}(366503875925), S_{21}(1466015503701), S_{22}(5864062014805), S_{23}(23456248059221), S_{24}(93824992236885), S_{25}(375299968947541), \dots, S_k\left(\frac{4^k - 1}{3}\right) k \rightarrow \infty,$$

②Classify the solutions of pure odd-number iteration based on their remainder modulo 3:

③For: $\{x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}\} = \{21, 1365, 87381, 5592405, 357913941, \dots\}$

$$x_1 \rightarrow L(x_1 = \frac{4^k - 1}{3} \equiv 0) = x_1 * 2^k (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty).$$

For: $\{x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}\} = \{1, 85, 5461, 349525, 22369621, \dots\}$

$$x_1 \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}; (\text{“expansion reproduction”}) \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

For: $\{x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}\} = \{5, 341, 21845, 1398101, 89478485, \dots\}$

$$x_1 \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}; (\text{“contraction reproduction”}) \rightarrow f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow$$

④Every stem number $x_i \rightarrow L(x_i) = x_i * 2^k (k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow$ leaf numbers. The collatz inverse tree is a tree in which the solutions from the 1-th iteration form the first-level branches, those from the 2-th iteration form the second-level branches, and so on. The solutions from the n-th iteration constitute the n-th-level branches. The stem number and leaf number produced at same level are pairwise disjoint. This creates a naturally occurring, infinitely extending tree with a controllable network-like neural structure.

The reverse tree generated by collatz pure odd-number iteration process resembles the growth, development, reproduction, and tillering process of wheat. Consider “1” as the most primitive seed. After countless tillering, numerous first-generation odd numbers are produced. Then, those seeds that can continue to reproduce offspring are selected. During the second planting, each seed can tillering infinitely again, produce in second-generation odd numbers. This cycle continues indefinitely. In this process, the stems of wheat similar to the odd number, while the leaf similar to even number, though leaves can grow infinitely. Here it should be emphasized that reproduction and tillering are not the same thing. This is the origin of many of the definitions used in this article. Pythagoras taught that all things are numbers, How appropriate it is to use this famous quote in reverse thinking.

Section 4: consecutive odd Synchronized collatz iteration Cluster Phenomena in the Collatz Pure Odd Number Iteration Reverse Tree

(1) For any positive integer k, we denote by k-C, the k-step consecutive odd Synchronized collatz iteration Cluster, where the letter C stands for consecutive, collatz, Cluster.

【Definition】 If “k” consecutive odd numbers have the same count steps of pure odd Collatz iterations, then we call them “k consecutive odd numbers have the same count steps of pure odd Collatz iterations Synchronized collatz iteration Cluster”, with the number of iterations being “i”, abbreviated as “k-c”.

(2) **【The representation method of “k-c”】**: We use the symbol $\langle n+k \rangle_{i,j}$ to represent “k-c”. Here, “k” denotes the number of consecutive odd-number sequences, “n” represents the first odd number in the consecutive odd-number sequence, and “i” indicates the number of iterations of pure odd numbers, and “j”

indicates the number of iterations of pure even numbers.

For example:

“2-c”:<49+2>_{7,17},<57+2>_{10,22},<65+2>_{8,17},<99+2>_{7,18},.....

“3-c”:<343+3>_{45,80},<387+3>_{43,78},<781+3>_{43,78},<841+3>_{12,29},.....

“4-c”:<943+4>_{10,26},<1494+4>_{14,33},<2359+4>_{18,40},<2655+4>_{16,37},.....

“5-c”:<4723+5>_{18,41},.....

“6-c”:<3983+6>_{15,36},<4193+6>_{20,44},.....

“7-c”:<2987+7>_{14,34},<5313+7>_{16,38},.....

“8-c”:<7453+8>_{22,48},<10635+8>_{16,39},.....

“9-c”:<7083+9>_{17,40},<27031+9>_{16,22},.....

.....

“11-c”:<57857+7>_{58,108},.....

.....

“21-c”:<7563373+21>_{34,77},.....

【Theorem】 : For every odd number in “k-c”, the total number of iterations, as well as the number of iterations for purely odd and purely even numbers, are always equal.

Proof:Here, we prove by contradiction .

First lets prove“k-c”:

Let:“k-c”=(n,n+2)_{i,j}, Then if C_{odd}(n)=i,C_{odd}(n+2)=i,and C_{even}(n)=j,

C_{even}(n+2)≠j, ∴ | C_{even}(n+2)-j | ≥1.

∴ C_{odd}(n)=i,C_{odd}(n+2)=i,

∴ n,n+2 should be n:(n+1)=1:2or2:1and n:(n+1)=1:3or3:1 .

This contradicts | (n+2)-n | =2(n≥49)(Since (49,51) is The minimum “2-c”)

∴ For any “2-c”=(n,n+2)_{i,j},the total number of iterations, as well as the number of iterations for purely odd and purely even numbers, are always equal.

For “k-c”=(a₁,a₂,a₃,.....a_m,a_{m+1},,,,,.....a_k),

The any (a_m,a_{m+1})=“2-c”,

∴ $\forall 1 \leq m \leq k-1, (a_m, a_{m+1}) = \text{“2-c”}$ the total number of iterations, as well as the number of iterations for purely odd and purely even numbers, are always equal.

∴ For every odd number in “k-c”, the total number of iterations, as well as the number of iterations for purely odd and purely even numbers, are always equal.

(3) “k-c”The distribution and density statistics statistics of the phenomenon in each consecutive extended interval. I₁-I₆Calculated manually by the author.

(4) “k-c”It has hierarchical nesting, meaning that “k-c” contains (k-1)clusters“ (k-1)-c”(k≠1).

	“2-c”	“3-c”	“4-c”	“5-c”	“6-c”	“7-c”
[1,5)	0					
	0					
[5,21)	0					
	0					
[85,340)	3					
	9.379%					
[85,341)	17					
	13.28%					
[341,1365)	77	10	1			
	15.04%	1.953%	0.19%			
[1365,5461)	357	87	29	13	7	2
	17.43%	4.248%	1.42%	0.635%	0.342%	0.097%
[5461, 21845)	12.13%	3.53%	0.82%	0.33%	0.04%	0.05%
.....

Therefore, any counts of “k-c”are not duplicated, as their starting points are different odd numbers.

(5) The following table shows the distribution and density statistics of the number of “k-c” occurrences from 11 to 34 iterations (In the table, the range of odd numbers used in the statistics is shown in parentheses after the number of iterations.) The super-large “k-c” in the table have been verified on the renowned website <https://www.dcode.fr/collatz-conjecture> , confirming the accuracy of the data:

iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"	Total	odd count	Percentage
11(≤3.4E18)	2-cluster	4727	428640	1.1028%
	3-cluster	883	428640	0.2060%
	4-cluster	111	428640	0.0259%
	5-cluster	40	428640	0.0093%
	6-cluster	12	428640	0.0028%
	7-cluster	8	428640	0.0019%
	8-cluster	2	428640	0.0005%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"	Total	odd count	Percentage
12(≤4.2E18)	2-cluster	7690	665043	1.1563%
	3-cluster	1451	665043	0.2182%
	4-cluster	224	665043	0.0337%
	5-cluster	68	665043	0.0102%
	6-cluster	18	665043	0.0027%
	7-cluster	10	665043	0.0015%
	8-cluster	5	665043	0.0008%
9-cluster	1	665043	0.0002%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"	Total	odd count	Percentage
13(≤3.03E18)	2-cluster	11478	945135	1.2144%
	3-cluster	2376	945135	0.2514%
	4-cluster	389	945135	0.0412%
	5-cluster	140	945135	0.0148%
	6-cluster	39	945135	0.0041%
	7-cluster	21	945135	0.0022%
	8-cluster	7	945135	0.0007%
	9-cluster	4	945135	0.0004%
	10-cluster	1	945135	0.0001%
	11-cluster	1	945135	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"	Total	odd count	Percentage
14(≤1.54E13)	2-cluster	18284	770096	2.3742%
	3-cluster	4031	770096	0.5234%
	4-cluster	609	770096	0.0791%
	5-cluster	539	770096	0.0700%
	6-cluster	79	770096	0.0103%
	7-cluster	38	770096	0.0049%
	8-cluster	14	770096	0.0018%
	9-cluster	8	770096	0.0010%
	10-cluster	1	770096	0.0001%

iteration cuont	11-cluster	1	Total	770096	0.0001%	
	numbers of "k-c"		odd count		Percentage	
	2-cluster	22766		943829	2.4121%	
	3-cluster	5408		943829	0.5730%	
	4-cluster	1012		943829	0.1072%	
	5-cluster	400		943829	0.0424%	
	15($\leq 9E12$)	6-cluster	128		943829	0.0136%
	7-cluster	59		943829	0.0063%	
	8-cluster	18		943829	0.0019%	
	9-cluster	8		943829	0.0008%	
	10-cluster	4		943829	0.0004%	
	11-cluster	1		943829	0.0001%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage	
	2-cluster	33710		832147	4.0510%	
	3-cluster	8510		832147	1.0227%	
	4-cluster	1454		832147	0.1747%	
	5-cluster	553		832147	0.0665%	
	6-cluster	199		832147	0.0239%	
	16($\leq 6.1E11$)	7-cluster	106		832147	0.0127%
	8-cluster	35		832147	0.0042%	
	9-cluster	16		832147	0.0019%	
	10-cluster	5		832147	0.0006%	
	11-cluster	3		832147	0.0004%	
	12-cluster	2		832147	0.0002%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage	
	2-cluster	53984		419795	12.8596%	
	3-cluster	13208		419795	3.1463%	
	4-cluster	2300		419795	0.5479%	
	5-cluster	899		419795	0.2142%	
	6-cluster	330		419795	0.0786%	
	17($\leq 1.0E9$)	7-cluster	150		419795	0.0357%
	8-cluster	50		419795	0.0119%	
	9-cluster	22		419795	0.0052%	
	10-cluster	6		419795	0.0014%	
	11-cluster	3		419795	0.0007%	
	iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
2-cluster		64043		522468	12.2578%	
3-cluster		16739		522468	3.2038%	
4-cluster		3564		522468	0.6821%	
5-cluster		1453		522468	0.2781%	
18($\leq 1.1E9$)		6-cluster	504		522468	0.0965%
7-cluster		277		522468	0.0530%	
8-cluster		110		522468	0.0211%	
9-cluster		58		522468	0.0111%	

	10-cluster	28	522468	0.0054%	
	11-cluster	15	522468	0.0029%	
	12-cluster	6	522468	0.0011%	
	13-cluster	5	522468	0.0010%	
	14-cluster	2	522468	0.0004%	
	15-cluster	1	522468	0.0002%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	81799		669604	12.2160%
	3-cluster	22947		669604	3.4270%
	4-cluster	4750		669604	0.7094%
	5-cluster	1932		669604	0.2885%
	6-cluster	743		669604	0.1110%
	7-cluster	399		669604	0.0596%
19($\leq 9.9E8$)	8-cluster	159		669604	0.0237%
	9-cluster	81		669604	0.0121%
	10-cluster	42		669604	0.0063%
	11-cluster	21		669604	0.0031%
	12-cluster	7		669604	0.0010%
	13-cluster	2		669604	0.0003%
	14-cluster	1		669604	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	109621		743727	14.7394%
	3-cluster	32169		743727	4.3254%
	4-cluster	6385		743727	0.8585%
	5-cluster	2700		743727	0.3630%
	6-cluster	1053		743727	0.1416%
	7-cluster	576		743727	0.0774%
	8-cluster	223		743727	0.0300%
	9-cluster	128		743727	0.0172%
	10-cluster	70		743727	0.0094%
20($\leq 6.6E8$)	11-cluster	39		743727	0.0052%
	12-cluster	20		743727	0.0027%
	13-cluster	10		743727	0.0013%
	14-cluster	9		743727	0.0012%
	15-cluster	2		743727	0.0003%
	16-cluster	2		743727	0.0003%
	17-cluster	1		743727	0.0001%
	18-cluster	1		743727	0.0001%
	19-cluster	1		743727	0.0001%
	20-cluster	1		743727	0.0001%
	21-cluster	1		743727	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
21($\leq 8.8E8$)	2-cluster	120344		971560	12.3867%
	3-cluster	35572		971560	3.6613%

	4-cluster	8789	971560	0.9046%	
	5-cluster	3888	971560	0.4002%	
	6-cluster	1510	971560	0.1554%	
	7-cluster	812	971560	0.0836%	
	8-cluster	321	971560	0.0330%	
	9-cluster	165	971560	0.0170%	
	10-cluster	84	971560	0.0086%	
	11-cluster	45	971560	0.0046%	
	12-cluster	20	971560	0.0021%	
	13-cluster	16	971560	0.0016%	
	14-cluster	6	971560	0.0006%	
	15-cluster	4	971560	0.0004%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	125875		794725	15.8388%
	3-cluster	40097		794725	5.0454%
	4-cluster	10584		794725	1.3318%
	5-cluster	4792		794725	0.6030%
	6-cluster	2016		794725	0.2537%
	7-cluster	1095		794725	0.1378%
22($\leq 5.8E8$)	8-cluster	446		794725	0.0561%
	9-cluster	251		794725	0.0316%
	10-cluster	134		794725	0.0169%
	11-cluster	73		794725	0.0092%
	12-cluster	28		794725	0.0035%
	13-cluster	14		794725	0.0018%
	14-cluster	5		794725	0.0006%
	15-cluster	1		794725	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	126285		843440	14.9726%
	3-cluster	40441		843440	4.7948%
	4-cluster	11843		843440	1.4041%
	5-cluster	5465		843440	0.6479%
	6-cluster	2455		843440	0.2911%
	7-cluster	1337		843440	0.1585%
	8-cluster	601		843440	0.0713%
23($\leq 7.8E8$)	9-cluster	325		843440	0.0385%
	10-cluster	182		843440	0.0216%
	11-cluster	107		843440	0.0127%
	12-cluster	57		843440	0.0068%
	13-cluster	22		843440	0.0026%
	14-cluster	11		843440	0.0013%
	15-cluster	10		843440	0.0012%
	16-cluster	6		843440	0.0007%
	17-cluster	3		843440	0.0004%

	18-cluster	1	843440	0.0001%	
	19-cluster	1	843440	0.0001%	
	20-cluster	1	843440	0.0001%	
	21-cluster	1	843440	0.0001%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	139513		1045826	13.3400%
	3-cluster	46332		1045826	4.4302%
	4-cluster	12615		1045826	1.2062%
	5-cluster	6064		1045826	0.5798%
	6-cluster	2623		1045826	0.2508%
	7-cluster	1456		1045826	0.1392%
	8-cluster	699		1045826	0.0668%
	9-cluster	376		1045826	0.0360%
	10-cluster	221		1045826	0.0211%
24($\leq 5.2E9$)	11-cluster	134		1045826	0.0128%
	12-cluster	74		1045826	0.0071%
	13-cluster	48		1045826	0.0046%
	14-cluster	17		1045826	0.0016%
	15-cluster	12		1045826	0.0011%
	16-cluster	10		1045826	0.0010%
	17-cluster	7		1045826	0.0007%
	18-cluster	5		1045826	0.0005%
	19-cluster	3		1045826	0.0003%
	20-cluster	1		1045826	0.0001%
	21-cluster	1		1045826	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	178411		999435	17.8512%
	3-cluster	58529		999435	5.8562%
	4-cluster	14200		999435	1.4208%
	5-cluster	6756		999435	0.6760%
	6-cluster	3122		999435	0.3124%
	7-cluster	1707		999435	0.1708%
	8-cluster	768		999435	0.0768%
	9-cluster	447		999435	0.0447%
25($\leq 3.48E8$)	10-cluster	254		999435	0.0254%
	11-cluster	154		999435	0.0154%
	12-cluster	84		999435	0.0084%
	13-cluster	51		999435	0.0051%
	14-cluster	17		999435	0.0017%
	15-cluster	13		999435	0.0013%
	16-cluster	10		999435	0.0010%
	17-cluster	5		999435	0.0005%
	18-cluster	3		999435	0.0003%
	19-cluster	2		999435	0.0002%

	20-cluster	1	999435	0.0001%
	21-cluster	1	999435	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	165164	1038365	15.9062%
	3-cluster	57186	1038365	5.5073%
	4-cluster	17959	1038365	1.7295%
	5-cluster	8717	1038365	0.8395%
	6-cluster	3966	1038365	0.3819%
	7-cluster	2221	1038365	0.2139%
	8-cluster	912	1038365	0.0878%
	9-cluster	547	1038365	0.0527%
	10-cluster	310	1038365	0.0299%
	11-cluster	181	1038365	0.0174%
26($\leq 4.14E8$)	12-cluster	116	1038365	0.0112%
	13-cluster	68	1038365	0.0065%
	14-cluster	39	1038365	0.0038%
	15-cluster	26	1038365	0.0025%
	16-cluster	18	1038365	0.0017%
	17-cluster	10	1038365	0.0010%
	18-cluster	8	1038365	0.0008%
	19-cluster	5	1038365	0.0005%
	20-cluster	2	1038365	0.0002%
	21-cluster	1	1038365	0.0001%
	22-cluster	1	1038365	0.0001%
	23-cluster	1	1038366	0.0001%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	58076	364631	15.9273%
	3-cluster	21720	364631	5.9567%
	4-cluster	7138	364631	1.9576%
	5-cluster	3616	364631	0.9917%
	6-cluster	1802	364631	0.4942%
	7-cluster	1026	364631	0.2814%
	8-cluster	564	364631	0.1547%
	9-cluster	349	364631	0.0957%
	10-cluster	221	364631	0.0606%
27($\leq 7.74E7$)	11-cluster	145	364631	0.0398%
	12-cluster	94	364631	0.0258%
	13-cluster	54	364631	0.0148%
	14-cluster	28	364631	0.0077%
	15-cluster	16	364631	0.0044%
	16-cluster	8	364631	0.0022%
	17-cluster	5	364631	0.0014%
	18-cluster	5	364631	0.0014%
	19-cluster	3	364631	0.0008%

	20-cluster	2	364631	0.0005%	
	21-cluster	2	364631	0.0005%	
	22-cluster	2	364631	0.0005%	
	23-cluster	2	364631	0.0005%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	61798		410773	15.0443%
	3-cluster	22200		410773	5.4044%
	4-cluster	6409		410773	1.5602%
	5-cluster	3252		410773	0.7917%
	6-cluster	1626		410773	0.3958%
	7-cluster	936		410773	0.2279%
	8-cluster	497		410773	0.1210%
	9-cluster	323		410773	0.0786%
	10-cluster	202		410773	0.0492%
	11-cluster	125		410773	0.0304%
28($\leq 9.67E7$)	12-cluster	74		410773	0.0180%
	13-cluster	55		410773	0.0134%
	14-cluster	31		410773	0.0075%
	15-cluster	16		410773	0.0039%
	16-cluster	9		410773	0.0022%
	17-cluster	4		410773	0.0010%
	18-cluster	3		410773	0.0007%
	19-cluster	2		410773	0.0005%
	20-cluster	2		410773	0.0005%
	21-cluster	1		410773	0.0002%
	22-cluster	1		410773	0.0002%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	70383		377222	18.6582%
	3-cluster	25086		377222	6.6502%
	4-cluster	6963		377222	1.8459%
	5-cluster	3553		377222	0.9419%
	6-cluster	1843		377222	0.4886%
	7-cluster	1019		377222	0.2701%
	8-cluster	458		377222	0.1214%
	9-cluster	287		377222	0.0761%
29($\leq 6.88E7$)	10-cluster	186		377222	0.0493%
	11-cluster	118		377222	0.0313%
	12-cluster	80		377222	0.0212%
	13-cluster	50		377222	0.0133%
	14-cluster	21		377222	0.0056%
	15-cluster	14		377222	0.0037%
	16-cluster	6		377222	0.0016%
	17-cluster	4		377222	0.0011%
	18-cluster	2		377222	0.0005%

	19-cluster	1	377222	0.0003%	
	20-cluster	1	377222	0.0003%	
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	62249		431905	14.4127%
	3-cluster	23017		431905	5.3292%
	4-cluster	7917		431905	1.8330%
	5-cluster	3990		431905	0.9238%
	6-cluster	1925		431905	0.4457%
	7-cluster	1094		431905	0.2533%
	8-cluster	498		431905	0.1153%
	9-cluster	297		431905	0.0688%
	10-cluster	181		431905	0.0419%
	11-cluster	98		431905	0.0227%
30($\leq 9.17E7$)	12-cluster	67		431905	0.0155%
	13-cluster	53		431905	0.0123%
	14-cluster	26		431905	0.0060%
	15-cluster	16		431905	0.0037%
	16-cluster	12		431905	0.0028%
	17-cluster	8		431905	0.0019%
	18-cluster	7		431905	0.0016%
	19-cluster	6		431905	0.0014%
	20-cluster	5		431905	0.0012%
	21-cluster	4		431905	0.0009%
	22-cluster	2		431905	0.0005%
iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"		Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	74698		434972	17.1731%
	3-cluster	26969		434972	6.2002%
	4-cluster	7217		434972	1.6592%
	5-cluster	3705		434972	0.8518%
	6-cluster	1937		434972	0.4453%
	7-cluster	1150		434972	0.2644%
	8-cluster	585		434972	0.1345%
	9-cluster	348		434972	0.0800%
	10-cluster	221		434972	0.0508%
31($\leq 1.22E8$)	11-cluster	123		434972	0.0283%
	12-cluster	75		434972	0.0172%
	13-cluster	42		434972	0.0097%
	14-cluster	23		434972	0.0053%
	15-cluster	17		434972	0.0039%
	16-cluster	10		434972	0.0023%
	17-cluster	7		434972	0.0016%
	18-cluster	5		434972	0.0011%
	19-cluster	5		434972	0.0011%
	20-cluster	2		434972	0.0005%

iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"	Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	71341	629218	11.3380%
	3-cluster	24228	629218	3.8505%
	4-cluster	8436	629218	1.3407%
	5-cluster	4240	629218	0.6739%
	6-cluster	2116	629218	0.3363%
	7-cluster	1181	629218	0.1877%
	8-cluster	484	629218	0.0769%
	9-cluster	312	629218	0.0496%
	10-cluster	187	629218	0.0297%
	11-cluster	111	629218	0.0176%
32($\leq 6.52E7$)	12-cluster	76	629218	0.0121%
	13-cluster	46	629218	0.0073%
	14-cluster	25	629218	0.0040%
	15-cluster	20	629218	0.0032%
	16-cluster	10	629218	0.0016%
	17-cluster	8	629218	0.0013%
	18-cluster	5	629218	0.0008%
	19-cluster	4	629218	0.0006%
	20-cluster	3	629218	0.0005%
	21-cluster	2	629218	0.0003%
	22-cluster	2	629218	0.0003%

iteration cuont	numbers of "k-c"	Total	odd count	Percentage
	2-cluster	133446	826703	16.1420%
	3-cluster	41765	826703	5.0520%
	4-cluster	8527	826703	1.0314%
	5-cluster	4427	826703	0.5355%
	6-cluster	2311	826703	0.2795%
	7-cluster	1323	826703	0.1600%
	8-cluster	596	826703	0.0721%
	9-cluster	379	826703	0.0458%
	10-cluster	228	826703	0.0276%
	11-cluster	124	826703	0.0150%
33($\leq 3.50E8$)	12-cluster	76	826703	0.0092%
	13-cluster	48	826703	0.0058%
	14-cluster	23	826703	0.0028%
	15-cluster	20	826703	0.0024%
	16-cluster	12	826703	0.0015%
	17-cluster	9	826703	0.0011%
	18-cluster	9	826703	0.0011%
	19-cluster	5	826703	0.0006%
	20-cluster	3	826703	0.0004%
	21-cluster	2	826703	0.0002%
	22-cluster	2	826703	0.0002%

iteration cuont	23-cluster numbers of "k-c"	1	826703	0.0001%
			Total	odd count
	2-cluster	162178	500212	32.4219%
	3-cluster	49204	500212	9.8366%
	4-cluster	11446	500212	2.2882%
	5-cluster	5747	500212	1.1489%
	6-cluster	2179	500212	0.4356%
	7-cluster	1240	500212	0.2479%
	8-cluster	558	500212	0.1116%
	9-cluster	352	500212	0.0704%
	10-cluster	206	500212	0.0412%
	11-cluster	114	500212	0.0228%
	12-cluster	79	500212	0.0158%
34(≤3.3E8)	13-cluster	50	500212	0.0100%
	14-cluster	35	500212	0.0070%
	15-cluster	27	500212	0.0054%
	16-cluster	15	500212	0.0030%
	17-cluster	12	500212	0.0024%
	18-cluster	9	500212	0.0018%
	19-cluster	7	500212	0.0014%
	20-cluster	4	500212	0.0008%
	21-cluster	3	500212	0.0006%
	22-cluster	3	500212	0.0006%
	23-cluster	1	500212	0.0002%
	24-cluster	1	500212	0.0002%
	25-cluster	1	500212	0.0002%

Statistical table data analysis: ①As the number of iterations increases, the length of “k-c” becomes longer.② Additionally, as the number of iterations increases, the density of “k-c” also rises. ③However, this density gradually decreases as k increases. ④When the density of “2-c”is the highest, reaching 37%. This is very important information.⑤The appearance of “k-c”is not accidental. The existence of “k-c”can be formally and rigorously proven using reverse iteration algorithms.

(6)“k-c”Proof of Existence:

① 【Key Lemmal1】 : If two consecutive odd numbers in a phase space are $x_{i-1,1}=n\equiv 1(mod 3)$ and $x_{i-1,2}=4n+1\equiv 2(mod 3)$ (which occurs frequently), then their corresponding sub-generation iteration odd numbers must satisfy the equation $x_i=2x_{i,2}+1$.

Proof:

For any odd number phase space : $S(x)=\{x,T_1,T_2,\dots,T_m,\dots\}(m\rightarrow\infty)$; $(x_{i-1,1}, x_{i-1,2})$ is tow odd numbers within phase space.It called synchronized odd pair.

◇ If $(x_{i-1,1},x_{i-1,2})=(x,T_1)$,and $x\equiv 1(mod 3),T_1\equiv 2(mod 3)$,

$$\because x_{i-1,1} = n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_i = \frac{n * 2^2 - 1}{3} = \frac{4n - 1}{3};$$

$$\because x_{i-1,2} = 4n + 1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_{i,2} = \frac{(4n + 1) * 2^1 - 1}{3} = \frac{8n + 1}{3};$$

$$\because 2 * \frac{4n - 1}{3} + 1 = \frac{8n + 1}{3}, \therefore x_i = 2x_{i,2} + 1$$

$$\because C_{\text{odd}}(n) = C_{\text{odd}}(4n + 1) = i - 1;$$

$$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = C_{\text{odd}}(2x_i + 1) = i. \text{ That is } C_{\text{odd}}(m) = C_{\text{odd}}(2m + 1).$$

【The range of next reproductive iterations theorem for two Consecutive tillering odd numbers】 In any phase space of a seed odd number, for two consecutive tillering odd numbers n and $(4n + 1)$, the relationship in the number of odd numbers produced by their next reproduction will definitely be $m = 2m + 1$.

Since there are infinitely many such continuous pairs of tillering odd numbers in any phase space of a seed odd number, the probability that the converse of this theorem holds increases as the number of iterations with purely odd numbers grows. As the number of iterations approaches infinity, this probability approaches 100%, but it will never equal 100% exactly.

【The converse proposition of the range of next reproductive iterations】 If two odd numbers is the pair $(m, 2m + 1)$, Their counts of pure odd number iterations is equal.

The probability that this converse proposition holds increases as the number of iterations increases. It also increases as the range of odd numbers expands. For details, please refer to the statistical report below:

(1) Complete statistics within a local region

The interval of statistics	Counts of the odd number total pairs	Count the Pairs for converse of proposition holds	percentage ratio that the converse of proposition is true
[1,5461)	1365	755	55.31%
[1,21845)	5461	3134	57, 39%

[1,87381)	21845	12897	59.04%
[1,349525)	87381	52705	60.32%
[1,1398101)	349525	214255	61.30%
[1,5592405)	1398101	868907	62.15%
[1,22369621)	5592405
.....

(2) The sample survey of a certain size for large odd number pairs:

The magnitude of the sample values	The number of samples	percentage ratio that the converse of proposition is true among it
10^8	1000	64.30%
10^9	1000	65.80%
10^{10}	1000	64.80%
10^{11}	1000	67.10%
10^{12}	1000	67.40%
10^{13}	1000	68.00%

10^{14}	1000	68.00%
10^{15}	1000	69.20%
10^{16}	1000	69.50%
10^{17}	1000	71.60%
10^{18}	1000	69.10%
10^{19}	1000	68.60%
10^{20}	1000	83.00%
10^{21}	1000	66.40%
10^{22}	1000	72.60%
10^{23}	1000	85.40%
10^{24}	1000	65.50%
10^{25}	1000	72.80%
10^{26}	1000	73.10%

10^{27}	1000	78.90%
10^{28}	1000	70.60%
10^{29}	1000	72.80%
10^{30}	1000	88.40%
10^{31}	1000	80.40%
10^{32}	1000	73.00%
10^{33}	1000	73.10%
10^{34}	1000	77.50%
10^{35}	1000	78.30%
10^{36}	1000	74.20%
10^{37}	1000	75.40%
10^{38}	1000	75.50%
10^{39}	1000	78.50%

10^{40}	1000	76.40%
10^{41}	1000	75.70%
10^{42}	1000	78.40%
10^{43}	1000	74.60%
10^{44}	1000	75.00%
10^{45}	1000	79.50%
10^{46}	1000	79.30%
10^{47}	1000	76.00%
10^{48}	1000	78.30%
10^{49}	1000	79.60%
10^{50}	1000	77.80%
10^{51}	1000	80.60%
10^{52}	1000	78.40%

10^{53}	1000	76.90%
10^{54}	1000	77.50%
10^{55}	1000	79.50%
10^{56}	1000	80.00%
10^{57}	1000	80.10%
10^{58}	1000	78.40%
10^{59}	1000	78.50%
10^{60}	1000	79.30%
10^{61}	1000	81.30%
10^{62}	1000	78.40%
10^{63}	1000	80.70%
10^{64}	1000	77.60%
10^{65}	1000	79.80%

10^{66}	1000	81.80%
10^{67}	1000	81.80%
10^{68}	1000	76.20%
10^{69}	1000	79.30%
10^{70}	1000	79.60%
10^{71}	1000	78.90%
10^{72}	1000	77.00%
10^{73}	1000	83.70%
10^{74}	1000	76.90%
10^{75}	1000	76.40%
10^{76}	1000	79.60%
10^{77}	1000	77.10%
10^{78}	1000	77.40%

10^{79}	1000	75.40%
10^{80}	1000	86.70%
10^{81}	1000	82.30%
10^{82}	1000	83.60%
10^{83}	1000	82.20%
10^{84}	1000	78.30%
10^{85}	1000	77.20%
10^{86}	1000	79.40%
10^{87}	1000	75.10%
10^{88}	1000	83.80%
10^{89}	1000	81.20%
10^{90}	1000	76.70%
10^{91}	1000	77.50%

10^{92}	1000	80.20%
10^{93}	1000	88.60%
10^{94}	1000	83.00%
10^{95}	1000	86.80%
10^{96}	1000	79.60%
10^{97}	1000	80.40%
10^{98}	1000	83.50%
10^{99}	1000	82.10%
10^{100}	1000	83.20%
.....
10^{200}	1000	88.0%
10^{500}	1000	90.4%
10^{1000}	1000	94.3%

10^{3000}	200	97.0%
.....

Data analysis: First, the statistics for numbers within the range 1–5,592,405 cover the entire range. In this case, the probability that the converse proposition holds increases gradually from 55.31% to 62.15%. Second, the statistics for values from 10^8 to 10^{100} involve selecting 1,000 samples from around that value range. Due to the small sample size, the probability fluctuations aren't very stable. However, the data shows that the probability of the converse proposition holding increases steadily, rising from 64.30% to 83.20%, with a peak of 88.60%. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the probability of the converse proposition holding increases as the data size grows, eventually approaching 100%. This pattern is similar to the behavior observed in the converse proposition of Fermat's Little Theorem.

Among the Data: Large-scale data computation is furnished by “kimi” such as the statistics for values from 10^{12} to 10^{3000}

◇ ◇ If $(x_{i-1,1}, x_{i-1,2}) = (x, T_1)$, and $x \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, T_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, T_2 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$;

$$\therefore x_{i-1,1} = T_1 = (4n+1) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_i = \frac{(4n+1)^* 4-1}{3} = \frac{16n-3}{3};$$

$$\therefore x_{i-1,2} = T_2 = 16n+5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_{i,2} = \frac{(16n+5)^* 2-1}{3} = \frac{32n+9}{3};$$

$$\therefore 2 * \frac{16n-3}{3} + 5 = \frac{32n+9}{3}, \therefore x_i = 2x_{i,2} + 5$$

$\therefore \exists$ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as $(n, 2n+5)$, If the seed odd number dare classified according to their remainder when divided by 3.

◇ ◇ ◇ If $(x_{i-1,1}, x_{i-1,2}) = (x, T_1)$, and $x \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, T_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, T_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$;

$$\therefore x_{i-1,1} = x = n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_i = \frac{n^* 2-1}{3} = \frac{2n-1}{3};$$

$$\therefore x_{i-1,2} = T_2 = 16n+5 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_{i,2} = \frac{(16n+5)^* 4-1}{3} = \frac{64n-19}{3};$$

$$\therefore 32 * \frac{2n-1}{3} + 7 = \frac{64n-19}{3}, \therefore x_i = 32x_{i,2} + 7$$

$\therefore \exists$ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as $(n, 32n+7)$, If the seed odd number dare classified according to their remainder when divided by 3.

$$\diamond \diamond \diamond \diamond \therefore x \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, T_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, T_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{3},$$

$$\therefore x_{i-1,1} = n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, \therefore x_{i,1} = \frac{n \cdot 2^2 - 1}{3} = \frac{4n-1}{3};$$

$$\therefore T_3 = x_{i-1,2} = 16n+5 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}, \rightarrow \text{By tiling function}$$

$$\rightarrow T_4 = x_{i-1,2} = 64n+21 \equiv 1 \pmod{3},$$

$$\therefore x_{i,2} = \frac{(64n+21) \cdot 4 - 1}{3} = \frac{64n+83}{3};$$

$$\therefore 16 \cdot \frac{4n-1}{3} + 33 = \frac{64n+83}{3}, \therefore x_{i,2} = 16 x_{i,1} + 33$$

$$\therefore \text{any odd number } n \rightarrow \text{By tiling function} \rightarrow (4n+1)$$

$$\therefore \exists \text{ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as } (n, 4n+1);$$

$$\therefore (2n+1) \rightarrow \text{By tiling function} \rightarrow (8n+5);$$

$$\therefore \exists \text{ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as } (n, 8n+5);$$

$\therefore \exists$ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as $(n, 16n+33)$, If the seed odd number dare classified according to their remainder when divided by 3.

The above classifications discuss the most compact regions in phase space. There are many similar situations, but they will not be analyzed in detail here.

And then by the tiling function $f^l(x) = 4x+1$

$$(n, 2n+1)_k \rightarrow (4n+1, 8n+5)_k \rightarrow 8n+5 = 2(4n+1)+3 \rightarrow (m, 2m+3)_k$$

$$(n, 2n+5)_k \rightarrow (4n+1, 8n+21)_k \rightarrow 8n+21 = 2(4n+1)+19 \rightarrow (m, 2m+19)_k$$

$$(n, 8n+5)_k \rightarrow (4n+1, 32n+21)_k \rightarrow 32n+21 = 8(4n+1)+15 \rightarrow (m, 8m+15)_k$$

$$(n, 16n+33)_k \rightarrow (4n+1, 64n+133)_k \rightarrow 64n+133 = 16(4n+1)+117 \rightarrow (m, 16m+117)_k$$

$$(n, 32n+7)_k \rightarrow (4n+1, 128n+29)_k \rightarrow 128n+29 = 32(4n+1)-3 \rightarrow (m, 32m-3)_k$$

$\therefore \exists$ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as $(n, 2n+1)_k, (n, 2n+5)_k, (n, 4n+1)_k, (n, 8n+5)_k, (n, 16n+33)_k, (n, 32n+7)_k, (m, 2m+3)_k, (m, 2m+19)_k, (m, 8m+15)_k, (m, 16m+117)_k, (m, 32m-3)_k, \dots$

By the same way:

$$(m, 2m+3)_k \rightarrow (4m+1, 8m+13)_k \rightarrow 8m+13 = 2(4m+1)+11 \rightarrow (t, 2t+11)_k$$

$$(m, 2m+19)_k \rightarrow (4m+1, 8m+77)_k \rightarrow 8m+77=2(4m+1)+75 \rightarrow (t, 2t+75)_k$$

$$(m, 32m-3)_k \rightarrow (4m+1, 128m-11)_k \rightarrow 128m-11=32(4m+1)+43 \rightarrow (t, 32t+43)_k, \dots$$

$\therefore \exists$ a vast amount of synchronized odd pair, form as $(t, 2t+11)_k, (t, 2t+75)_k, (t, 32t+43)_k, \dots$

By the same way, It can be continue to forever. This is closely related to the 2-adic structure of natural numbers.

② Key Lemma2: The expression for the 1-th order tiling Function is: $f^1(x)=4x+1$

\therefore synchronized odd: $n, (2n+1), (4n+1), (2n+3), (2n+5), (4n+5), (8n+5), (16n+5), \dots$. It's easy to become consecutive odd numbers

③ Key Lemma3: Based on Key Lemma2, "2-c" can be concluded that usually appears consecutively, at the position of twice the previous of "2-c".

"2-c" Proof of Existence:

Proof:

First case:

If n is an odd number, and $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

And $(2n+3)$ is an odd number, and $(2n+3) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

Meet condition $C_{\text{odd}}(n)=C_{\text{odd}}(2n+3)=k$, Then:

$$n \rightarrow \frac{4n-1}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}\right)=k+1;$$

$$(2n+3) \rightarrow \frac{2(2n+3)-1}{3} = \frac{4n+5}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4n+5}{3}\right)=k+1;$$

$$\therefore \frac{4n+5}{3} - \frac{4n-1}{3} = 2;$$

$\therefore \frac{4n-1}{3}, \frac{4n+5}{3}$ to become two consecutive odd numbers and their pure odd count of iterations is equal.

$\therefore \exists n$, Let $\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}, \frac{4n+5}{3}\right)$ is synchronized odd pair, It is a "2-c"

And this "2-c" is generated from synchronized odd pair $(n, 2n+3)$.

Second case:

If n is an odd number, and $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

And $(2n-3)$ is an odd number, and $(2n-3) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

Meet condition $C_{\text{odd}}(n) = C_{\text{odd}}(2n-3) = k$, Then:

$$n \rightarrow \frac{4n-1}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$(2n-3) \rightarrow \frac{2(2n-3)-1}{3} = \frac{4n-7}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4n-7}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$\therefore \frac{4n-1}{3} - \frac{4n-7}{3} = 2;$$

$\therefore \frac{4n-7}{3}, \frac{4n-1}{3}$ to become two consecutive odd numbers. and their pure odd count of iterations is equal.

$\therefore \exists n$, Let $\left(\frac{4n-7}{3}, \frac{4n-1}{3}\right)$ is synchronized odd pair, It is a "2-c"

And this "2-c" is generated from synchronized odd pair $(n, 2n-3)$.

Third case:

If n is an odd number, and $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

And $(8n-3)$ is an odd number, and $(8n-3) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

Meet condition $C_{\text{odd}}(n) = C_{\text{odd}}(8n-3) = k$, Then:

$$n \rightarrow \frac{4n-1}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}\right) = k+1; \rightarrow T_1\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}\right) = 4 * \frac{4n-1}{3} + 1 = \frac{16n-4}{3} + 1 = \frac{16n-1}{3};$$

$$\rightarrow C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{16n-1}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$(8n-3) \rightarrow \frac{2(8n-3)-1}{3} = \frac{16n-7}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{16n-7}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$\therefore \frac{16n-1}{3} - \frac{16n-7}{3} = 2;$$

$\therefore \frac{16n-7}{3}, \frac{16n-1}{3}$ to become two consecutive odd numbers. and their pure odd count of iterations is equal.

$\therefore \exists n$, Let $\left(\frac{16n-7}{3}, \frac{16n-1}{3}\right)$ is synchronized odd pair, It is a "2-c"

And this "2-c" is generated from synchronized odd pair $(n, 8n-3)$.

Fourth case:

If n is an odd number, and $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

And $(8n+3)$ is an odd number, and $(8n+3) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

Meet condition $C_{\text{odd}}(n) = C_{\text{odd}}(8n+3) = k$, Then:

$$n \rightarrow \frac{4n-1}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}\right) = k+1; \rightarrow T_1\left(\frac{4n-1}{3}\right) = 4 * \frac{4n-1}{3} + 1 = \frac{16n-4}{3} + 1 = \frac{16n-1}{3};$$

$$\rightarrow C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{16n-1}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$(8n+3) \rightarrow \frac{2(8n+3)-1}{3} = \frac{16n+5}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{16n+5}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$\therefore \frac{16n+5}{3} - \frac{16n-1}{3} = 2;$$

$\therefore \frac{16n-1}{3}, \frac{16n+5}{3}$ to become two consecutive odd numbers. and their pure odd count of iterations is equal.

$\therefore \exists n$, Let $\left(\frac{16n-1}{3}, \frac{16n+5}{3}\right)$ is synchronized odd pair, It is a "2-c"

And this "2-c" is generated from synchronized odd pair $(n, 8n+3)$.

Since Key Lemma 1, Key Lemma 2 and Key Lemma 3, As the number of iterations increases, and the odd number "n" is constantly changing, So the synchronized odd of $(n, 2n-3), (n, 2n+3), (n, 8n-3)$ and $(n, 8n+3)$ will occur frequently, so the "2-c" will occur frequently too.

For example about: "2-c" can be concluded that usually appears consecutively at the position of twice the previous :

$(49, 51)_7$	$(65, 67)_8$	$(87, 89)_9$
$(99, 101)_7$	$(131, 133)_8$	$(177, 179)_9$
$(433, 435)_7$	$(633, 635)_8$	$(355, 357)_9$
$(867, 869)_7$	$(1271, 1273)_8$	$(735, 737)_9$

(1731,1715) ₇	(4667,4669) ₈	(1457,1459) ₉
(3819,3821) ₇	(4707,4709) ₈	(2915,2917) ₉

【The Probability Estimation Theorem of “2-c” which Distributed within the Set of Odd Numbers】
The Probability of “2-c” which Distributed within the Set of Odd Numbers is asymptotically at least equal to $P(“2-c”) = \frac{1}{8} = 12.5\%$.

∴ The “2-c” is generated from the pair of odd integers $(n, 2n-3), (n, 2n+3), (n, 8n-3)$ and $(n, 8n+3)$

∴ When $n \rightarrow \infty$, The Probability of the pair of odd integers $(n, 2n-3), (n, 2n+3), (n, 8n-3)$ and $(n, 8n+3)$ is $P = \frac{n}{8n+3}$

$$\rightarrow n \rightarrow \infty, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n}{8n+3} = \frac{1}{8} = 12.5\%$$

This asymptotic estimate of the probability distribution closely matches the statistical probability within the extended interval, as well as the statistical probability among all odd numbers within the number of iterations.

“3-c” Proof of Existence:

Proof:

If m is an odd number, and $16m+5 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

And $(2m+1)$ is an odd number, and $(2m+1) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$,

And $(16m+11)$ is an odd number, and $(16m+11) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$,

Meet condition $C_{\text{odd}}(16m+5) = C_{\text{odd}}(2m+1) = C_{\text{odd}}(16m+11) = k$, Then:

$$16m+5 \rightarrow \frac{2(16m+5)-1}{3} = \frac{32m+9}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{32m+9}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$2m+1 \rightarrow T_2 = \frac{(2m+1) \cdot 4^2 - 1}{3} = \frac{32m+15}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{32m+15}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$16m+11 \rightarrow \frac{2(16m+11)-1}{3} = \frac{32m+21}{3}; C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{32m+21}{3}\right) = k+1;$$

$$\therefore \frac{32m+21}{3} - \frac{32m+15}{3} = 2; \text{ and } \frac{32m+15}{3} - \frac{32m+9}{3} = 2;$$

∴ $\frac{32m+9}{3}, \frac{32m+15}{3}, \frac{32m+21}{3}$ to become three consecutive odd numbers, and their pure odd count of iterations is equal.

∴ $\exists m$, Let $(\frac{32m+9}{3}, \frac{32m+15}{3}, \frac{32m+21}{3})$ is synchronized odd clusters, It is a “3-c”

And this “3-c” is generated from synchronized odd clusters $(16m+5, 2m+1, 16m+11)$.

Since Key Lemma 1, Key Lemma 2 and Key Lemma 3, As the number of iterations increases, and the odd number “m” is constantly changing, So the synchronized odd clusters: $(16m+5, 2m+1, 16m+11)$, and it will occur frequently, so the “3-c” will occur frequently too

【The Probability Estimation Theorem of “3-c” which Distributed within the Set of Odd Numbers】
 The Probability of “3-c” which Distributed within the Set of Odd Numbers is asymptotically at least equal to $P(“3-c”) = \frac{1}{16} = 6.25\%$.

∴ The “3-c” is generated from synchronized odd clusters $(16m+5, 2m+1, 16m+11)$.

∴ When $m \rightarrow \infty$, The Probability of synchronized odd clusters $(16m+5, 2m+1, 16m+11)$ is $P = \frac{m}{16m+5}$

$$\rightarrow m \rightarrow \infty, \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m}{16m+5} = \frac{1}{16} = 6.25\%$$

This asymptotic estimate of the probability distribution closely matches the statistical probability within the extended interval, as well as the statistical probability among all odd numbers within the number of iterations.

(7) The proof methods for “4-c”, “5-c”, “6-c”, …, “k-c” are the same, so they won’t be elaborated on here.

(8) The Estimation of “k-c” density distribution.

Let’s carefully examine the table below together:

	“2-c”	“3-c”	“4-c”	“5-c”	“6-c”	“7-c”
[1,5)	0					
	0					
[5,21)	0					
	0					

[85,340)	3					
	9.379%					
[85,341)	17					
	13.28%					
[341,1365)	77	10	1			
	15.04%	1.953%	0.19%			
[1365,5461)	357	87	29	13	7	2
	17.43%	4.248%	1.42%	0.635%	0.342%	0.097%
.....

Since The Probability “2-c” is asymptotically at least equal to $P (“2-c”) = \frac{1}{8}$, The Probability “3-c” is asymptotically at least equal to $P (“3-c”) = \frac{1}{16}$, We will speculate that: $P (“4-c”) = \frac{1}{32}$, $P (“5-c”) = \frac{1}{64}$,at least equal to $P (“k-c”) = \frac{1}{2^{k+2}}$

Is it true? In fact the existence of the tiling function will substantially raise this Probability

(9) The proportion of “k-c” and the number of odd numbers it contains within the extended interval

【Definition】 : An odd number that does not form a continuous synchronous cluster with other odd numbers is called an isolated odd number.

table①: $I_7=[5461,21845)$

The order of cluster	Number of clusters	Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters	Odds in cluster/Total odds
2-c	994	1988	24.27%
3-c	289	867	10.58%

4-c	67	268	3.27%
5-c	27	135	1.65%
6-c	3	18	0.22%
7-c	4	28	0.34%
8-c	2	16	0.20%
9-c	1	9	0.11%
Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters		3311	40.42%
Total Number of isolated odd numbers		4881	59.58%

table②:I₈=[21845,87381)

The order of cluster	Number of clusters	Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters	Odds in cluster/Total odds
2-c	4034	8068	24.62%
3-c	1203	3609	11.01%
4-c	322	1288	3.93%
5-c	137	685	2.09%

6-c	51	306	0.93%
7-c	14	98	0.30%
8-c	13	104	0.32%
9-c	7	63	0.19%
10-c	2	20	0.19%
11-c	1	11	0.03%
12-c	1	12	0.04%
Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters		14264	43.53%
Total Number of isolated odd numbers		18507	56.47%

table③:I₉=[87381,349525)

The order of cluster	Number of clusters	Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters	Odds in cluster/Total odds
2-c	16152	32304	24.65%
3-c	5188	15564	11.87%
4-c	1481	5924	4.52%

5-c	669	3345	2.55%
6-c	268	1608	1.23%
7-c	130	910	0.69
8-c	49	392	0.30%
9-c	43	387	0.30%
10-c	25	250	0.19%
11-c	7	77	0.06%
12-c	5	60	0.05%
13-c	5	65	0.05%
14-c	1	14	0.01%
15-c	1	15	0.01%
Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters		60915	46.47%
Total Number of isolated odd numbers		70156	53.53%

table④:I₁₀=[349525,1398101)

The order of cluster	Number of clusters	Total Number of odd numbers in the	Odds in cluster/Total odds
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		clusters	
2-c	63759	127518	24.32%
3-c	21875	64725	12.35%
4-c	6529	26116	4.98%
5-c	3142	15710	3.00%
6-c	1441	8466	1.61%
7-c	674	4718	0.90%
8-c	306	2448	0.47%
9-c	174	1566	0.30%
10-c	149	1490	0.28%
11-c	53	583	0.11%
12-c	35	420	0.08%
13-c	21	273	0.05%
14-c	17	238	0.05%
15-c	8	120	0.02%

16-c	3	48	0.01%
17-c	2	34	0.01%
18-c	4	72	0.01
19-c	2	38	
20-c	1	20	
21-c	1	21	
Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters		254624	48.53%
Total Number of isolated odd numbers		269663	51.43%

table⑤:I₁₁=[1398101,5592405)

The order of cluster	Number of clusters	Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters	Odds in cluster/Total odds
2-c	253897	507794	24.21%
3-c	88624	265872	12.68%
4-c	27641	110564	5.27%
5-c	13932	69660	3.32%

6-c	6383	38298	1.83%
7-c	3307	23149	1.10%
8-c	1608	12864	0.61%
9-c	930	8370	0.40%
10-c	680	6800	0.32%
11-c	350	3850	0.18%
12-c	208	2496	0.12%
13-c	163	2119	0.10%
14-c	87	1218	0.06%
15-c	68	1020	0.05%
16-c	32	512	0.02%
17-c	25	425	0.02%
18-c	22	396	0.01%
19-c	9	171	0.01%

20-c	12	240	0.01%
21-c	10	210	0.01%
22-c	5	110	
23-c	2	46	
24-c	1	24	
25-c	2	50	
26-c	3	78	
33-c	2	66	
40-c	1	40	
Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters		1056442	50.38%
Total Number of isolated odd numbers		1040709	49.62%

table⑥:I₁₂=[5592405,22369621)

The order of cluster	Number of clusters	Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters	Odds in cluster/Total odds
2-c	1001552	2003104	23.88%

3-c	36053	1036159	12.95%
4-c	117344	469376	5.60%
5-c	60558	302790	3.61%
6-c	29103	174618	2.08%
7-c	15425	107975	1.29%
8-c	7844	62752	0.75%
9-c	4856	43704	0.52%
10-c	3312	33120	0.39%
11-c	1811	19921	0.24%
12-c	1157	13884	0.17%
13-c	873	11349	0.14%
14-c	523	7322	0.09%
15-c	371	5565	0.07%
16-c	226	3616	0.04%
17-c	156	2652	0.03%

18-c	109	1962	0.02%
19-c	98	1862	0.02%
20-c	61	1220	0.01%
21-c	75	1575	0.02%
22-c	41	902	0.01%
23-c	28	644	0.01%
24-c	21	504	0.01%
25-c	23	575	0.01%
26-c	17	442	0.01%
27-c	9	243	
28-c	5	140	
29-c	5	1456	
30-c	3	90	
31-c	4	124	

32-c	3	96	
33-c	3	99	
34-c	3	102	
35-c	1	35	
36-c	2	72	
37-c	3	111	
38-c	1	38	
41-c	1	41	
44-c	1	44	
Total Number of odd numbers in the clusters		4358973	51.96%
Total Number of isolated odd numbers		4029641	48.04%

Summarize it

the extended interval	Total Number of isolated odd numbers	Percentage of Total Number of isolated odd numbers	Percentage of Total Number of odd numbers in the synchronized clusters
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$I_7=[5461,21845)$	$2*4^6=8192$	59.58%	40.42%
$I_8=[21845,87381)$	$2*4^7=32768$	56.47%	43.53%
$I_9=[87381,349525)$	$2*4^8=131072$	53.53%	46.47%
$I_{10}=[349525,1398101)$	$2*4^9=524288$	51.43%	48.53%
$I_{11}=[1398101,5592405)$	$2*4^{10}=2097152$	49.62%	50.38%
$I_{12}=[5592405,22369621)$	$2*4^{11}=8388608$	48.04%	51.96%
$I_{13}=[22369621,89478485)$	$2*4^{12}=33554432$		

Analysis and statistical information on the data in the above table: First, the “k-c” in the table does not refer to the nested “k-c” studied earlier. Second, as the extended interval increases, the proportion of odd numbers in the synchronized clusters gradually rises, while the proportion of isolated odd numbers decreases. Third, starting from the 13th extended interval $I_{13}=[22369621,89478485)$, the proportion of odd numbers during continuous synchronous cluster exceeds 50%.

(10) Definition of minimum “k-c” and its statistical data analysis: Here, the synchronized cluster with the smallest numerical value among all “k-c”s is referred to as the minimum “k-c”. The statistical data is shown in the table below:

The minimum “k-c”	The length of The minimum “k-c”	The counts of pure odd iterations
2-c	(49, 51)	7
3-c	(343, 347)	45
4-c	(943, 949)	10
5-c	(2359, 2365)	18

6-c	(1991, 2001)	15
7-c	(2987, 2999)	14
8-c	(7453, 7467)	22
9-c	(7083, 7099)	17
10-c	(36209, 36227)	10
11-c	(57857, 57877)	58
12-c	(57347, 57369)	43
13-c	(202929, 202953)	72
14-c	(331779, 331805)	28
15-c	(298145, 298173)	30
16-c	(467469, 467499)	58
17-c	(709519, 709551)	69
18-c	(530053, 530087)	32
19-c	(843273, 843309)	43
20-c	(596311, 596349)	30

21-c	(1264925, 1264965)	42
22-c	(2836257, 2836289)	32
23-c	(2565633, 2565667)	76
24-c	(4330041, 4330087)	73
25-c	(3848469, 3848517)	75
26-c	(3264429, 326479)	72
32-c	(5772713, 5772773)	73
33-c	(4075907, 4075971)	80
34-c	(6841723, 6841789)	77
35-c	(13756305, 13756373)	77
36-c	(10317293, 10317363)	76
37-c	(14690077, 14690149)	70
38-c	(13019669, 13019743)	72
40-c	(5158597, 5158675)	76
41-c	(6113891, 6113971)	79

44-c	(18341745, 18341831)	78	Data anal ysis: ∴T he mini mu m“2 0-c”
46-c	(22781943, 22782033)	86	
53-c	(30375937, 30376041)	86	
56-c	(24455665,24455775)	79	
.....	

= (596311, 596349) , and $2^{19}=524288, 2^{20}=1048576,$

∴The initial odd number of “20-c”: $596311 < 2^{20}$

The initial odd number of “53-c”:

$$30375937 \div 2^{53} = 30375937 \div (9.00 \times 10^{15}) = 3.3 \times 10^{-7}$$

The initial odd number of “56-c”:

$$24455665 \div 2^{56} = 24455665 \div (7.205 \times 10^{16}) = 3.3939 \times 10^{-10}$$

This indicates that the ability of pure odd-number iterations to reversely generate odd numbers is far beyond our imagination. Previously, we underestimated the distribution probability of “k-c”. As the number of iterations increases, the distribution probability of “k-c” will become higher and higher. However, the length of “k-c” will never exceed half of the initial odd number.

(11)The double "tail" algebraic topological space S(85) exhibits resonance phenomena with S(341).The path of pure odd number iterations of The minimum synchronized cluster“10-c”= (36209, 36227) :

Initial odd number	The path of pure odd number iterations	The iterative path belongs to "tail" algebraic topological space
36209	36209→27157→1273→955→1433→1075→1613→605→227→341→1	S(341)

36211	36211→54317→20369→15277→5729→4297→3223→4835→7253→85→1	S(85)
36213	36213→3395→5093→955→→1433→1075→1613→605→227→341→1	S(341)
36215	36215→54323→81485→30557→11459→17189→3223→4835→7253→85→1	S(85)
36217	36217→27163→40745→30559→45839→68759→103139→154709→1813→85→1	S(85)
36219	36219→54329→40747→61121→45841→34381→12893→4835→7253→85→1	S(85)
36221	36221→13583→20375→30563→45845→2149→403→605→227→341→1	S(341)
36223	36223→54335→81503→122255→183383→275075→412613→77365→7253→85→1	S(85)
36225	36225→27169→20377→15283→22925→8597→403→605→227→341→1	S(341)
36227	36227→54341→10189→3821→1433→1075→1613→605→227→341→1	S(341)

Data analysis: First, all the odd numbers in the iteration paths of these 10 odd numbers represented by "10-c" are composed of the algebraic topological spaces S(85) and S(341) respectively. Second, no any two odd numbers from different algebraic topological spaces with different "tails" are equal. Third, when combined perfectly, these algebraic topological spaces with different "tails" form the 10 consecutive odd numbers within the framework of Peano axioms. Fourth, the total number of iterations, as well as the number of pure odd iterations ,as well as the number of pure even iterations , are all equal for these 10 initial odd numbers.

(12)The strong robustness of "k-c" provides a theoretical basis for the application of the collatz iteration in neural networks. The pairwise disjointness of algebraic topological space about any odd number creates favorable conditions for neural network technology. This is the future prospects for mathematical applications of "k-c".

(13)Another way to classify "k-c": The same tail"k-c" and The different tail"k-c", along with examples:If the k odd numbers in "k-c" converge to the same odd number before "1", then this "k-c" is called a "same-tail "k-c"". If the k odd numbers in "k-c" converge to different odd numbers before "1",

then this "k-c" is called a "different-tail "k-c"".

For example:

"same-tail "k-c"":

①"4-c"=(1495,1501),tail=5;

②"13-c"=(115556353,115556377),tail=341;

③"23-c"=(38356907,38356953),tail=85;

"different-tail "k-c"":

①"2-c"=(232220849,232220851),

232220849tail=5461;

232220851tail=21845;

②"6-c"=(232209841,232209847),

232209841tail=5461;

232209843tail=5461;

232209845tail=5461;

232209847tail=21845;

③"7-c"=(232209905,232209917),

232209905tail=21845;

232209907tail=5461;

232209909tail=21845;

232209911tail=5461;

232209913tail=5461;

232209915tail=5461;

232209917tail=5461;

(14)Example of a classification list where different "tails" converge to "1":

$x_1 = \text{tail}$	The residue classes Modulo 3	Model of reproduction	x_2	The total steps of pure even iterations Converge to "1" from tail
5	$X_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	3	$2 + 2 * 1$
21	$X_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2 + 2 * 2$
85	$X_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	113	$2 + 2 * 3$
341	$X_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	227	$2 + 2 * 4$
1365	$X_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2 + 2 * 5$
5461	$X_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	7281	$2 + 2 * 6$
21845	$X_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	14563	$2 + 2 * 7$
87381	$X_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2 + 2 * 8$
349525	$X_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	466033	$2 + 2 * 9$
1398101	$X_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	932067	$2 + 2 * 10$

5592405	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*11$
22369621	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	29826161	$2+2*12$
89468485	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	59625323	$2+2*13$
357913941	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*14$
1431655765	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	1908874353	$2+2*15$
5726623061	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	3817748707	$2+2*16$
22906492245	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*17$
91625968981	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	122167958641	$2+2*18$
366503875925	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	244335917283	$2+2*19$
1466015503701	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*20$
5864062014805	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	7818749353073	$2+2*21$
23456248059221	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	15637498706147	$2+2*22$
93824992236885	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	$\text{Tail} * 2^k (k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*23$
357299968947541	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	500399958596721	$2+2*24$

1501199875790165	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	1000799917193433	$2+2*25$
6004799503160661	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	Tail* $2^k(k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*26$
24019198012624645	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	32025597350190193	$2+2*27$
96076792050570581	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	64051194700380387	$2+2*28$
384307168202282325	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	Tail* $2^k(k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*29$
153722867280912930 1	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	2049638230412172401	$2+2*30$
614891469123651720 5	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	4099276460824344803	$2+2*31$
245956587649460688 21	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	Tail* $2^k(k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*32$
983826350597842752 85	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	131176870746379033713	$2+2*33$
393530540239137101 141	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	262353693492758067427	$2+2*34$
157412216095654840 4565	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	Tail* $2^k(k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*35$
629648864382619361 8261	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	839531819176825815768 1	$2+2*36$
251859545753047744 73045	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	167906363835365163153 63	$2+2*37$
100743818301219097 892181	$X_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$	No tail	Tail* $2^k(k \rightarrow \infty)$	$2+2*38$

402975273204876391 568725	$X_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	$X_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$	637300364273168522091 633	$2 + 2 * 39$
161190109281950556 6274901	$X_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$	$X_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$	107460072854633704418 3267	$2 + 2 * 40$
$X_i = \frac{4^n - 1}{3}$	$2 + 2n$

(15) Since the range of natural numbers we typically use is too small, it's impossible to encounter the odd numbers that exist in the algebraic topological spaces generated by very large tail numbers. Nor can we detect the even numbers formed from these odd numbers, let alone observe the property of pairwise disjoint between these natural numbers generated by algebraic topological spaces of distinct tail numbers, that is, the algebraic topological spaces generated by distinct tail numbers have closure property. For example, the smallest odd number generated by a tail number of 85 is 75; the smallest odd number generated by a tail number of 341 is 151; the smallest odd number generated by a tail number of 5461 is 7281; the smallest odd number generated by a tail number of 21845 is 14653; In theory, the number of natural numbers in each algebraic topological space generated by a given tail number is the same. But when the tail number is large, the corresponding algebraic topological space contains larger natural numbers. When these numbers are mixed together, they create what could be called "chaos" among the natural numbers. Within a smaller range, most natural numbers are those generated by a tail number of 5, so it seems like everything we see consists of numbers of the type of convergent "5→1". However, examples like 75, 151, 7281, and 14653 clearly demonstrate the differences between the algebraic topological spaces created by different tail numbers. The type of convergent:

$75 \rightarrow 85 \rightarrow "1"; 151 \rightarrow 341 \rightarrow "1"; 7281 \rightarrow 5461 \rightarrow "1"; 14653 \rightarrow 21845 \rightarrow "1"; \dots \dots 21 * 2^n \rightarrow 1; 1365 * 2^n \rightarrow 1; 873 * 2^n \rightarrow 1; 5592405 * 2^n \rightarrow 1; \dots \dots$

Chapter 4: The Vertical Generation of Natural Numbers

Section 1: Definition and Induction of the Parallel Generation Method of Natural Numbers

① Peano Axioms System:

Initial Element 0 or 1; Successor Function $f(n) = n + 1$; Identity Element 1; Starting Point 0 or 1; Once iteration generate a natural number, next iteration generate a natural number, the two natural number are visible, and adjacent. Axiomatic infinity, infinity is inexpressible (Potential infinity).

② Set-Theoretic Generation System:

Initial Element 0 or 1; $0 = \emptyset$; $1 = \{0\}$; $2 = \{0, 1\}$; $n + 1 = n \cup \{n\}$; iteration Function $f(n) = n + 1$; Identity Element 1; Starting Point 0 or 1; Once iteration generate a natural number, next iteration generate a natural number, the two natural number are visible, and adjacent. Axiomatic infinity, infinity is inexpressible (Potential infinity).

③ Generation of natural numbers by the additive semigroup System.

Generate from $1, \mathbb{N} = \{1, 1+1, 1+1+1, \dots\}$, iteration Function $f(n) = n+1$; Identity Element 1; Starting Point 0 or 1; Once iteration generate a natural number, next iteration generate a natural number, the two natural number are visible, and adjacent. Axiomatic infinity, infinity is inexpressible (Potential infinity).

In summary, these three ways of generating natural numbers are merely described using different mathematical concepts. In reality, they shared characteristic: the successor function $f(n) = n+1$. Therefore, essentially, they represent the same method of generating natural numbers.

【Definition】: Starting from the initial point 1, a sequence of consecutive natural numbers is generated through the successor function $f(n) = n+1$. This method of generation is known as the parallel generation mode of natural numbers.

Section 2: The Vertical Generation of Natural Numbers

【Definition】: Starting from point 1, the infinite tillering function $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ is used to generate countless odd numbers by one iteration. classification of odd numbers modulo 3 modulo 3 : $x_i \equiv 0, 1, 2 \pmod{3}$, Among them first filtered cease reproduction odd numbers: $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, And then select the reproductive odd numbers: $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$. The reproductive odd numbers are used to produce offspring odd numbers through both expansion-based reproduction $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; (“expansion reproduction”) and contraction-based reproduction $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$; (“contraction reproduction”). This process is repeated indefinitely, generated the set of all odd natural numbers. From each odd number (which called stem number), The all even numbers are generated using the leaf function $L(x) = x * 2^k$ (x is odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$), generated even numbers (which called leaf number). Then generated the set of all even natural numbers. This method of generating mode of natural numbers is called vertical generation.

Comparison Table of Basic Principles between Parallel Line Generation and Perpendicular Line Generation in Natural Numbers:

	the parallel generation mode	The vertical generation mode
Initial Element	0 or 1	1
Identity Element	1	1

Starting Point	0 or 1	1
Generate functions	Successor $f(n)=n+1$	<p>①the infinite tillering function $f^n(x)=\frac{3x+1}{3}*4^{n-\frac{1}{3}}$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty$);</p> <p>②classification of odd numbers modulo 3 modulo 3 :$x_i \equiv 0, 1, 2 \pmod{3}$;</p> <p>③Select the odd numbers:$x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$ as the reproductive odd numbers;</p> <p>④$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; (“expansion reproduction”);</p> <p>$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$; (“contraction reproduction”)</p> <p>⑤This process(①②③④) is repeated indefinitely, generated the set of all odd natural numbers</p> <p>⑥The all even numbers are generated using the leaf function $L(x)=x*2^k$(x is odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$)</p>
Mathematical operations used with generate natural numbers	Addition	Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication, Division, Exponentiation, modulo 3 classification operation.
Counts of natural numbers by Once iteration generate	1	<p>Trough the reproductive odd number :1; Trough the infinite tillering function: infinitely many odd numbers;</p> <p>Trough the leaf function: infinitely many even numbers</p>
The visible of next natural number by iteration	Visible and Adjacent	<p>Visible and The value range of the next odd number : $\frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$ or $\frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; Range Approximates to $\frac{4}{3}$ or $\frac{2}{3}$;</p>

generated		Range of the two adjacent infinite tilling Odd number : $x \rightarrow 4x+1$; Range of the two adjacent infinite leaf number: $x \rightarrow 2x$;
Expression mode of infinity	Asymptotic and Limit $\rightarrow \infty$	Asymptotic and Limit $\rightarrow \infty$
Is it Axiomatic for infinity?	Axiomatic infinity	Axiomatic infinity
The number of iterations required to reach infinity	Infinitely many times	Only one generated iterations times, and by the infinite tilling function .
Is it visible at infinity?	Invisible but it feel very far to infinity.	Invisible, but it feel very close to infinity.
The properties of infinity	Potential infinity	Potential infinity and not actual infinity
Can infinity be classified?	Can not be classified	Can be classified

【The Theorem of every natural number can be generated by the vertical generation method】

Proof: For any natural number x :

If x is even number, Then Through the inverse function of an k -th leaf function $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k}$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$, until $\frac{x}{2^k}$ is integer), any even number can be uniquely mapped to its corresponding odd number. This mode of classification is comprehensive and non-missing for all even numbers, so it is sufficient to cover all cardinal numbers.

If x is odd number, Then Through the decision function $x \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ or $x \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$,

$x \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \rightarrow x$ is a tilling odd number; $\rightarrow x \rightarrow$ By the reverse tracing tilling function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$

$x \rightarrow$ back to its corresponding seed odd number $x_i \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8}$.

If $x \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \rightarrow$ then $x = 8n + 1 \rightarrow 3x + 1 = 3(8n + 1) + 1 \rightarrow x = \frac{3(2n+1)+1}{3} * 4^1 - \frac{1}{3}$.

If $x \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \rightarrow$ then $x = 8n + 3 \rightarrow 3x + 1 = 3(8n + 3) + 1 \rightarrow x = \frac{3(8n+3)+1}{3} * 4^0 - \frac{1}{3}$.

If $x \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \rightarrow$ then $x = 8n + 7 \rightarrow 3x + 1 = 3(8n + 7) + 1 \rightarrow x = \frac{3(8n+7)+1}{3} * 4^0 - \frac{1}{3}$.

So $x \equiv 1, 3, 7 \pmod{8} \rightarrow x$ is a seed odd number; This mode of classification is comprehensive and non-missing for all odd numbers.

By such way, all odd numbers can be classified into tillering odd number or seed odd number; This mode of classification is comprehensive and non-missing for all odd numbers, so it is sufficient to cover all cardinal numbers.

For every tillering odd number x , Through the inverse tiller function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$ (until $\frac{x-1}{4}$ is odd integer), x can trace a tillering odd number back to its corresponding seed odd number.

For every seed odd number x , Through the classification of modulo 3: $x_i \equiv 0, 1, 2 \pmod{3}$, This mode of classification is comprehensive and non-missing for all odd numbers, so it is sufficient to cover all cardinal numbers.

For every seed odd number x , Select the odd numbers: $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$ as the reproductive odd numbers;

$x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; (“expansion reproduction”);

$x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$; (“contraction reproduction”)

$x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow$ nonexistence- x_{i+1} (“stopping reproduction, only tiller”)

This mode of reproduction (including tillering) classification is comprehensive and non-missing for all odd numbers, so it is sufficient to cover all cardinal numbers.

Since every even number can be expressed as $x * 2^k$ (where x is any odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$);

every seed odd number can be expressed as: $\frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$ or $\frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$;

every tillering odd number can be expressed as: $\frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3} * 4^n$ or $\frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3} * 4^n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}, n \rightarrow \infty$);

This mode of expression is comprehensive and non-missing for all odd numbers, so it is sufficient to cover all cardinal numbers.

There is no one natural number does not contain these structures. So every natural number can be generated by the vertical generation method. This is a proof with structure .

Section 3: Characteristics of the vertical generation method of natural numbers:

Initial Element 1; The infinite tiling function $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ (x is odd number $n \rightarrow \infty$) ; Identity Element 1; Starting Point 1; classification of odd numbers modulo 3 : $x_i \equiv 0, 1, 2 \pmod{3}$; Among them ,first filtered cease reproduction odd numbers: $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, And then select the reproductive odd numbers: $x_i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}$. The reproductive odd numbers are used to produce offspring odd numbers through both expansion-based reproduction $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; (“expansion reproduction”) and contraction-based reproduction $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$; (“contraction reproduction”). This process is repeated indefinitely, generated the set of all odd natural numbers. From each odd number (which called stem number) ,The all even numbers are generated using the leaf function $L(x) = x * 2^k$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$), generated even numbers (which called leaf number) . Then generated the set of all even natural numbers. One reproduction generate an odd number (which is seed number), Then tiling to countless odd numbers are distributed in the phase space of seed number by the infinite tiling function $f^n(x) = \frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}$ (x is odd number $n \rightarrow \infty$) ,So the infinity is not defined axiomatically, but rather structurally visible. So infinity is expressible (Actual infinity). The residue modulo 3 of the odd number (which is seed number) by next reproduction generate is unpredictable, but its range can be known: $\frac{4}{3}$ or $\frac{2}{3}$. This is not chaotic behavior of collatz iteration.

Section 4: Manifestations of "Verticality" in the Generation of Verticality of Natural Numbers

(1) The visibility of the next natural number generated, the certainty of the value range of the next natural number. According to Lemma 6 ,and the disjointness of the element that belong to algebraic topological spaces of odd seeds, and Convergence of Pure Odd-Number Iterations ,it is possible to determine the number of iterations required to generate the next odd number.

classification of odd numbers modulo 3 : $x_i \equiv 0, 1, 2 \pmod{3}$; Then:

① $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \rightarrow$ cease reproduction

② $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$; (“expansion reproduction”)

③ $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \rightarrow x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$; (“contraction reproduction”)

∴ The next odd number is visibility; The value range of the next odd number is certainty; For tiling odd number it can be hold by the reversible tracing function $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$. For leaf number it can be hold

by the reversible tracing function $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k}$.

(2) The seed odd number infinite tillering to $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [\frac{3x+1}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3}] = \infty$ (x is odd number), this is exponentially visible and expressible.

For example: generate odd number $\frac{3 * 1+1}{3} * 4^{10000} - \frac{1}{3}$. It must by $[\frac{3 * 1+1}{3} * 4^{10000} - \frac{1}{3}]$ times iterations through Successor Function $f(n)=n+1$; but It only by 10000 times iterations through tillering Function, and only 1 times pure odd iterations, because $x_1 = \frac{3 * 1+1}{3} * 4^{10000} - \frac{1}{3}$.

(3) Generated leaf numbers from the stem number to $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x * 2^k = \infty$ by the leaf function $L(x) = x * 2^k$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$), this is exponentially visible and expressible.

For example: generate leaf number $3 * 2^{10000}$. It must by $3 * 2^{10000}$ times iterations through Successor Function $f(n)=n+1$; but It only by 10000 times iterations through leaf Function and only two times pure odd iterations, because $x_2 = 3$.

(4) From Lemma 4 and Lemma 5, it can be concluded that in the vertical generation of natural numbers, when expanding from parent intervals to sub expanded intervals, the generation rate of odd numbers is strictly controlled at 4 times. Moreover, this generation rate maintains the invariance of the number of pure odd number iterations, forming a global-local bijection and a point-to-point one-to-one mapping—no more, no less. On continuous expansion intervals, this exponential growth rate of 4 is remarkably significant. Therefore, for any size of odd number, the number of pure odd number iterations exhibits strict linear growth, rather than being chaotic iteration and unpredictable as previously mentioned. Starting from the initial element "1", an infinite number of odd numbers that are the result of 1st-order pure odd-number iterations are generated through the infinite tillering function. These odd numbers are arranged in an orderly manner within continuous expanded intervals, and they serve as the first odd number in each expanded interval.

Section 5: A Study on the Differences Between Odd and Even Number Generation Methods

We can analogize the way natural numbers are generated to the growth process of wheat. The number "1" serves as the most primitive seed, which, through infinite tillering, gives rise to countless odd numbers that are the result of one-time pure odd number iterations. In forward Collatz iterations, these odd numbers are referred to as "tail numbers." In reverse Collatz iterations, we designate them as the

0-st primitive seed $x_1 = \frac{(3 * 1+1)}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} = 1$ ($n=0$), 1-nd primitive seed $x_1 = \frac{(3 * 1+1)}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} = 5$ ($n=1$), 2-rd primitive seed $x_1 = \frac{(3 * 1+1)}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} = 21$ ($n=2$), and so on, up to the k-th primitive seed $x_1 = \frac{(3 * 1+1)}{3} * 4^n - \frac{1}{3} = 1$ ($k=n-1$).

We know that the tillering of wheat does not equate to reproduction. In fact, it maintains the constancy of wheat's genetic traits and the equivalence between generations. The same applies to odd-numbered

tillering. Since odd numbers correspond to the stems of wheat, they are called “stem numbers,” while even numbers correspond to the leaves, hence they are called “leaf numbers.” The difference is that the series of tillering in wheat is finite, whereas the tillering of odd numbers is infinite. Similarly, the number of leaves in wheat grows finitely, but the leaf function generate leaf numbers has an infinite range. Stems and leaves represent two different forms, and accordingly, stem numbers and leaf numbers have distinct ways of being generated and different algebraic structures. Therefore, in group theory, the set of odd numbers is not closed under addition operation, whereas the set of even numbers is closed under addition operation. The fundamental reason for this difference lies in their distinct ways of generation and algebraic structures, which cannot be explained by group theory.

Section 6: Since the tillering function generates odd numbers at rate of 4 times, The leaf function generates even numbers at rate of 2 times. the generation of natural numbers is progressive. In other words, the process of generating natural numbers incorporate the time dimension. Therefore, we must classify the stems number and leaf number within the interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$.

Section 7: In the interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$, the leaf number is classified according to their count of leaves: $x_i * 2^1$ represents 1-leafed leaf number; $x_i * 2^2$ represents 2-leafed leaf number; $x_i * 2^3$ represents 3-leafed leaf number; and so on. In general, $x_i * 2^k$ represents k-leafed leaf number.

Section 8: In the interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$, The leaf numbers can also be classified based on the stems number of they be generated. This is expressed as the k-leafed leaf number $x_i * 2^k$ resulting from a stem number of x_i . For example, 128 is 7-leafed leaf number produced by the stem number “1”; 48 is 4-leafed leaf number produced by the stem number “3”; and so on.

Section 9, in chronological order, within the interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$, the stems numbers can be divided into with leaves stems numbers and without leaves stems numbers. For example, within interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$, The stems numbers within $1 \leq x_i \leq 2^n$ represents with leaves stems numbers, while The stems numbers within $2^n < x_i \leq 2^{2n}$ represents without leaves stems numbers.

Section 10 【 In the vertical generation of natural numbers, the generating functions: ①“contractive reproduction”: $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$ (x_i is the seed odd number, and: $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$); ②expansion reproduction :

$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$ (x_i is the seed odd number, and: $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$) and: leaf function: $L(x) = x * 2^k$ (where x is an odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$) are precisely inverse functions to the two functions: $f(x) = 3x + 1$ (x is an odd number) and $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k}$ (x is an even number, until $\frac{x}{2^k}$ is odd number) in Collatz’s forward iteration. 】

First, from stem numbers to leaf numbers, the leaf function: $L(x) = x * 2^k$ (where x is an odd number, $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \rightarrow \infty$) is inverse function to the piecewise function: $L^{-1}(x) = \frac{x}{2^k}$ (x is an even number, until $\frac{x}{2^k}$ is odd number) in Collatz’s forward iteration.

Second, the reproduction functions ①“contractive reproduction”: $x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 2 - 1}{3}$ (x_i is the seed odd number, and: $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$) and ②“expansion reproduction” :

$x_{i+1} = \frac{x_i * 4 - 1}{3}$ (x_i is the seed odd number, and: $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$) for odd numbers are inverse functions to the

piecewise function $f(x)=3x+1$ in Collatz's forward iteration.

$$\frac{x_i^* 2^{-1}}{3} \rightarrow f(x)=3x+1 \rightarrow x_i^* 2^1(\text{primary leaf number}) \rightarrow (\div 2^1) \rightarrow x_i$$

$$\frac{x_i^* 4^{-1}}{3} \rightarrow f(x)=3x+1 \rightarrow x_i^* 2^2(\text{secondary leaf number}) \rightarrow (\div 2^2) \rightarrow x_i$$

Thus, Collatz's forward iteration and the vertical generation of natural numbers form two one-to-one mappings, which explains why Collatz's forward iteration can converge back to "1". This is the explanation of reason from a functional perspective of generated natural numbers.

Third, in Collatz's forward iteration, if, in 1937, Mr. Collatz placed the inverse function of the tiling function: $f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4}$ (until $\frac{x-1}{4}$ is seed odd number) —before function $f(x)=3x+1$, Then the tiling odd numbers within the iteration path will be screened out by the inverse function; Then the seed odd numbers that remaining can be seen clearly. Additionally, The odd numbers as kind of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ will also appear, and the "hailstone" phenomenon would eliminate during iteration path by the inverse function: $f^{-n}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4^n}$. The oscillation amplitude of these seed odd numbers would be limited to two

values: $x_{i+1} \rightarrow \frac{x_i^* 2^{-1}}{3}$ and $x_{i+1} \rightarrow \frac{x_i^* 4^{-1}}{3}$. Perhaps this conjecture has been proven early. For example:

$$61 \rightarrow f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow 15 \rightarrow f(x) = 3x+1 \rightarrow 46 \rightarrow \div 2^1 \rightarrow 23 \rightarrow f(x) = 3x+1 \rightarrow 70 \rightarrow 2^1 \rightarrow 35 \rightarrow f(x) = 3x+1 \rightarrow 106 \rightarrow 2^1 \rightarrow 53 \rightarrow f^{-2}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4^2} \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow f(x) = 3x+1 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 2^1 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow f^{-1}(x) = \frac{x-1}{4} \rightarrow 1.$$

【Section 11】 The chaos of the collatz iteration can be entirely explained by the vertical generation method of natural numbers.

(1) Extreme sensitivity to the initial value. This is mainly because each initial value belongs to a different algebraic topological space associated with a particular seed odd number, and these algebraic topological spaces are closed. If two initial values belong to different algebraic topological spaces corresponding to different tail odd numbers, their forward iteration paths will never intersect. If they belong to the same algebraic topological space associated with a particular tail odd number, then their paths will intersect at some point corresponding to that seed odd number.

(2) Nonlinearity and discontinuous jumps. Countless leaf numbers is generated by a stem number, which follows a linear pattern. However, the way stem numbers are generated itself follows a non-linear pattern based on modulo 3 classification. Odd and even branches cannot be differentiated mathematically, due to this difference in how stem numbers and leaf numbers are produced. Their algebraic structures differ, resulting in different topological structures that cannot be analyzed using continuous mathematical tools. The $(3x+1)$ formula creates a pseudo-random numerical evolution because it represents the inverse functions of two different odd-number generating functions: namely, an expansion-based reproduction pattern and a contraction-based reproduction pattern. These two

patterns are organized according to modulo 3 classification of odd numbers. Since modulo 3 classification differs from modulo 2 classification, it's impossible to predict the remainder properties of the next odd number when these patterns alternate. Nevertheless, overall, the probability of $x_i \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and $x_i \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ occurring is equal. Therefore, this pseudo-randomness can still be controlled with a 50% probability.

(3) Explosive oscillations, without monotonicity, boundaries, or periodicity. The reason is all odd numbers does not classified into “tillering odd numbers” or “seed odd numbers”. Infinite tillering odd numbers are the main cause of these explosive oscillations. We've already proven the convergence of pure odd number iterations, which indicates its monotonicity. The thresholds for both “contractive reproduction” and “expansion reproduction” are fixed, indicating that the iteration is bounded. The reason of unbounded is caused by Infinite tillering odd numbers, but precisely controllable and what we hope to see. Moreover, 1-order tillering function can map all odd numbers from the parent expansion interval to the sub-expansion intervals. thereby maintaining the constancy of the number of iterations—a perfection form of expression of periodicity.

(4) Unpredictability and computational complexity. Unpredictability is strictly controlled by iterative upper bound functions, with the exception of odd numbers for which the escape rate approaches 0. Computational complexity has been formulated as an algorithmic formula related to the vertical generation of natural numbers.

(5) Statistical law coexist with microscopic chaos. At the macroscopic level, The total iterations steps $\approx C \cdot \lg n$, the proportion of even steps $\log_2 3 \approx 1.585$, conforms to the formulaic calculations used in vertical generation methods. Microscopically, however, the complexity of each iteration's branches is random and unpredictable. This can be calculated using The count of hailstone amplitude formula for an odd number, with precision up to the next odd number, achieving zero-error calculation, and get this result is not by the forward iterations try to compute. While there's a fractal/self-similar structure, no comprehensive analytical formula exists for it. This issue is resolved through 1-order tillering function to control over the continuously extended intervals, ensuring a one-to-one mapping between the parent extended intervals to the subextended intervals (one-fourth of the odd numbers). The inheritance of pure odd iteration counts creates a bijection from the global to the local scale. Fractal/self-similar structures are formed by expanding a parent region and mapping it entirely to a child region through 1-order tillering function. This represents not a chaotic phenomenon, but rather a strict one-to-one mapping relationship between the continuous parent and child regions.

【Section 12】 In the vertical generation of natural numbers, The ultimate iterative odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ can not to continue reproduce .It give rise to the meta-reflection on mathematical of pure odd number iterations.

【Theorem】 : Any prime number is not the largest counts of pure odd number iterations in an algebraic topological space of a seed number .

Proof:

∴ The ultimate iterative odd numbers of $x_i \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ can not to continue reproduce ,it is the largest counts of pure odd number iterations in an algebraic topological space of a seed number .And any

prime number is not the odd number characterized by $x_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, so Any prime number is not the largest counts of pure odd number iterations in an algebraic topological space of a seed number ,it can be reproduced continuously .

We analyze all prime numbers within the extended interval ,range [1,5952405]as follows:

①There all are 386700 prime numbers,among them ,There all are 96680 1-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 25.00%,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

②Among them ,There all are 24185 2-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 24.99%among the 1-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

③Among them ,There all are 6078 3-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 25.1%among the 2-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

④Among them ,There all are 1529 4-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 25.1%among the 3-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

⑤Among them ,There all are 380 5-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 24.80%among the 4-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

⑥Among them ,There all are 99 6-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 26.00%among the 5-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

⑦Among them ,There all are 27 7-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 27.2%among the 6-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

⑧Among them ,There all are 5 8-order tillering prime numbers,percentage ratio is 18.51%among the 7-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

⑨Among them ,There all are only one 9-order tillering prime number,percentage ratio is 20.00%among the 8-order tillering prime numbers,equals to $\frac{1}{4}$;

Key finding: $7 \rightarrow T_{10}=7689557$ is a 10-order tillering prime number, and its “tail” is 5;

Key finding: $113 \rightarrow T_6=464213$ is a 6-order tillering prime number, and its “tail” is 85;

The above data shows that: First, the low of distribution about the “seed odd numbers” and “tillering

odd numbers”are identical within the all of ordinary odd numbers or within the all prime numbers. Second, although prime numbers are special cases of odd numbers, they do not exhibit any special structures or characteristics in the iteration process involving purely odd numbers. In other words, the rules governing the Kolatz iteration of prime numbers are the same as those for ordinary odd numbers. Therefore, studying the Kolatz iteration of very large prime numbers has little practical value or theoretical significance. Third, the “tail theory” related to iterations of purely odd numbers still holds true for prime numbers, making it valuable from both practical and mathematical perspectives.

Section 13: In interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$, Mersenne numbers can be divided into those with odd exponents and those with even exponents. Interestingly, Mersenne numbers with odd exponents happen to be the largest stems number of “leaved stems” in interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$, while those with even exponents are the largest stems number of “leafless stems”. Therefore, we classify Mersenne numbers as those with odd exponents and those with even exponents within interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$. It can also be referred to as 2^n-1 (n is odd number):the with leaves stems number of maximum stems number in the interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$; 2^n-1 (n is even number):the without leaves stems number of maximum stems number in the interval $[1, 2^{2n}]$.

Section 14: **【The theorem of Mersenne numbers’s Iterative trend and Characteristics】** The iterative trend and characteristic of Mersenne numbers is that the first part shows a single upward trend, with first peak value behind it (It could be the peak as well), the latter part shows a single downward trend. Let 2^n-1 (n is odd number) denote a Mersenne number with an odd exponent. Then $2^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number) represents a Mersenne number with an even exponent; they are consecutive Mersenne numbers. For any two consecutive Mersenne number, the The probability of $C_{\text{odd}}(2^n-1)=C_{\text{odd}}(2^{n+1}-1)$ is about $\frac{7}{12}$. Let the symbol $C_t(n)$ denote the total number of iterations for odd numbers n. Thus, it follows that $C_{\text{odd}}(2^n-1)=C_{\text{odd}}(2^{n+1}-1)$ and $C_t(2^n-1)+1=C_t(2^{n+1}-1)$

Proof:

Let 2^n-1 (n is odd number), by forward iterations \rightarrow

$3(2^n-1)+1=3*2^n-3+1=3*2^n-2$; Since only one factor as 2^1 within it.

$\rightarrow(3*2^n-2)\div 2^1=3*2^{n-1}-1$; Then once more by forward iterations \rightarrow

$\rightarrow 3(3*2^{n-1}-1)+1=3^2*2^{n-1}-3+1=3^2*2^{n-1}-2$; As the same way, only one factor as 2^1 within it. Then once more by forward iterations \rightarrow

$(3^2*2^{n-1}-2)\div 2^1=3^2*2^{n-2}-1 \rightarrow$ So on continue until to $3^{n-1}*2^1-1$;

And there are counts of “n-1” times pure odd number iterations were consumed from 2^n-1 (n is odd number) to $3^{n-1}*2^1-1$.

Let $2^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number), As the same way, $2^{n+1}-1 \rightarrow 3^n*2^1-1$;

And there are counts of “n” times pure odd number iterations were consumed from $2^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number) to 3^n*2^1-1 .

①The next we proof the odd number $x_i=3^{n-1}*2^1-1$ (n is odd number)

By forward iterations $\rightarrow[3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1]$,Its only even factor is 4.

$$[3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1]=3^n*2^1-2=(2+1)^n*2^1-2=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2+c-n^{n-1}*2^1+c-n^n*2^0]*2^1-2$$

$$=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2+2n+1]*2^1-2$$

$$=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1$$

$$+2n*2^1+1*2^1-2$$

$$=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1+2n*2^1$$

$$=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1+4n$$

∴n is odd number,

∴ Although for $[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1$ even factor is 8, but for $4n$ only even factor is 4.

∴ For the even number $[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1+4n$, The only even factor is 4.

∴ For the even number $[3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1]$, The only even factor is 4.

∴ The odd number $x_i=3^{n-1}*2^1-1$ (n is odd number), By forward iterations $(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)\rightarrow[3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1]\div 4\rightarrow\frac{3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1}{4}$ is an odd integer .

And for the odd number $\frac{3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1}{4}$, there are counts of “n-1”+1=“n” times pure odd number

iterations were consumed from 2^n-1 (n is odd number) to $\frac{3(3^{n-1}*2^1-1)+1}{4}$.

②The next we proof the odd number $x_i=3^n*2^1-1$ (n is odd number) is a tiling odd number:

$$x_i=3^n*2^1-1=(2+1)^n*2^1-1=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2+c-n^{n-1}*2^1+c-n^n*2^0]*2^1-1$$

$$=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2$$

$$+2n+1]*2^1-1$$

$$=[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1$$

$$+2n*2^1+1*2^1-1.$$

∴ For the even number $[c-n^0*2^n+c-n^1*2^{n-1}+c-n^2*2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2}*2^2]*2^1$, even factor is 8, Let:

$$[c-n^0 2^n + c-n^1 2^{n-1} + c-n^2 2^{n-2} + \dots + c-n^{n-2} 2^2] * 2^1 = 8m \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}),$$

$$\text{Then: } x_i = 3^{n*2^1-1} = 8m + 2n * 2^1 + 1 * 2^1 - 1 = 8m + 4n + 1 = 4(2m+n) + 1;$$

∴ n is odd number, ∴ $2m+n$ is odd number too,

∴ $4(2m+n)+1$ is a tillering odd number,

∴ $x_i = 3^{n*2^1-1}$ is a tillering odd number,

And for the odd number 3^{n*2^1-1} , there are counts of “ n ” times pure odd number iterations were consumed from $2^{n+1}-1$ ($n+1$ is even number) to 3^{n*2^1-1} .

$$\textcircled{3} \text{ And : } 4 * \left(\frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4} \right) + 1 = 3^{n*2^1-1}, \frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4} \text{ is an odd number, } 3^{n*2^1-1} \text{ is an odd number,}$$

Since **【 Inference 1 】** : Any tillering odd number and its corresponding seed odd number has the same Trajectory Suffixes, denoted as: $T_k = TS = x_0$ (from x_0).

∴ For Mersenne number 2^n-1 (n is odd number) and Mersenne number $2^{n+1}-1$ ($n+1$ is even number), starting from $\frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4}$ and 3^{n*2^1-1} , their has the same Trajectory Suffixes, denoted as:

$$\frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4} = TS = 3^{n*2^1-1}$$

$$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4}\right) = C_{\text{odd}}(3^{n*2^1-1}).$$

Since the odd number $\frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4}$, there are counts of “ $n-1$ ”+1=“ n ” times pure odd number iterations were consumed from 2^n-1 (n is odd number) to $\frac{3(3^{n-1} * 2^{1-1}) + 1}{4}$, and the odd number 3^{n*2^1-1} , there are counts of “ n ” times pure odd number iterations were consumed from $2^{n+1}-1$ ($n+1$ is even number) to 3^{n*2^1-1} , so their total counts of pure odd iteratins is equal.

$$\therefore C_{\text{odd}}(2^n-1) = C_{\text{odd}}(2^{n+1}-1).$$

Since 3^{n*2^1-1} is a tillering odd number, for the Mersenne number $2^{n+1}-1$ ($n+1$ is even number), its counts of pure even iteratins is one more times, and its total counts iteratins is one more times too.

$$\therefore C_i(2^n-1) + 1 = C_i(2^{n+1}-1).$$

④ According to **【 Key Lemma 1 】** : If two consecutive odd numbers in a phase space are $x_{i-1,1} = n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ and $x_{i-1,2} = 4n+1 \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ (which occurs frequently), then their corresponding sub-generation iteration odd numbers must satisfy the equation $x_i = 2x_i + 1$.

Its converse can be expressed as : for odd number x_i and $2x_i+1$,

its counts of pure odd number iterations is equal as $C_{\text{odd}}(x_i) = C_{\text{odd}}(2x_i + 1)$. The probability that this converse is true proposition is about $\frac{7}{12}$. This is similar to the converse of Fermat's little theorem.

∴ For any two odd numbers pair such form as $(n, 2n+1)$, The probability of $C_{\text{odd}}(n) = C_{\text{odd}}(2n+1)$ is about $\frac{7}{12}$.

$$\because 2^{n+1} - 1 = 2(2^n - 1) + 1$$

∴ For any two consecutive Mersenne number, the probability of $C_{\text{odd}}(2^n - 1) = C_{\text{odd}}(2^{n+1} - 1)$ is about $\frac{7}{12}$.

Let's take a look at the table below:

Mersenne numbers	Parity of the exponent	Total number of iterations	The counts of Pure odd number iterations	The upper bound of Pure odd number iterations	Does it exceed The upper bound
$2^1 - 1$	Odd number				
$2^2 - 1$	Even number	7	2	13	
$2^3 - 1$	Odd number	16	5	27	
$2^4 - 1$	Even number	17	5	27	
$2^5 - 1$	Odd number	106	39	39	
$2^6 - 1$	Even number	107	39	39	

2^7-1	Odd number	46	15	51	
2^8-1	Even number	47	15	51	
2^9-1	Odd number	61	20	63	
$2^{10}-1$	Even number	62	20	63	
$2^{11}-1$	Odd number	156	55	74	
$2^{12}-1$	Even number	157	55	74	
$2^{13}-1$	Odd number	158	55	86	
$2^{14}-1$	Even number	159	55	86	
$2^{15}-1$	Odd number	129	43	98	
$2^{16}-1$	Even number	130	43	98	
$2^{17}-1$	Odd number	224	79	110	
$2^{18}-1$	Even number	225	79	110	

$2^{19}-1$	Odd number	177	60	122	
$2^{20}-1$	Even number	178	60	122	
$2^{21}-1$	Odd number	303	108	133	
$2^{22}-1$	Even number	304	108	133	
$2^{23}-1$	Odd number	473	173	145	Yes
$2^{24}-1$	Even number	474	173	145	Yes
$2^{25}-1$	Odd number	444	161	157	Yes
$2^{26}-1$	Even number	445	161	157	Yes
$2^{27}-1$	Odd number	384	137	169	
$2^{28}-1$	Even number	385	137	169	
$2^{29}-1$	Odd number	448	161	180	
$2^{30}-1$	Even number	449	161	180	

$2^{31}-1$	Odd number	450	161	192	
$2^{32}-1$	Even number	451	161	192	
$2^{33}-1$	Odd number	527	190	204	
$2^{34}-1$	Even number	528	190	204	
$2^{35}-1$	Odd number	529	190	216	
$2^{36}-1$	Even number	530	190	216	
$2^{37}-1$	Odd number	531	190	227	
$2^{38}-1$	Even number	532	190	227	
$2^{39}-1$	Odd number	533	190	239	
$2^{40}-1$	Even number	534	190	239	
$2^{41}-1$	Odd number	535	190	251	
$2^{42}-1$	Even number	536	190	251	

$2^{43}-1$	Odd number	586	209	263	
$2^{44}-1$	Even number	587	209	263	
$2^{45}-1$	Odd number	588	209	275	
$2^{46}-1$	Even number	589	209	275	
$2^{47}-1$	Odd number	590	209	286	
$2^{48}-1$	Even number	591	209	286	
$2^{49}-1$	Odd number	592	209	298	
$2^{50}-1$	Even number	593	209	298	
$2^{51}-1$	Odd number	594	209	310	
$2^{52}-1$	Even number	595	209	310	
$2^{53}-1$	Odd number	852	308	322	
$2^{54}-1$	Even number	853	308	322	

$2^{55}-1$	Odd number	598	209	334	
$2^{56}-1$	Even number	599	209	334	
$2^{57}-1$	Odd number	856	308	345	
$2^{58}-1$	Even number	857	308	345	
$2^{59}-1$	Odd number	858	308	357	
$2^{60}-1$	Even number	859	308	357	
$2^{61}-1$	Odd number	860	308	369	
$2^{62}-1$	Even number	861	308	369	
$2^{63}-1$	Odd number	862	308	381	
$2^{64}-1$	Even number	863	308	381	
$2^{65}-1$	Odd number	856	305	392	

$2^{66}-1$	Even number	857	305	392	
$2^{67}-1$	Odd number	729	255	404	
$2^{68}-1$	Even number	730	255	404	
$2^{69}-1$	Odd number	930	332	416	
$2^{70}-1$	Even number	931	332	416	
$2^{71}-1$	Odd number	932	332	428	
$2^{72}-1$	Even number	933	332	428	
$2^{73}-1$	Odd number	934	332	439	
$2^{74}-1$	Even number	935	332	439	
$2^{75}-1$	Odd number	1073	385	451	
$2^{76}-1$	Even number	1074	385	451	

$2^{77}-1$	Odd number	938	332	463	
$2^{78}-1$	Even number	939	332	463	
$2^{79}-1$	Odd number	940	332	475	
$2^{80}-1$	Even number	941	332	475	
$2^{81}-1$	Odd number	1446	527	487	Yes
$2^{82}-1$	Even number	1447	527	487	Yes
$2^{83}-1$	Odd number	1448	527	498	Yes
$2^{84}-1$	Even number	1449	527	498	Yes
$2^{85}-1$	Odd number	1450	527	510	Yes
$2^{86}-1$	Even number	1451	527	510	Yes
$2^{87}-1$	Odd number	1359	491	522	

$2^{88}-1$	Even number	1360	491	522	
$2^{89}-1$	Odd number	1454	527	534	
$2^{90}-1$	Even number	1455	527	534	
$2^{91}-1$	Odd number	1456	527	545	
$2^{92}-1$	Even number	1457	527	545	
$2^{93}-1$	Odd number	1458	527	557	
$2^{94}-1$	Even number	1459	527	557	
$2^{95}-1$	Odd number	1460	527	569	
$2^{96}-1$	Even number	1461	527	569	
$2^{97}-1$	Odd number	1462	527	581	
$2^{98}-1$	Even number	1463	527	581	

$2^{99}-1$	Odd number	1464	527	592	
$2^{100}-1$	Even number	1465	527	592	
.....			
$2^{2n-1}-1$	Odd number	$C(2^{2n-1}-1)=i$			
$2^{2n}-1$	Even number	$C(2^{2n}-1)=i+1$			

Statistics Table of Total number of iterations Data source explanation: All of the odd numbers have been verified on the renowned website <https://www.dcode.fr/collatz-conjecture> , confirming the accuracy of the data.

Data analysis: First, the number of pure odd iterations between the Mersenne number 2^n-1 (n is odd number)and the next Mersenne number $2^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number)is equal, with a difference of 1 in total iterations. Second, there are 64 cases where consecutive Mersenne numbers have the same number of pure odd iterations, accounting for 64% of the total. Third, the first phase of iteration for Mersenne numbers shows a single upward trend, with a first peak occurring at this stage. Fourth,among the first 100 Mersenne numbers, it was found that the convergence tail for the two Mersenne numbers $2^{65}-1$ and $2^{66}-1$ is 341, the convergence tail for the rest Mersenne numbers is 5. Fifth, among the first 100 Mersenne numbers, 10 numbers, namely $2^{23 \rightarrow 26}-1$ and $2^{81 \rightarrow 86}-1$, exceed the upper bound of the iteration function in terms of the number of pure odd iterations, accounting for 10% of the total.If this data is placed within continuous expanded intervals, the escape rate is $5/2^{100}$ (Because what's studied here are pure odd number iterations.). Its impact on the accuracy of upper bound function of iterations estimates is virtually zero.Sixth, although Mersenne numbers possess strong 2-adic structure, this structure only determines the iteration pattern for the first half of the path in the Collatz sequence. For the latter half of the path, the iteration follows the usual rules of natural numbers. Extremely few existence of Mersenne numbers that exhibit “escape behavior” clearly illustrates this point. All these findings confirm our previous conclusions.

Section 15 【The theorem on the iterative pattern of Mersenne numbers with base 3】Mersenne numbers with base 3 classification: 3^n-1 (n is odd number) and $3^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number), Correlation iteration number : $C_{\text{odd}}(3^n-1)=C_{\text{odd}}(3^{n+1}-1)+1$; $C_t(3^n-1)=C_t(3^{n+1}-1)+1$.

Proof:①For 3^n-1 (n is odd number),

$$3^n-1=(2+1)^n-1=c-n^0 2^n+c-n^1 2^{n-1}+c-n^2 2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2} 2^2+c-n^{n-1} 2^1+c-n^n 2^0-1=c-n^0 2^n+c-n^1 2^{n-1}+c-n^2 2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2} 2^2+2n+1-1=c-n^0 2^n+c-n^1 2^{n-1}+c-n^2 2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2} 2^2+2n$$

∴ n is an odd number, ∴ $c-n^0 2^n+c-n^1 2^{n-1}+c-n^2 2^{n-2}+\dots+c-n^{n-2} 2^2$ is an even number, 2n only even factor is 2^1 .

∴ $(3^n-1) \div 2^1$ is an odd number, ∴ $\frac{3^n-1}{2}$ is an odd number,

② For 3^n-1 (n is odd number) and $3^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number)

Let: $C_{\text{odd}}\left(\frac{3^n-1}{2}\right)=i, x_i = \frac{3^n-1}{2}$;

∴ $\frac{3^n-1}{2}$ By forward iterations $\rightarrow x_{i-1} = 3 * \frac{3^n-1}{2} + 1 = \frac{3^{n+1}-3}{2} + 1 = \frac{3^{n+1}-1}{2}$;

∴ $3^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number); From the certain perspective of vertical generation method of natural numbers: $3^{n+1}-1$ (n+1 is even number) is an leaf number, and generated by the stem number x_{i-1} ;

∴ No matter by how much times “ $\div 2$ ”, $3^{n+1}-1 \rightarrow x_{i-1}$;

and: $C_{\text{odd}}(x_{i-1})=i-1$, since $C_{\text{odd}}(x_{i-1} * 2^k)=i-1$, ∴ $C_{\text{odd}}(3^{n+1}-1)=i-1$.

And there one times pure odd number iteration from $\frac{3^n-1}{2}$ By forward iterations to $x_{i-1} = 3 * \frac{3^n-1}{2} + 1 =$

$$\frac{3^{n+1}-3}{2} + 1 = \frac{3^{n+1}-1}{2}$$
 ;

∴ The counts of pure even number iterations is equal between 3^n-1 and $3^{n+1}-1$; ∴ $C_t(3^n-1)=C_t(3^{n+1}-1)+1$; $C_{\text{odd}}(3^n-1)=C_{\text{odd}}(3^{n+1}-1)+1$;

Let’s take a look at the table below:

Mersenne numbers of base on 3	Parity of the exponent	Total number of iterations	The counts of Pure odd number iterations	The upper bound of Pure odd number iterations	Does it exceed The upper bound
3^1-1	Odd number				
3^2-1	Even number				

3^3-1	Odd number	10	2		
3^4-1	Even number	9	1		
3^5-1	Odd number	96	34		
3^6-1	Even number	95	33		
3^7-1	Odd number	32	8		
3^8-1	Even number	31	7		
3^9-1	Odd number	43	11		
$3^{10}-1$	Even number	42	10		
$3^{11}-1$	Odd number	134	45		
$3^{12}-1$	Even number	133	44		
$3^{13}-1$	Odd number	132	43		
$3^{14}-1$	Even number	131	42		

$3^{15}-1$	Odd number	99	29		
$3^{16}-1$	Even number	98	28		
$3^{17}-1$	Odd number	190	63		
$3^{18}-1$	Even number	189	62		
$3^{19}-1$	Odd number	139	42		
$3^{20}-1$	Even number	138	41		
$3^{21}-1$	Odd number	261	88		
$3^{22}-1$	Even number	260	87		
$3^{23}-1$	Odd number	427	151		
$3^{24}-1$	Even number	426	150		
$3^{25}-1$	Odd number	394	137		
$3^{26}-1$	Even number	393	136		

$3^{27}-1$	Odd number	330	111		
$3^{28}-1$	Even number	329	110		
$3^{29}-1$	Odd number	390	133		
$3^{30}-1$	Even number	389	132		
$3^{31}-1$	Odd number	388	131		
$3^{32}-1$	Even number	387	130		
$3^{33}-1$	Odd number	461	158		
$3^{34}-1$	Even number	460	157		
$3^{35}-1$	Odd number	459	156		
$3^{36}-1$	Even number	458	155		
$3^{37}-1$	Odd number	457	154		
$3^{38}-1$	Even number	456	153		

$3^{39}-1$	Odd number	455	152		
$3^{40}-1$	Even number	454	151		
$3^{41}-1$	Odd number	453	150		
$3^{42}-1$	Even number	452	149		
$3^{43}-1$	Odd number	500	167		
$3^{44}-1$	Even number	499	166		
$3^{45}-1$	Odd number	498	165		
$3^{46}-1$	Even number	497	164		
$3^{47}-1$	Odd number	496	163		
$3^{48}-1$	Even number	495	162		
$3^{49}-1$	Odd number	494	161		
$3^{50}-1$	Even number	493	160		

$3^{51}-1$	Odd number	492	159		
$3^{52}-1$	Even number	491	158		
$3^{53}-1$	Odd number	746	256		
$3^{54}-1$	Even number	745	255		
$3^{55}-1$	Odd number	488	155		
$3^{56}-1$	Even number	487	154		
$3^{57}-1$	Odd number	742	252		
$3^{58}-1$	Even number	741	251		
$3^{59}-1$	Odd number	740	250		
$3^{60}-1$	Even number	739	249		
.....
$3^{2n-1}-1$	Odd number	k	i		

$3^{2^n}-1$	Even number	k-1	i-1		
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Table data analysis: Among the first 60 Mersenne numbers with base 3, both the number of pure odd iterations and the total number of iterations satisfy the theorem. None of the pure odd iteration counts exceeded the estimated value given by the upper bound formula. This indicates that the special algebraic structure of Mersenne numbers with base 3 results in relatively small iteration counts.

【Section 16】 The addition rule for the stem numbers and leaf numbers

① Let a stem number is S_1 , Another stem number is S_2 , So:

$$S_1 + S_2 = L_5 \quad (L_5 \text{ is a leaf number, and } L_5 = S_5 * 2^k, k \geq 1).$$

$$\because k \geq 1 \therefore S_5 < \max(S_1, S_2)$$

Addition of two stem numbers, the sum is a leaf number. Moreover, the stem number which generate this leaf number does not exceed the max of the two addends. In other words, a leaf number can be represented as the sum of two stem numbers that are smaller than it.

② Let a stem number is S_1 , Let a leaf number is $L_2 = S_2 * 2^j, j \geq 1$, So:

$$S_1 + L_2 = S_1 + S_2 * 2^j = S_3 \quad (S_3 \text{ also is a stem number})$$

$$\therefore S_3 > \max(S_1, L_2).$$

Addition of a stem number and a leaf number, the sum also is a stem number. Moreover, the stem number that as the sum necessarily exceed the max of the two addends. In other words, a stem number can be represented as the sum of a stem number and a leaf number that are smaller than it.

③ Let a leaf number is $L_1 = S_1 * 2^k, k \geq 1$, Another leaf number is $L_2 = S_2 * 2^j, j \geq 1$, So: $L_1 + L_2 = S_1 * 2^k + S_2 * 2^j$, Let: $j \leq k$,

$$\text{then: } L_1 + L_2 = S_1 * 2^k + S_2 * 2^j = 2^j (S_1 * 2^{k-j} + S_2), \text{ If } k=j,$$

$$\text{then: } L_1 + L_2 = S_1 * 2^k + S_2 * 2^j = 2^j (S_1 + S_2); \text{ then continue this operation. If } k \neq j,$$

$$\because k \geq 1, j \geq 1, \therefore k-j \geq 1$$

$$\therefore (S_1 * 2^{k-j} + S_2) > \max(S_1, S_2).$$

Addition of two leaf numbers, the sum is also a leaf number. Moreover, the stem number which generate this leaf number as sum necessarily exceed the max of the stem number which generate two addends. since the ①②, it can be hold: A stem number can be represented as the sum of three stem numbers that are smaller than it.

【Section 17 Stem numbers-Based Sum Representation】 Addition Rule 1 and Addition Rule 3 are Stem

numbers-Based Sum Representation . The difference between it and the Goldbach conjecture lies in whether it's possible to reduce the length of the "stem" to a smaller value, that is, to a prime number.

【Future Work】

(1)The vertical generation of natural numbers is a structural method of creation that is independent of the numbers' values. It relates to the generational relationships between natural numbers and involves operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, exponentiation, modular classification, and modular arithmetic. In group theory, previously, the closure in group theory is satisfied only with respect to the designated operation, Now, in an algebraic topological space of a seed odd number, the closure in group theory is satisfied the operations of the vertical generation of natural numbers, including addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, exponentiation, modular classification, and modular arithmetic. This opens up new perspectives and directions for further research in group theory. Further research can be conducted by examining the operational properties of stem numbers and leaf numbers.

(2)In the vertical generation of natural numbers, the infinite "tillering function" of odd numbers had be discovered, and it possess that preserve the invariance of the number of iterations involving purely odd numbers. Further research into the "tillering function" can shed light on properties of the algebraic topological space which generated by the seed odd numbers , allowing us to establish dynamic models and theories related to these algebraic topological spaces. The infinite phase space associated with leaf counts may seem like a simple reconfiguration of even-number theory at first glance, but it actually reveals the fundamental structural differences between even and odd numbers. This phase space theory is also a type of dynamic model. The distinct structures and properties of these two models are key reasons behind the chaotic behavior of natural numbers. By exploring this approach, we can clarify what's meant by the "chaos" in natural numbers and establish a clear mathematical framework for understanding their randomness.

(3)The discoveries and preliminary studies for the "k-clusters" reveal the intrinsic property between the vertical and parallel ways in which natural numbers are generated. This relationship represents the result of resonance between these two distinct generation methods under certain conditions. Further research on "k-clusters" can be deeply integrated with neural network technology to create a natural neural network system for representing natural numbers. Moreover, the closed nature of the algebraic topological spaces produced by different starting seed odd numbers provides favorable conditions for the development of such neural networks. Finally, "k-clusters"'s strong robustness makes it one of the most powerful sources of controllable energy within neural networks.

(4)In the vertical generation of natural numbers, the precise controllability of infinitely tillering odd numbers and infinite leaf numbers provides a theoretical foundation for applications in computer science involving collatz's pure odd number iteration. The hailstone formula for pure odd number iterations offers new research directions in algorithmics. The uncertainties arising from "expansion reproduction" mode and "contraction reproduction" mode patterns stem from the inconsistency between remainders under modulo 3 and modulo 2 classification, thus opening up new approaches and theoretical frameworks for cryptography.

(5)The upper bound function of purely odd-number iterations provides an estimate for the number of

iterations in the continuous extension interval. The inverse proposition of the theorem regarding the number of iterations required for two consecutive odd numbers to produce another odd number shows that as the data size increases, the probability that this inverse proposition holds also rises. This presents valuable opportunities for collaboration among large computing institutions, serving as a platform for them to showcase their capabilities. It also serves as an important means of verifying the effectiveness of vertical generation methods for natural numbers.

(6)The vertical generation of natural numbers, combined with set theory, group theory, probability theory, measure theory, information theory, control theory, game theory, modular theory, and other fields, provides significant support for the development of number theory.

(7)The pure odd number iterations of natural numbers involves time stamping each stem number and each leaf number. The time stamping the counts of pure odd number iterations of each stem number, The time stamping the counts of pure odd number iterations and the counts of k-order leaf function of each leaf number, from the perspective of mathematical philosophy, the vertical generation of natural numbers incorporates a dimension of time. In this process, time is an inherent aspect of number generation, thereby demonstrating the existence of time itself. This time element increases gradually as both the stem numbers and leaf numbers grows.

Appendix: The counts of pure odd number iterations about Mersenne number:

n	2^n-1	total	counts of iterations
1	1	1	
2	3	3	8
3	7	7	17
4	15	15	18
5	31	31	107
6	63	63	108
7	127	127	47
8	255	255	48
9	511	511	62
10	1023	1023	63
11	2047	2047	157
12	4095	4095	158
13	8191	8191	159
14	16383	16383	160
15	32767	32767	130
16	65535	65535	131
17	131071	131071	225
18	262143	262143	226
19	524287	524287	178
20	1048575	1048575	179
21	2097151	2097151	304
22	4194303	4194303	305
23	8388607	8388607	474

24	16777215	475
25	33554431	445
26	67108863	446
27	134217727	385
28	268435455	386
29	536870911	449
30	1073741823	450
31	2147483647	451
32	4294967295	452
33	8589934591	528
34	17179869183	529
35	34359738367	530
36	68719476735	531
37	137438953471	532
38	274877906943	533
39	549755813887	534
40	1099511627775	535
41	2199023255551	536
42	4398046511103	537
43	8796093022207	587
44	17592186044415	588
45	35184372088831	589
46	70368744177663	590
47	140737488355327	591
48	281474976710655	592
49	562949953421311	593
50	1125899906842621	594